

HOW EFFECTIVE IS THE CORPORATE GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE OF BANGLADESH TO FIT IN THE CURRENT BANKING SYSTEM?

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This dissertation is submitted for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration.

September 2024

Declaration

I declare that this thesis titled " How Effective Is The Corporate Governance Structure Of Bangladesh To Fit In The Current Banking System? " is entirely my own work. It contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which has been accepted for any other degree or diploma at any other educational institution, except where due acknowledgment has been made in the text.

Personal details withheld.

Saddam Hassan Talukder

31/07/2024

Acknowledgement

First and foremost, I express my profound gratitude to Almighty Allah for the strength and wisdom bestowed upon me to complete this research.

I am immensely grateful to my supervisors, Dr. Alloysius Egbulonu, Dr. Karen Meher and Prof. Nazrul, for their invaluable guidance, expertise, and unwavering support throughout this journey. Their insights and dedication have significantly shaped the direction and execution of this thesis.

I also wish to thank the faculty and staff of the School of Business & Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland for their assistance and for providing an enriching academic environment. My gratitude extends to my peers and colleagues who provided both academic collaboration and personal encouragement.

A special note of gratitude goes to my friend, Tanjil Islam, whose motivation and support have been crucial in spurring me further in my research endeavours.

Finally, and most significantly, my deepest gratitude is extended to my parents. This thesis is dedicated to them in honour of the sacrifices they made to teach me the essential lessons of life. I am eternally indebted to every member of my family, especially my wife, Dr Alifa whose endless support and belief in my capabilities have been a constant source of strength and inspiration, and who have stood by me through all the challenges faced during this study. Immense thanks to each of them for their unwavering and unconditional support.

Dedication

This dissertation is dedicated to my late father, Jabbal Ahamed Talukder. His unwavering belief in my potential and his constant encouragement have always guided me.

He always told me, "You can do it," and those words were not merely a statement of encouragement but a beacon that guided me through every challenge. His wisdom, strength, and deep belief in perseverance have left an indelible mark on my character and aspirations. Completing this DBA is not just an academic achievement but a fulfilment of the promise I made to him to always strive for excellence. To my father, who remains my hero and my guiding star—every page of this journey bears your imprint.

Abstract

This thesis investigates the complexities of corporate governance within the banking sector of Bangladesh, critically evaluating its effectiveness in light of international norms and the unique challenges presented by the local context. Employing a rigorous methodological approach that combines quantitative analysis with a detailed literature review, the study examines how various governance mechanisms influence key financial performance indicators, specifically Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

The findings reveal that conventional governance metrics such as board composition and the frequency of meetings do not significantly affect financial performance, challenging prevailing assumptions about their effectiveness. Instead, the research identifies ownership structure and executive compensation as critical factors that substantially impact bank performance. It demonstrates that while director and CEO share ownership negatively affects ROA, a broader public and institutional ownership base positively influences both ROA and ROE, suggesting a complex interplay between different types of ownership and financial outcomes.

This thesis contributes significantly to the academic discourse on corporate governance by providing nuanced insights into the specific conditions of Bangladesh's banking industry. It also offers valuable recommendations for policymakers, regulatory bodies, and banking executives, advocating for governance frameworks that prioritise qualitative over quantitative metrics and adapt to the specific socio-economic conditions of Bangladesh. The recommendations propose enhancing governance practices by adhering to global standards and integrating these standards with local realities to foster a more resilient and responsive banking sector.

Table of Contents

1	Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.1	Introduction.....	1
1.2	Background of the Study	3
1.2.1	The Banking Sector’s Crucial Role in Economic Dynamics.....	3
1.2.2	Vulnerabilities Exposed by Global and Local Banking Failures.....	3
1.2.3	Governance Mechanisms, a strategic lever and Banking Stability.....	4
1.2.4	Regulatory Oversight and Its Implications	5
1.2.5	The Globalisation Challenge.....	5
1.3	Research problem.....	6
1.4	Research gap	8
1.4.1	Limited Focus on Banking Sector Governance:	9
1.4.2	Over-reliance on Ownership structure, Board compositions, and Agency Theory:	10
1.4.3	Ineffectiveness of Regulatory Frameworks:	10
1.4.4	Partial Examination of Governance Elements:	11
1.5	Theoretical Framework.....	12
1.5.1	Agency Theory:	12
1.5.2	Stakeholder Theory:.....	13
1.5.3	Stewardship Theory:	13
1.5.4	Institutional Theory:.....	13
1.5.5	Resource Dependency Theory	14

1.6	Research Methodology	14
1.7	Research Aim, objectives and questions.....	16
1.7.1	Research aim and objectives	16
1.7.2	Main Research Question:	16
1.8	Findings.....	17
1.9	Significance and Contribution of the Study.....	19
1.9.1	Reassessing Board Composition Guidelines:	19
1.9.2	Rethinking Governance Practices:	19
1.9.3	Evaluating Executive Compensation and Ownership Structures such as Director's share:	20
1.9.4	Emphasising Broad-based Ownership:	21
1.9.5	Policy Implications and Future Governance Reforms:	21
2	Chapter two: Literature review	22
2.1	Segment one: historical evolution, conceptual framework, and models, theories, and mechanisms	23
2.1.1	Corporate governance history	23
2.1.2	Defining corporate governance.....	25
2.1.3	Definition of corporate governance for the banking sector	27
2.1.4	Corporate Governance Models	29
2.1.5	Corporate Governance Model of Bangladesh.....	35
2.1.6	Review of corporate governance's theoretical frameworks.....	36
2.1.7	Synthesis of the Theories	64

2.1.8	The Relationship between Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Firm Performance	66
2.2	Empirical literature review on internal corporate governance mechanisms and their relationship with the firm performance	69
2.2.1	Board composition	69
2.2.2	Board meeting frequency	77
2.2.3	Financial and remuneration policy.....	82
2.2.4	Ownership structure	86
2.3	The Case Study of Bangladesh	92
2.3.1	Introduction of Bangladesh from an Economic Perspective.....	92
2.3.2	The Corporate Sector of Bangladesh	95
2.3.3	Bangladesh's Banking Industry	98
2.3.4	Key Features of Bangladesh's Corporate Sector	102
2.3.5	The Development of Corporate Governance in Bangladesh	104
2.3.6	Key Institutional Involvements in Bangladesh's Corporate Governance Reforms	107
2.3.7	Bangladesh Bank:	108
2.3.8	Bangladesh's Banking Regulations	111
2.4	Reviewing the Corporate Governance Code of Bangladesh and the development of hypotheses.....	115
2.4.1	Board size.....	115
2.4.2	Independent Directors in board composition.....	117

2.4.3	Gender Diversity in Board Composition	119
2.4.4	Board meeting frequency	120
2.4.5	Executive Committee Meetings and Bank Performance	122
2.4.6	Audit Committee Meetings and Bank Performance	123
2.4.7	Audit Committee and Its Functions	125
2.4.8	Compensation and Bank Performance.....	127
2.4.9	Ownership Structure of Banks	129
2.5	Conclusion	131
3	Chapter Three: Research Method	133
3.1	Research Aim.....	133
3.2	Research Objectives.....	134
3.3	Research questions and hypotheses	135
3.3.1	Main Research Question:.....	136
3.3.2	Research Hypotheses	137
3.4	Research Design.....	139
3.4.1	Research Philosophy	139
3.4.2	Positivist Paradigm:	139
3.4.3	Interpretative Paradigm:.....	140
3.4.4	Realist Paradigm:	140
3.4.5	Justification for the Selection of Positivism as the Research Paradigm	140
3.5	Research approach	142
3.5.1	Justification for the Deductive Approach	144

3.6	Research Methodology	145
3.6.1	Justification for the Quantitative Research Method.....	145
3.7	Data Collection	148
3.7.1	Population and Sample	148
3.7.2	Justification for Using Purposive Sampling in This Study	151
3.7.3	Sources and collection of the data	152
3.7.4	The Rationale for Using Secondary Data	153
3.8	Data design: Panel Data	155
3.8.1	Justification for Using Panel Data in This Research	155
3.9	Determination and quantification of variables.....	158
3.9.1	Dependent Variables:.....	158
3.9.2	Justification for choosing Accounting-based over market-based performance metrics.....	158
3.9.3	Independent Variables:	160
3.10	The Estimation of Panel Data Regression Models	162
3.10.1	Pooled OLS regression model	163
3.10.2	Fixed-Effects Model	163
3.10.3	Random-Effects Model.....	164
3.10.4	Selecting the correct model for this study.....	164
3.10.5	Data diagnostic test.....	166
3.11	Robustness check	168
3.11.1	Rationale for Using a two-step system estimator	169

3.12	Statistical Significance of the Findings.....	170
3.13	Conclusion	171
4	Chapter four: Data analysis.....	173
4.1	Introduction.....	173
4.2	Descriptive Statistics of Data.....	173
4.2.1	Measures of Central Tendency	174
4.2.2	Measures of Variability (Dispersion):	174
4.2.3	Measures of Normality (Skewness and Kurtosis):.....	174
4.2.4	Graphical representations.....	175
4.2.5	Return on Equity (ROE)	176
4.2.6	Return on Assets (ROA)	177
4.2.7	Board Size.....	177
4.2.8	Independent Board Directors	178
4.2.9	Female Board Members	178
4.2.10	Audit Committee Members.....	178
4.2.11	Number of Audit Committee Meetings	179
4.2.12	Number of Executive Committee Meetings	179
4.2.13	Number of Board Meetings	180
4.2.14	Audit Fees	180
4.2.15	CEO's Pay.....	180
4.2.16	Directors and CEO's Share (%).....	181
4.2.17	Institutional Share (%)	181

4.2.18	General Public Share (%).....	182
4.2.19	Government Share (%)	182
4.3	Data Diagnostics test for panel data.....	183
4.3.1	Multicollinearity Test.....	183
4.3.2	Normality Test	185
4.3.3	Linearity Test	187
4.4	Regression analysis	189
4.4.1	Model Selection	193
4.4.2	Justification for Random Effect Model Selection.....	196
4.5	Random Effect Model Regression Analysis	197
4.5.1	Random effect Regression results (ROA).....	197
4.6	Random effect Regression results (ROE)	201
4.7	Comparison and Implications of the findings.....	205
4.8	Model diagnostic for panel data.....	206
4.8.1	Homoscedasticity Test	206
4.8.2	Autocorrelation test.....	207
4.9	Residual matrix	208
4.9.1	Breusch-Pagan LM Test of Independence.....	209
4.10	Hypothesis tests based on random effect regression result.....	212
4.11	Conclusion	218
5	Chapter five: Robustness check	219
5.1	Introduction.....	219

5.2	Two-step system estimator	219
5.2.1	Justification for choosing a two-step system estimator for robustness check	220
5.2.2	Justification for Using Lagged Data	221
5.2.3	Justification for Using Log Variables	222
5.3	Explanation of Model Fitness	223
5.4	Regression result	223
5.5	Summary of Diagnostic Tests for Both Models	225
5.6	Hypotheses testing based on two-step system estimator	226
5.7	Summary of the findings for both models	230
5.7.1	Elasticities Summary	231
5.7.2	Combine findings of the random effect model and two-step system estimator model.....	231
6	Chapter Six: Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusions	233
6.1	Introduction.....	233
6.2	Summary and discussion of the findings	233
6.3	Assessing the Corporate Governance Code for Bangladesh’s Banking Sector and proposing best practices of recommendation.....	243
6.3.1	Recommendation for Board Size, Composition, and Dynamics	244
6.3.2	Recommendation for Board and Committee Activities.....	246
6.3.3	Financial and remuneration policies	247
6.3.4	Recommendation for ownership structure	250

6.3.5	Additional recommendations for policymakers.....	252
6.4	Implementation strategy for reformed corporate governance code for Bangladesh banks.....	255
6.5	Significance of the Findings	258
6.5.1	Contribution to Academic and Practical Fields	259
6.6	Limitation.....	260
6.6.1	Key Findings and Limitations.....	260
6.6.2	Methodological and Definitional Limitations.....	261
6.6.3	Implications for Practice and Policy	261
6.6.4	Recommendations for Future Research	262
6.7	Conclusion	262
7	References.....	265
8	Appendix	293

List of Tables

TABLE 1: LISTED COMPANIES ON THE DSE AND CSE. SOURCE: BBS (2019).....	96
TABLE 2:DEPTH OF THE BANKING SYSTEM. SOURCE: WORLD BANK (2019).....	100
TABLE 3: MEMBERS OF BANGLADESH’S TASK FORCE ON CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SOURCE: EXTRACTED FROM THE TASKFORCE MEMBER’S LIST, BEI (2004, PP. 8-9)	111
TABLE 4:CATEGORIES OF BANKS IN BANGLADESH. SOURCE: BANGLADESH BANK (2019)	149
TABLE 5: LIST OF DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	162
TABLE 6: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE FINDINGS.....	176
TABLE 7: THE VARIANCE INFLATION FACTOR (VIF) TEST	184
TABLE 8: REGRESSION RESULT FOR ROA	191
TABLE 9: REGRESSION RESULT FOR ROE.....	192
TABLE 10: RESULT FOR HAUSMAN SPECIFICATION TEST ESTIMATION	194
TABLE 11: RESULT FOR B/P LM TEST ESTIMATION.....	195
TABLE 12: RANDOM EFFECT MODEL RESULT FOR ROA	197
TABLE 13: RANDOM EFFECT MODEL RESULT FOR ROE.....	202
TABLE 14:THE RESULT FOR BREUSCH-PAGAN / COOK-WEISBERG TEST	207
TABLE 15:RESULT FOR WOOLDRIDGE TEST	208
TABLE 16: RESULT OF RESIDUAL MATRIX	210
TABLE 17:THE TWO-STEP SYSTEM ESTIMATOR FOR ROA AND ROE.....	224
TABLE 18:SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS	232

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC CORPORATE GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK DIAGRAM. SOURCE: COMPILED BY AUTHOR, ADAPTED FORM CERNAT (2004).....	29
FIGURE 2:INCREMENTAL CONTRIBUTION OF GDP GROWTH IN BANGLADESH. SOURCE: COMPILED BY AUTHOR, SOURCED FROM BBS (2019).....	93
FIGURE 3: SECTORAL CONTRIBUTIONS TO GDP IN BANGLADESH. SOURCE: COMPILED BY AUTHOR, SOURCED FROM BBS (2019).....	94
FIGURE 5: TOTAL FINANCIAL COMPANIES CATEGORISED BY SECTOR ON THE DSE AND CSE. SOURCE: COMPILED BY AUTHOR, SOURCED FROM DSE (2016)	97
FIGURE 6:KEY INSTITUTIONAL INVOLVEMENT IN BANGLADESH’S CORPORATE GOVERNANCE REFORMS. SOURCE: AUTHOR.....	108
FIGURE 7:ORGANISATION OF THE CODE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE FOR BANGLADESH. SOURCE: BEI (2004, P. 2)	113
FIGURE 8: THE HISTOGRAM OF REGRESSION STANDARDISE RESIDUALS	186
FIGURE 9:LINEARITY ASSUMPTION IN REGRESSION ANALYSIS.	188

LIST OF FIGURES

EQUATION 3.1: FORMULA FOR OLS REGRESSION MODEL	163
EQUATION 3.2: FORMULA FOR FIXED-EFFECT REGRESSION MODEL	163
EQUATION 3.3:FORMULA FOR RANDOM-EFFECT REGRESSION MODEL	164
EQUATION 5.1: TWO- STEP SYSTEM ESTIMATOR MODEL FOR ROA	221
EQUATION 5.2:TWO- STEP SYSTEM ESTIMATOR MODEL FOR ROE.....	221

Abbreviation list

ADB - Asian Development Bank

B/P LM Test - Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Test

BAS - Bangladesh Accounting Standards

BB – Bangladesh Bank

BBS - Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics

BDT - Bangladeshi Taka (Official currency name of Bangladesh)

BEI - Bangladesh Enterprise Institute

BFRS - Bangladesh Financial Reporting Standards

BIS - Bank for International Settlements

BSEC - Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission

CSE - Chittagong Stock Exchange

DSE - Dhaka Stock Exchange

ESG - Environmental, Social, and Governance

ESOPs - Employee Stock Ownership Plans

GAAP - Generally Accepted Accounting Principles

GRI - Global Reporting Initiative

IBRD - International Bank for Reconstruction and Development

ICAB - Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh

IDA - International Development Association

OLS - Ordinary Least Squares

RJSC - Registrar of Joint Stock Companies and Firms

ROA - Return on Assets

ROE - Return on Equity

SASB - Sustainability Accounting Standards Board

VIF - Variance Inflation Factor

1 Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

In recent decades, global financial scandals involving corporations such as WorldCom, Enron, Parmalat, and Xerox have brought to light significant vulnerabilities within the corporate governance frameworks of major financial markets in Europe, Asia, and the USA. Alexakis et al. (2019) noted that these occurrences have sparked renewed discussions about the effectiveness of corporate governance frameworks and the inherent conflicts between shareholders and management that impede economic growth in developed and developing countries.

Chazi et al. (2018) indicated that the main purpose of corporate governance is to reduce agency conflicts and empower shareholders to oversee management, ensuring their interests are safeguarded through adherence to a set of rules and regulations. According to Taylor (2019), the financial crises of the late 2000s accentuated the fragility of financial institutions in the face of inadequate governance frameworks, sparking a worldwide movement towards strengthening these structures. The aftermath of the crisis highlighted the urgent need for reforms to minimise vulnerabilities within corporate governance structures and push towards developing statutory governance frameworks to strengthen shareholder influence within public corporations. As a result, many emerging countries have adopted either the mainstream Anglo-American, German-based, Japanese or a combination of these three models to reform their corporate governance. However, Sobhan (2014) and Chowdhury (2015) expressed substantial concerns regarding the effectiveness of reformed corporate governance systems due to each country's distinct institutional framework, economic and political factors, and social norms that influence businesses and corporate governance.

Despite these efforts, Aliani et al. (2022) discovered that the implementation and effectiveness of corporate governance reforms have been inconsistent. There has been a movement towards adopting governance models from more developed economies in emerging markets. In line with this trend, the Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI) introduced a detailed corporate governance code for the first time in Bangladesh, applicable to both financial and non-financial corporations (BEI, 2004). However, Sobhan (2014) and Madaan et al. (2022) have noted that the effectiveness of these models in unique local contexts has been subject to debate. Sobhan (2014) found that the banking sector in developing nations like Bangladesh presents challenges compounded by weak regulatory frameworks and limited shareholder protections, prompting a reevaluation of the suitability of these imported governance models. While developed nations often penalise non-compliance, Hassan and Halbouni (2016) found that developing nations tend to offer leeway, allowing companies to explain non-adherence.

This study intends to appraise the efficacy of Bangladesh's current corporate governance framework by analysing the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and accounting-based performance metrics such as ROA (return on assets) and ROE (return on equity). The research aims to evaluate the suitability of corporate governance frameworks in Bangladesh for the context of the Bangladeshi banking sector, employing a methodological approach that combines quantitative analysis with a comprehensive review of the literature. Additionally, this study seeks to enrich the academic discussion on corporate governance and provide valuable insights for the formulation of new governance frameworks in Bangladesh that address the distinct challenges faced by banks in emerging economies.

1.2 Background of the Study

1.2.1 The Banking Sector's Crucial Role in Economic Dynamics

According to Brown et al. (2017), the essence of a thriving economy can often be traced back to the robustness of its banking sector, a crucial pillar that not only mirrors a country's economic prospects but also drives its progress. Cox et al. (2004) identified that banks facilitate capital flow across sectors as intermediaries, fueling economic activities and growth. This mutual link emphasises the sector's crucial role in influencing economic environments and the utmost significance of a robust corporate governance framework to guarantee the efficient operation of the monetary system (Brown et al., 2017; Tanna et al., 2017; Islam and Deegan, 2021).

1.2.2 Vulnerabilities Exposed by Global and Local Banking Failures

The spectre of global banking failures, with notable crises in both developed and emerging markets, is a stark reminder of the vulnerabilities inherent within the banking system (Khatun, 2018). Numerous institutions in developed economies, including Lehman Brothers, Northern Rock, Washington Mutual, Lincoln Savings and Loan Association, Royal Bank of Scotland Group, Anglo Irish Bank, Bank West, ABN-Amro, and Banco Espírito Santo collapsed over the past two decades. Many studies, such as (Barth et al., 2003; Imam and Malik 2007; Erkens et al., 2012; Hoque and Muradoglu, 2013; Kolsi and Zehri, 2014; Battaglia and Gallo, 2015; Epure and Lafuente, 2015; Donaldson and Davis, 2017; Khatun, 2018; Nguyen et al., 2020) have suggested that inadequate compliance on corporate governance systems are commonly considered a leading factor in bank failures.

Islam et al. (2021) found that these episodes, transcending geographical boundaries, have highlighted the need for a strong governance framework, especially in emerging

economies such as Bangladesh, where the consequences of such failures have been significant. According to Hossain and Akter (2018), financial scams involving Janata Bank, Agrani Bank, Sonali Bank, BASIC Bank, and Oriental Bank have significantly impacted Bangladesh's economy, resulting in a monetary swindle of BDT 22501m (USD 2.68 bn). These instances diminish public trust and highlight the systemic vulnerabilities that might result from governance failures. Islam et al. (2021) further added that the Bangladesh banking sector, with its own share of challenges, epitomises the pressing need for a governance framework that is both robust and responsive to the complexities of the financial system.

1.2.3 Governance Mechanisms, a strategic lever and Banking Stability

The intricate nature of banking, characterised by the dual role of safeguarding depositor interests and facilitating capital allocation, necessitates a governance framework that is both stringent and comprehensive (Ochanda, 2017). Banks facilitate exchange between savers and borrowers, thus contributing to the equilibrium of monetary supply and demand. The vigilance of regulators in enforcing banking laws and oversight mechanisms ensures deposit safety, loan repayment, and overall economic integrity (Khatun, 2017; Quaresma et al., 2018; Pham & Islam, 2021).

The strategic imperatives of robust corporate governance practices are increasingly recognised for their potential to augment bank performance, attract investment, and accelerate sustainable growth. Empirical research such as (Bepari and Mollik, 2008; Ntim and Osei, 2019; Farooque et al., 2010; Ferdous, 2012; Abdallah and Ismail, 2017; Al-Najjar and Clark 2017; Ararat et al., 2017) substantiates a positive correlation between sound governance frameworks and enhanced bank performance, highlighting the strategic value of governance in fortifying competitive advantage and optimising stakeholder value. In the context of Bangladesh (Bepari and Mollik, 2008; Farooque et al., 2010; Ferdous, 2012)

argued that the banking sector is a critical conduit for economic development, aligning governance practices with international best standards is not merely a regulatory issue but a strategic necessity for national economic stability. Khatun (2018) suggested that this framework must extend beyond mere compliance with regulatory norms to embed a culture of ethical decision-making and risk awareness at all levels of banking operations.

1.2.4 Regulatory Oversight and Its Implications

The banking sector is subject to more rigorous standards of accountability and transparency than non-banking entities, primarily due to its systemic importance and the potential for widespread impact from its failure. Tomar and Bino (2012) argued that this elevated standard necessitates a governance framework that includes diligent oversight by regulators and adherence to stringent internal controls. Mitchell and Joseph (2021) further added that regulatory bodies, including the central bank and other financial oversight agencies, are critical in shaping the governance landscape. These entities are tasked with setting governance standards, enforcing compliance, and ensuring that the banking sector operates within the bounds of financial prudence and integrity. For emerging economies like Bangladesh, the regulatory framework must be agile enough to adapt to global trends while addressing local market nuances (BIS, 2015).

1.2.5 The Globalisation Challenge

Globalisation presents a double-edged sword for the banking sector in Bangladesh. On the one hand, it promises greater integration with the global financial system, access to foreign capital, and the adoption of best practices. On the other hand, Haque and Azmat (2022) argued that it poses significant challenges in managing cross-border risks, competing with international banks, and adhering to international governance standards. The pace at which Bangladesh can navigate these challenges and leverage the opportunities presented by

globalisation will be a crucial determinant of its banking sector's future trajectory (Ahmed, 2010; Azmat and Coghill, 2010).

Given the banking sector's pivotal role in fostering economic development and the critical challenges posed by governance lapses, this study is predicated on critically examining corporate governance mechanisms within the Bangladeshi banking sector to find how effective Bangladesh's corporate governance structure is to fit in the current banking system.

1.3 Research problem

Bangladesh's economy has grown significantly in the last two decades, with small businesses transforming into global corporations. World Bank (2019) identifies the demographic dividends, strong RMG exports, remittances, and stable macroeconomic conditions fuel this growth. The banking sector is pivotal for scholarly scrutiny in Bangladesh's rapidly evolving economic landscape. According to Siddiqui and Uddin (2016), this sector is crucial in raising capital for a country like Bangladesh and its development. However, Rahman et al. (2018) argued that it faces governance issues threatening its operational integrity and overall macroeconomic stability. This study found a significant issue with governance structures and how they relate to the performance of banks. If the current corporate governance code effectively mitigates financial malfeasance and fosters sustainable economic growth, why has the country witnessed several scandals in recent decades? Nevertheless, the following problems have motivated researchers to investigate the connection between Bangladeshi banks' performance and corporate governance practices.

Firstly, the Regulatory Frameworks may have theoretical robustness but lacks Practical Efficacy. The Bangladesh Code of Corporate Governance, established primarily to improve governance standards and prevent stock market crises like the one in 1996, sets forth

best practices introduced in 2004. Despite these measures, the market faced another downturn in 2011, driven by financial scandals from 1996 to 2011. These events, which drew international concern and shareholder distress, prompted the Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI) to revise the Code in 2012, mandating its adoption by listed companies and financial institutions. The necessity to scrutinise the Code's effectiveness or compliance to ensure robust governance in the banking sector is evident. Nevertheless, the persistence of financial misconduct despite regulatory efforts highlights a significant gap between regulatory aims and actual outcomes, indicating that the enforcement and accountability mechanisms are notably inadequate. This gap is compounded by a culture of impunity among key market players, revealing deep flaws in the sector's regulatory and accountability structures (Haque & Azmat, 2022; Hossain et al., 2018).

Secondly, Financial Scandals are Indicators of Deep-Rooted Governance Issues. The historical financial scandals, transcending mere financial mismanagement to encompass loan fraud, share dilution, and unauthorised financial endorsements, epitomise the systemic governance maladies afflicting the banking sector (Akhter, 2019). For instance, Ferdous (2012) revealed severe irregularities in Sonali Bank, where unauthorised loans of BDT 36.50 billion (\$461m) were issued based on forged documentation. Similarly, Farooque et al. (2007) highlighted the involvement of six commercial banks in a \$190 million lending scandal. Despite regulatory efforts, Ferdous (2012) contended that the unauthorised loan sanctions by Sonali Bank were not just an operational failure but also a deeper institutional governance crisis, leading Akhter (2019) to believe that these scandals continue and that a thorough review of the corporate governance code is necessary to ensure financial stability.

Finally, Rahman and Zaman (2021) state that the banking sector's critical role in channelling savings into investments for economic growth underscores the importance of sound governance mechanisms within these institutions. Hossain et al.(2018) further added that as custodians of public funds, banks are responsible for adhering to stringent governance standards, ensuring transparency, accountability, and prudent risk management. The dereliction of these standards can adversely affect financial stability and investor confidence. Shedding light on the inherent risks and vulnerabilities within the banking industry in Bangladesh, Rashid et al. (2020) argued that accentuating the need for a comprehensive study of governance mechanisms to mitigate these risks within the banking industry.

This study seeks to address the effectiveness gap by conducting a detailed analysis of existing corporate governance frameworks and their application within the banking sector. By examining the impact of governance mechanisms on banking performance, this research will add to scholarly discussions and guide policy reforms, thereby improving the sector's resilience and fostering sustainable economic growth.

1.4 Research gap

Studying corporate governance practices in emerging nations is a crucial area of interest for researchers, policymakers, and industry experts. Despite the extensive global research in corporate governance, significant research gaps persist, particularly concerning its application and effectiveness within Bangladesh's banking system. The author of this research conducted a comprehensive literature review on the topic. Since corporate governance covers a wide range of sub-topics, the researcher had to narrow down the financial and non-financial sectors. Following the decision to focus on the financial sector, the study's author examined corporate governance challenges in the banking sector for

Bangladeshi banks operating under Bangladesh's corporate governance code. This research study aims to solve those concerns.

1.4.1 Limited Focus on Banking Sector Governance:

Many existing researches predominantly focus on the connection between corporate governance and overall business performance, yet they often overlook bank governance, especially within the Bangladeshi context. Although numerous studies, such as those by Beiner et al. (2006), Bhagat and Bolton (2008), Chan (2014), Dancey and Reidy (2017), Ferdous (2012), and Hiraki et al. (2003), have investigated the link between corporate governance and firm performance worldwide, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding the unique aspects of governance in the banking sector, which is vital for economic development. Furthermore, while existing studies on corporate and bank governance issues, such as those by Adams and Mehran (2012), Hoque et al. (2013), Jiang et al. (2012), Kim and Rasiah (2010), Swain (2009), and Tomar and Bino (2012), provide valuable insights, their focus on specific countries limits them and thus do not fully address global bank governance challenges. In the context of Bangladesh, only a few studies, including those by Al-Mamun & Rahman (2019), Hoque et al. (2017), and Rahman et al. (2012), have examined the impact of corporate governance on bank performance. In these studies, researchers have looked at different aspects of corporate governance, including financial stability, board effectiveness, and the role of comprehensive disclosure in improving bank performance. While these studies provide valuable insights, there remains a gap in understanding the current effectiveness of Bangladesh's corporate governance code. This research seeks to address this gap by offering insights into how each component of the corporate governance code influences the performance of selected banks, thereby determining the actual effectiveness of the existing Code amidst the unique challenges and opportunities within the banking industry of Bangladesh.

1.4.2 Over-reliance on Ownership structure, Board compositions, and Agency Theory:

Corporate governance and bank performance are still emerging topics in Bangladesh, with relatively few studies conducted specifically on bank governance. Key contributions include those from Al-Mamun & Rahman (2019), Bepari and Mollik (2008), Hoque et al. (2017), Imam and Malik (2007), Mahmud (2013), Rahman et al. (2012), Siddiqui (2011), and Shoban (2014). Following research trends in developed countries, Bangladeshi scholars have mainly concentrated on elements like board composition and ownership structure, predominantly applying Agency theory to explore corporate governance and firm performance. Hence, this approach fails to adequately capture the governance issues within the banking sectors completely due to Bangladesh's socio-economic and legal landscape, thereby limiting the comprehensive understanding of governance mechanisms. This study utilises a multi-theoretical approach, incorporating various frameworks, such as stakeholder theory, stewardship theory, and institutional theory, to provide a more accurate analysis to address the gap.

1.4.3 Ineffectiveness of Regulatory Frameworks:

Over the past 30 years, Bangladesh has seen numerous corporate scandals, including loan fraud, excessive equity financing, share dilution, and bankruptcy. Sonali Bank, the largest state-owned bank, sanctioned unauthorised loan applications with forged documentation totalling approximately BDT 36.50 billion (\$461m) from their single branch. The central bank found that senior Sonali Bank executives collaborated with borrowing companies to steal money. The Bismillah Group's \$190 million lending scandal involved six commercial banks. Bangladesh has enacted several regulatory and legal frameworks to reform its corporate governance code, such as the Banking Companies Act 1991, Securities

and Exchange Commission Act 1993, Financial Institutions Act 1993, Companies Act 1994, and Bankruptcy Act 1997. Despite these efforts, ongoing scandals indicate that these frameworks might not effectively foster good governance within the banking sector.

Additionally, Bangladesh is a participant in the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, which seeks to enhance the resilience of the global banking system by bolstering the regulatory capital requirements and risk coverage standards of the capital framework. However, the above scandals lead us to assume that these legislative and regulatory frameworks are insufficient and ineffective in encouraging good governance in the Bangladeshi banking sector. The existing regulatory frameworks, derived from legislative enactments and international standards, may lack clarity and enforcement mechanisms, rendering them ineffective in fostering good governance practices. Through a comprehensive examination of Bangladesh's legislative and institutional frameworks, this study seeks to identify deficiencies and propose remedial measures to strengthen governance mechanisms in the banking sector. Despite regulatory efforts to enhance corporate governance standards within Bangladeshi banks, corporate malpractice and financial misconduct persist.

1.4.4 Partial Examination of Governance Elements:

Previous studies in Bangladesh have often adopted a narrow focus, concentrating on isolated elements of corporate governance such as ownership concentration, CEO remuneration, or different elements of board composition while neglecting the broader spectrum of governance mechanisms. Furthermore, the limited application of theoretical models, primarily centred on agency theory, fails to provide a holistic understanding of governance dynamics (Siddiqui, 2011). This study seeks to overcome these limitations by comprehensively examining all the governance elements in the corporate governance code, such as board composition, board activities, audit function, subcommittee functions, CEO

remuneration and ownership concentration against the bank performance measures such as ROE and ROA to identify their relationship and employing a diverse range of theoretical perspectives with the findings.

The identified research gaps emphasise the pressing need to examine corporate governance practices within Bangladesh's banking sector comprehensively. By addressing these gaps and employing a multi-theoretical approach, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the intricacies of corporate governance and its implications for bank performance in Bangladesh. Through empirical analysis and critical evaluation, the research endeavours to inform policymakers, regulators, and industry stakeholders, facilitating the development of robust governance frameworks conducive to sustainable economic growth and financial stability.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for investigating the relationship between Corporate governance and bank performances in Bangladesh is built on a foundation that integrates critical theoretical perspectives, each offering unique insights into the multifaceted nature of governance. They are as follows.

1.5.1 Agency Theory:

Agency theory focuses on the conflicts between owners (principals) and managers (agents) and provides a foundational lens through which the governance issues in banks can be examined. It addresses how shareholders can ensure managerial actions align with their interests, particularly in contexts like Bangladesh, where corporate governance practices are evolving. This theory helps understand the governance structures that mitigate bank agency problems, such as board composition, executive compensation, and shareholder rights.

1.5.2 Stakeholder Theory:

Stakeholder theory broadens the scope of analysis beyond the shareholder-manager pair to include other stakeholders such as employees, customers, suppliers, and the community. This theory is pertinent to understanding how banks in Bangladesh navigate their responsibilities to various stakeholders while adhering to governance codes. It underscores the importance of transparency, accountability, and ethical business practices in sustaining the long-term interests of all stakeholders.

1.5.3 Stewardship Theory:

In contrast to agency theory, stewardship theory posits that managers are stewards whose interests are aligned with those of the corporation and its shareholders. This perspective is relevant for examining the intrinsic motivations of bank managers in Bangladesh to comply with governance codes for the collective good of the bank and its stakeholders. It also explores the conditions under which stewardship is more likely to flourish, such as corporate culture and governance policies that empower managers.

1.5.4 Institutional Theory:

Institutional theory provides insights into how regulatory frameworks, cultural norms, and societal expectations influence Bangladesh's corporate governance practices and code compliance. It examines banks' pressures from regulatory bodies, industry norms, and cultural expectations to adopt certain governance practices. This theory is crucial for understanding the adoption, implementation, and effectiveness of governance codes in the Bangladeshi banking sector, highlighting the role of coercive, mimetic, and normative pressures.

1.5.5 Resource Dependency Theory

This theory highlights the bank's dependence on external resources and how governance structures are designed to manage external dependencies and uncertainties. It is relevant to understand how banks in Bangladesh leverage their boards and governance practices to secure essential resources, navigate environmental uncertainties, and maintain competitive advantages.

The theoretical framework concludes with an integrative perspective combining insights from the abovementioned theories to provide a holistic understanding of corporate governance and code compliance in Bangladesh's banking sector. This approach acknowledges the multifaceted nature of corporate governance, considering both the internal dynamics within banks (as highlighted by agency, stewardship, and resource dependency theories) and the external pressures and expectations (as emphasised by stakeholder and institutional theories).

By integrating these theories in this study, the theoretical framework has guided the empirical investigation and contributed to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities in enhancing corporate governance and code compliance in emerging economies like Bangladesh.

1.6 Research Methodology

The study outlines its comprehensive research approach, which is crucial in examining the effectiveness and suitability of Bangladesh's current corporate governance code for the banking sector. The primary goal is to examine how various corporate governance mechanisms relate to bank performance, aiming to recommend best practices for enhancing the protection of shareholders' and stakeholders' interests in the banking industry.

The research adopts a positivist philosophy, utilising a deductive approach to test hypotheses derived from existing theories and literature empirically. This methodological choice underpins a quantitative research strategy, deemed most suitable for this study due to its focus on measuring and analysing the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and bank performance through statistical methods. The data collection process relied solely on both primary and secondary data. The data source includes a comprehensive range of public financial reports and databases, ensuring the study's reliance on accurate and audited information.

The sample for this study comprises 33 scheduled banks listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange, selected through purposive sampling to ensure relevance and adherence to Bangladesh's corporate governance code. The study utilised a balanced panel dataset from 2012 to 2017, allowing for an accurate analysis of the temporal dynamics affecting corporate governance and bank performance.

Analytical methods include multiple regression analysis, with a detailed discussion on the choice between pooled OLS regression, fixed-effects, and random-effects models based on statistical tests like the Hausman Specification test and the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test. The chapter also addresses diagnostic tests for data normality, linearity, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation, highlighting the rigorous statistical scrutiny applied to ensure the reliability and robustness of the findings.

Delineating this study's methodological approach and analytical techniques sets a solid foundation for the empirical investigation, aiming to contribute meaningful insights into the relationship between corporate governance practices and bank performance in Bangladesh. The hypotheses were tested using a random effect model, and a robustness check was carried out using a two-step system estimator. This methodical approach emphasises the

study's commitment to academic discipline and its potential to inform policy and practice within the banking sector.

1.7 Research Aim, objectives and questions

1.7.1 Research aim and objectives

The research aim is to assess the effectiveness and appropriateness of Bangladesh's existing corporate governance code for the banking sector. This study is structured around several detailed research objectives to effectively address the broader aim of evaluating the effectiveness and suitability of the corporate governance code to fit in the banking industry of Bangladesh. These objectives are designed to assess current practices and identify potential improvements to enhance the sector's stability and attractiveness to investors. The objectives and sub-objectives are as follows:

- I. Examine Corporate Governance and Bank Performance: Analyse the relationship between governance structures like board composition, board and sub-committee activities, financial and compensation policies, and various ownership structures, and their influence on bank performance.
- II. Recommend Best Practices: Based on the findings, propose optimal governance practices specifically tailored for the Bangladeshi banking sector to enhance investor attractiveness and safeguard shareholder and stakeholder interests.

1.7.2 Main Research Question:

How effective and appropriate is the current corporate governance code in enhancing the performance and stability of banks in Bangladesh?

Supporting sub- Research Questions:

1. What is the effect of the composition and size of bank boards, including the presence of independent and female directors, on the performance of banks in Bangladesh?
2. What is the impact of board and committee activities, such as the frequency and nature of meetings, on the performance of banks?
3. How do financial and compensation policies, including audit fees, directors' fees, and CEO remuneration, correlate with bank performance in Bangladesh?
4. How do different ownership structures, such as director, institutional, public, and government shareholdings, affect the performance of banks?

1.8 Findings

The research conducted on the governance factors affecting the performance of banks in Bangladesh from 2012 to 2017 provides insights into how various aspects of corporate governance and ownership structures impact financial outcomes. The study meticulously analysed the relationship between bank performance metrics, such as Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA), and a range of governance variables, including board composition, the presence of independent and female directors, governance practices like board and committee meetings, audit-related finances, and diverse ownership forms.

One of the prominent findings from the study is the lack of significant impact of board composition on bank performance. Specifically, the board size, the proportion of independent directors, and the presence of female directors do not correlate with improved financial performance. These results suggest that the effectiveness of a board may not solely

depend on its size or diversity but perhaps on the quality of oversight and strategic decision-making.

In examining governance practices, the study reveals that the frequency of board meetings, executive committee meetings, and audit committee meetings, along with the number of members in the audit committee, do not have a significant relationship with the banks' financial outcomes. The results indicate that the quantity of governance activities does not directly translate into financial success, pointing towards the importance of the content and productivity of these meetings rather than their frequency.

Financial aspects of the governance mechanisms, such as audits and directors' fees, are under scrutiny and have shown no significant relationship with bank performance. This finding implies that these expenditures, often seen as indicators of thorough governance or compensation for oversight, do not directly affect a bank's financial performance.

Ownership structure emerged as a critical factor with mixed effects on bank performance. The study identifies a significant but negative relationship between CEO remuneration and ROE, suggesting that higher executive pay does not necessarily lead to better equity returns. Moreover, the ownership analysis reveals that while Director or CEO share ownership negatively impacts ROA, institutional and public share ownership have beneficial effects, particularly public ownership, which positively affects both ROE and ROA. Interestingly, government share ownership was found to have no significant effect on bank performance, challenging assumptions about the efficacy of state ownership in enhancing financial outcomes.

The research demonstrates a complex interplay between governance factors and bank performance, highlighting that no single factor guarantees financial success. The positive impact of public ownership on financial performance stands out, suggesting that broader

ownership may align with better bank outcomes. These findings indicate the need for a more comprehensive understanding and approach to corporate governance and ownership strategies to enhance bank performance in Bangladesh.

1.9 Significance and Contribution of the Study

The findings from this research hold profound significance in the context of Bangladesh's Corporate Governance Code and the banking industry, offering critical insights and implications for policymakers, regulators, corporate leaders, and investors. Bangladesh has been evolving its corporate governance frameworks to enhance transparency, accountability, and efficiency within its corporate sectors, including the banking industry, which is pivotal to the country's economic growth and stability. The subtle outcomes of this study illuminate several areas of focus and potential reevaluation within these frameworks.

1.9.1 Reassessing Board Composition Guidelines:

The study's indication that board size, independence, and diversity (including gender diversity) do not have a direct impact on bank performance challenges existing assumptions about board composition. In the context of the Bangladesh Corporate Governance Code, which emphasises board structure as a cornerstone of effective governance, these findings suggest a need for a more refined approach. Instead of prescribing quantitative measures for board composition, the focus might shift towards enhancing the quality of board deliberations, the strategic competencies of board members, and their ability to provide adequate oversight and strategic guidance.

1.9.2 Rethinking Governance Practices:

The lack of a significant relationship between the frequency of board and committee meetings and bank performance raises questions about current governance practices. This

outcome suggests that the emphasis should not solely be on the quantity of governance activities but on their quality and substance. For the Bangladesh banking sector, this could mean revising guidelines to encourage more meaningful engagement in meetings, focusing on strategic discussions, risk management, and value creation rather than mere compliance and procedural regularities.

1.9.3 Evaluating Executive Compensation and Ownership Structures such as Director's share:

The analysis reveals a negative relationship between the share or ownership of Directors or CEOs and Return on Equity (ROE), which adds a layer of complexity to the understanding of corporate governance and its influence on financial performance. This insight, coupled with findings on the negative relationship between CEO pay and bank performance and the varied impacts of different ownership structures, underlines the intricate dynamics of incentive systems and their effects on organisational outcomes. Such evidence challenges the conventional wisdom that higher executive ownership and remuneration straightforwardly align their interests with those of shareholders to enhance company performance. Instead, it suggests that excessive executive ownership might lead to risk-averse behaviours, a concentration of power that inhibits innovation, overconfidence, or entrenchment, all potentially detrimental to a company's efficiency in generating profits. These findings highlight the need for the development of more sophisticated compensation frameworks. By integrating a broader set of performance metrics beyond traditional financial indicators, these frameworks could better align with long-term performance and shareholder value creation, reflecting the nuanced impact of executive incentives on organisational success.

1.9.4 Emphasising Broad-based Ownership:

The positive impact of public share ownership on bank performance is a critical insight for the Bangladesh banking sector, suggesting that broader ownership may enhance accountability and performance. This finding supports initiatives to encourage more involvement in the equity markets and might influence policies to facilitate public listings and equity ownership by a diverse set of institutional investors. It underscores the potential benefits of democratising ownership and aligning interests between banks and their broader stakeholder groups.

1.9.5 Policy Implications and Future Governance Reforms:

The findings of this study offer a foundation for targeted governance reforms in the banking sector, emphasising the need for policies that go beyond conventional wisdom and quantitative metrics. Regulators and policymakers could leverage this research to refine the Corporate Governance Code, tailoring it to encourage practices and structures that are genuinely conducive to enhancing bank performance and stability. This could involve more flexible, principle-based regulations that allow banks to adopt governance practices best suited to their unique contexts and challenges.

In conclusion, the significance of this research extends beyond academic contributions, offering practical insights into the evolution of corporate governance standards in Bangladesh. By acknowledging the complexity of factors influencing bank performance and the limitations of one-size-fits-all solutions, Bangladesh can advance its governance frameworks better to support the resilience and growth of its banking sector and, by extension, its broader economy.

2 Chapter two: Literature review

This chapter thoroughly examines corporate governance, detailing its historical development, theoretical foundations, and diverse models. It also explores mechanisms crucial for addressing the main research question: How effective is Bangladesh's corporate governance structure fitting into the current banking system? The chapter is structured into four main sections for clarity and depth. The first section establishes the theoretical landscape of corporate governance, tracing its evolution and discussing global models and mechanisms. This foundational understanding sheds light on the principles that could inform effective governance practices in Bangladesh. In the second section, the focus shifts to a review of empirical literature on internal corporate governance mechanisms. This segment assesses various studies to understand the effectiveness of governance tools and their impact on organisational efficacy, offering insights into best practices and potential pitfalls. The third section delves into Bangladesh's corporate landscape, exploring the country's economic, social, and institutional dynamics. This analysis provides a contextual backdrop essential for evaluating governance structures in the Bangladeshi banking sector. The fourth section thoroughly examines Bangladesh's corporate governance code, analysing its provisions, theoretical justifications, and practical implications. Hypotheses are formulated to guide empirical investigations, aiming to assess the alignment between the governance code and the operational realities of Bangladesh's banking system.

This chapter synthesises existing research and contextualises it within Bangladesh's socio-economic environment, aiming to provide a comprehensive perspective on the efficacy of corporate governance structures in the country's banking system. Through this structured presentation, the chapter enhances understanding of the theoretical and practical aspects of corporate governance.

2.1 Segment one: historical evolution, conceptual framework, and models, theories, and mechanisms

2.1.1 Corporate governance history

It is impossible to comprehend corporate governance appropriately without understanding the source and development of its evolution. The narrative of corporate governance started long ago, and its roots are in critical historical events that are still studied by many to this day. According to Baskin & Miranti (1997), its formal establishment dates back to the 1592 establishment of the Levant Company by Queen Elizabeth I. This company was entrusted with regulating trade with the Ottoman Empire. Nevertheless, Wells (2010) argues that the genuine need for corporate governance became apparent in 1600 following the formation of the East India Company, which introduced a structured board of directors and a chief executive officer to enforce accountability abroad.

Smith (1776) identified in his book, “Wealth of Nations”, the possibility of conflicts of interest between owners and managers, arguing that managers could not always operate in the owners’ best interest because they hold no ownership stake. However, Smith’s finding was not regarded seriously because hardly any passive investors existed then. According to Cheffins (2000), the urge for corporate governance practice became the focus of public attention for the first time during the period of British liberal Industrial Investigations of 1926-1928 because it widely revealed the influence of managers over investors’ interests.

In the US, Berle and Means (1932) criticised the corporate culture during the Great Economic Depression of the 1930s. They proposed that shareholders be allowed to sell their shares if they were discontented. In fact, this idea was warmly accepted amidst the Great Depression. Years later, Ocasio and Joseph (2005) identified that corporate governance had

become another topical issue due to the failure of Penn Central in the 1970s due to financial mismanagement and poor corporate governance. To avoid a similar situation, a set of new regulations was put forward and managed by the Federal Securities and Exchange Commission to enhance the accountability of the managers and leaders.

According to Tricker (2000), the 1970s was also the decade that shook the world with several big scandals, including Watergate and Teapot Dome, which demonstrated the need for governance reform. This period also saw the introduction of the Agency theory by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, which suggested that managers often put their interests above those of the shareholders.

Denis (2001) identified that the UK faced its share of turmoil in the early 1990s, beginning with the financial debacle involving the Bank of Credit and Commerce, followed by the mysterious death of Robert Maxwell, which revealed significant financial mismanagement. These events led to the establishment of the Cadbury Committee. The Cadbury Report of 1992 influenced UK corporate governance and set a benchmark worldwide, inspiring numerous countries to revise their governance codes, including emerging countries like Bangladesh (Ferdous, 2012).

According to Rosen (2007) and Solomon (2007), From 1990 to 2004, significant strides were made in corporate governance, with numerous reports transitioning into legislative reforms to enhance accountability and protect shareholder interests. Among those reports, the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, enacted in 2002, was critical in changing the US corporate governance legislation. The Viénot Report of 1995 in France and Daniel Bouton's report of 2002 facilitated a corporate reform involving auditors and regulators, responsibility distribution among market players, executive roles, and the board directors' role to promote a fair corporate governance system. The Cadbury report from 1992 had the most significant

impact on the current corporate governance system in the UK. The report examined the causes of company failure, and a corporate governance code for best practices was included. The London Stock Exchange eventually added the proposal as an appendix to its listing regulations for all businesses seeking to trade on the exchange to assure compliance with the recommendation. Along with subsequent reports like the Greenbury Report (1995), the Higgs Report (2003), and the Hampel Report (2003), they have been instrumental in shaping UK corporate law. According to Ferdous (2012), Bangladesh's first "comply-or-explain" voluntary corporate governance code was enacted in 2004. However, Bangladesh's Securities and Exchange Commission did not apply the Code as legal compliance for Bangladesh's stock market trading until 2006.

This journey through the history of corporate governance highlights how each crisis and subsequent reform has helped to sculpt a more accountable and transparent corporate world, reflecting a continuous evolution to keep pace with business and financial changes. The corporate governance code was implemented to protect shareholders' interests and address the ongoing conflicts between managers and investors. Over the past few centuries, a range of innovative models and theories have emerged to enhance corporate governance and improve the security and efficiency of companies. Regardless of the efforts, whenever a new financial crisis arises, or a company collapses, experts and regulators revisit the same century-old debate.

2.1.2 Defining corporate governance

As a result of globalisation and cross-border commercial interactions, the importance of corporate governance has expanded rapidly more than ever. However, what is corporate governance? What does it do? According to Freeman et al. (2004), corporate governance is constantly increasing, and the complexity of the topic does not allow it to be defined

universally. Gruszczyński (2020) asserts that many scholars have attempted to clarify corporate governance, stating that it aims to ensure shareholders' safety and respect other stakeholders' interests. Today, corporate governance is widely applied in business practices, and its importance goes beyond simply relying on a set of rules or codes.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2004) defines corporate governance as the framework of rules, relationships, systems, and processes within and by which authority is exercised and controlled in corporations. It highlights how governance helps define corporate objectives, achieve them, and monitor progress while ensuring that the interests of shareholders and other key stakeholders are protected through a structured governance system. On the other hand, the Cadbury Committee (1992) describes corporate governance more narrowly as the systems by which companies are directed and controlled, focusing on the structure that allows for regulatory oversight of board and management decisions to safeguard shareholder interests.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) view corporate governance as a set of procedures designed to ensure that investors see a return on their investments. This perspective underscores the practical importance of a governance code in preventing managerial abuses. Similarly, Davidson et al. (2005) define corporate governance as the actions a company undertakes to guide and control its operations to the mutual benefit of the company and its shareholders. Yet, the practical implications of corporate governance can vary widely, as Bednarek and Moszoro (2014) discuss. For example, Dedu and Chitan, (2013) analyse it in terms of institutional arrangements that influence decision-makers and relationships among participants to ensure fair decision-making within the company.

The way corporate governance is defined can differ significantly depending on the viewpoint. For instance, the Cadbury Committee (1992), Davidson et al. (2005), and the

OECD (2004) approach corporate governance from a control perspective, while Shleifer and Vishny (1997) emphasise the relationships between investors and management. Meanwhile, Morck et al. (2005) and Solomon (2007) adopt a broader approach that includes various stakeholders in the decision-making process. In contrast, Dedu and Chitan (2013) focus on the institutional and decision-making frameworks. Despite these variations, Monks and Minow (2004) believe that corporate governance plays a comprehensive and pivotal role in contemporary business, while Lepineux (2005) suggests that the lack of a standard definition makes it difficult to distinguish between effective and ineffective governance practices, which often vary by industry and country.

2.1.3 Definition of corporate governance for the banking sector

Corporate governance in the banking sector encompasses the intricate process of guiding and overseeing a bank's activities towards optimal outcomes. Adams and Mehran (2012) underline the indispensable role of robust corporate governance in protecting the interests of shareholders and stakeholders, fostering accountability, transparency, and trustworthiness within the institution. Solomon (2007) posits that governance norms tailored to the banking sector must diverge from those applicable to non-financial entities, acknowledging the unique dynamics inherent in banking operations, capital structures, and client relationships.

Corporate governance in the banking industry is defined as an approach to directing and monitoring a bank's operations to achieve the best possible results. According to Adams and Mehran (2012), strong corporate governance is necessary to protect shareholders and stakeholders by improving a company's responsibility, transparency, and trustworthiness. Moreover, Solomon (2007) suggested that the corporate governance norm of a bank should be distinct from a non-financial firm's governance structure. Due to the nature of the

business, a bank's capital structure, operations, and client interactions are distinct from those of non-financial companies. Corporate governance is further defined by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2004) as the method by which different management groups, such as directors, senior management, and executives, control the bank and all of its linked affairs. Combined Code (2003) claims that effective banking governance necessitates a board of directors who are qualified to fulfil their duties. Their responsibilities include establishing a corporate value system with a tailored strategic plan for shareholders' value maximisation combined with corporate social responsibilities and monitoring progress in an efficient setting backed by an independent and competent internal audit system. They also have to create a specific job description, distribute the role and responsibilities to build accountability and transparency and facilitate fair employee remuneration schemes to drive everyone to attain the bank's collective goal.

Walker (2009) further added that a bank's corporate governance is built on securing and advancing shareholders' interests by establishing a bank's strategic leadership and forming a management board capable of doing so. A report by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2004) provides a similar analysis of the definition of the bank's governance. It highlights the roles and responsibilities of the board and senior management in managing the bank while determining its risk exposure, defending the interests of stakeholders and depositors, and satisfying shareholder expectations.

Corporate governance is simply a tool for establishing the methods and mechanisms employed in the operation of the business, as well as the ways employed to control the company. How efficient such systems work might depend primarily on each nation's unique cultural, economic, and legal differences. The various forms of corporate governance are

being implemented globally. Among these models, Anglo-American and Continental European models are significant.

2.1.4 Corporate Governance Models

Corporate governance models provide a structured framework through which companies are directed and controlled, reflecting the varied interests of stakeholders involved in the management and outcomes of the business. These models differ significantly worldwide, shaped by regional legal systems, economic environments, and cultural norms. The most commonly discussed models are External and Insider governance models. Cernat (2004) argued that these models are widely referred to as Anglo-American and Continental-European models in corporate governance literature, respectively. Each model offers distinct approaches to balance the power between shareholders, boards of directors, and other stakeholders. Such frameworks influence corporate decisions and policies and determine organisations’ transparency, accountability, and sustainability within the global business landscape.

Figure 1: Schematic Corporate Governance Framework diagram. Source: Compiled by Author, adapted form Cernat (2004)

2.1.4.1 External or Anglo-American model of corporate governance

In the external model of corporate governance, commonly seen in the Anglo-American framework, the market acts as a pivotal monitoring tool. This separation of ownership from management in major publicly listed companies, as identified by Cernat (2004), is prevalent in countries like the UK and USA. In these systems, shareholders play a significant role, electing independent and non-executive directors to boards that oversee management. Operating within highly liquid capital markets, these boards are empowered to make transparent and aggressive business decisions, including taking over smaller firms.

Despite being often grouped under this model, UK and US corporate governance practices exhibit significant differences. In the UK, the roles of the company's CEO and board chairman are distinctly separate to prevent conflicts of interest, while in the USA, it is common for the same individual to hold both roles, a practice known as role duality, which Aguilera and Jackson (2010), argue has become a norm. According to La Porta et al. (2002), this model primarily prioritises shareholder interests with shareholders selecting board directors, independent directors, non-executive directors, and members of the Single-tiered Executive Board, who then exercise significant control over the company's operations, including key executive, remuneration, and audit committees.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) further noted that in the outsider system, management remuneration is closely tied to board performance, potentially leading to an agency problem where management may prioritise personal interests over those of the shareholders. This issue is compounded by the fact that shareholders, particularly in larger firms, are typically dispersed and not actively involved in daily decision-making. This dispersion allows management to wield greater control, often without effective oversight from these

shareholders who, despite having the power, seldom exert significant influence due to the free-rider problem. As La Porta et al. (2002) explain, in countries with robust legal systems, this arrangement often benefits the small and scattered shareholders who opt to free-ride on the efforts of others without directly engaging in governance activities.

Williams and Conley (2005) and Cernat (2004) noted that managers within the Anglo-American corporate governance framework often prioritise short-term, quarterly results. This focus can lead to myopic behaviours, identified by Keasey et al. (1997) as a characteristic of this model, increasing the risk of hostile takeovers due to the emphasis on immediate financial outcomes over long-term stability.

A classic case of such myopia was Enron in the late 1990s. It was celebrated as a model Anglo-American company until its downfall when executive compensation remained unaffected despite its plummeting share price. Resonating this pattern, Tomar and Bino (2012) observed similar compensation trends during the financial crisis, where loss-suffering banks continued to pay hefty bonuses, demonstrating a continued disregard for broader financial health in favour of short-term gains.

Nevertheless, the Anglo-American governance framework has supported economic expansion in the US and UK. Its robust structure efficiently aligns management with shareholder profit maximisation, allowing for easy shareholder exits and fostering economic growth. This model's strength lies in its ability to adapt and evolve, maintaining its relevance and effectiveness in promoting corporate success and resilience.

2.1.4.2 Insider or continental European model (German-Japanese model)

On the other hand, the insider model of corporate governance, also known as the continental European model, empowers managers with greater decision-making authority.

Freeman (2009) argued that this model adopts a holistic view of stakeholder theory, using managerial discretion to balance the interests of shareholders with those of other stakeholders. Ghauri and Gronhaug (2010) highlighted that countries adhering to this model benefit from significant financial and capital market leverage and tend to feature small to medium-sized enterprises with concentrated ownership structures and less transparent, highly effective boards.

Cernat (2004) explains that insider models are predominantly funded by family and bank investments, unlike equity financing, which is more typical of external models. This financing structure makes the insider model prevalent in many European and Asian countries, including Japan, Italy, and Germany, which have been instrumental in evolving corporate governance within Europe. Keasey et al. (1997) describe the emergence of neo-corporatism in Italian discourse in the late 1980s, leading to adaptations in business and market regulations across less receptive markets. These socio-economic dynamics have given rise to various distribution and control structures uniquely suited to their respective markets. In these systems, the high concentration of ownership allows shareholders considerable influence over corporate management, demonstrating the distinct characteristics and implications of the insider governance model.

The German governance model adeptly harmonises the interests of a wide array of stakeholders, guiding the alignment of policy directions. Traditionally, German banks have been instrumental in corporate governance, exerting significant influence on company decisions through their deep involvement in corporate financing. This contrasts sharply with the US system, where banks typically maintain a more detached role. In Germany, banks can wield considerable control over companies, often representing their clients' investments, with the authority to vote and make pivotal business decisions.

Germany operates under a dual governance structure that not only complies with national policies designed to foster worker participation in business processes and promote industrial democracy but also ensures active engagement in daily corporate operations. This system features two separate boards: the Executive Board, which manages day-to-day operations, and the Supervisory Board, which oversees and makes broader governance decisions. This dual board setup provides a rigorous monitoring and control mechanism, facilitating substantial oversight and validation of corporate decisions, thus upholding stringent governance standards that serve both corporate and stakeholder interests effectively.

Hiraki et al. (2003) describe the Japanese corporate governance model as one characterised by a 'holding notion', grouping industrial entities with aligned objectives and strategies. This model emphasises maintaining strong relationships with shareholders and the keiretsu—a network of loyal consumers and suppliers—which is central to resisting hostile takeovers, preventing shareholder opportunism, and sustaining long-term economic relationships. The keiretsu system encourages both cooperation and competitive interactions among Japanese firms, most of which are integrated into this network.

Two distinct legal relationships typically govern Japanese governance: one involves collective decisions among shareholders, consumers, trade unions, creditors, suppliers, and local governments, and the other manages interactions between owners and various stakeholders, including managers. This structure emphasises that complex relationships should not interfere with organisational operations. Despite aiming to enhance enterprise revenue and control, shareholder involvement often constrains management decisions, indicating a governance focus on internal control. However, unlike the German model, where significant shareholders participate directly in management to foster economic productivity, the Japanese model prioritises the engagement of key stakeholders like banks, unions, and

suppliers in decision-making processes, reducing the reliance on strong capital markets (Hiraki et al., 2003).

Barros et al. (2012) note that the Japanese governance framework promotes firm monitoring and flexible financing through enhanced communication with banks, which are crucial as primary funding sources. Kaplan and Minton (1994) suggest that control-oriented ownership often justifies limited share issuance to individuals, institutions, or banks that influence management strategies, aiming to secure long-term assurance relationships beyond mere financial gains.

Moreover, the direct involvement of the government in shaping corporate policy is significant, with the Central Bank and the Ministry of Finance playing a central role in governance through strategic collaboration (Hu and Izumida, 2008). An informal process known as Gyosei Shido allows government officials to influence corporate norms and policies, while Amakudari—the practice where senior bureaucrats move into high-profile roles in the corporate and public sectors—reflects state influence and has been criticised as corrupt and obstructive to economic and political reforms.

Contrary to the US, Japan's control-oriented governance is straightforward due to a robust shareholder structure, though Aoki (2000) points out that Japan faces significant challenges in improving governance quality and addressing corporate responsibility, largely due to the dominance of family-owned enterprises. In this context, banks and institutional investors usually play a minor role, primarily providing debt funding and occupying senior management positions, thus focusing more on monitoring and protecting foreign investors' interests in successful companies. This arrangement underscores a governance system that values the passivity of shareholders and the predominance of internal managers, anchored in strong, often isolated, management practices.

Aguilera and Jackson (2010) highlighted that while the core principles of corporate governance underscore the rights and obligations of various stakeholders, the application of these principles can vary significantly across different global business practices. Aoki (2000) and Letza et al. (2008) echo this sentiment, noting the diversity in business practices that lead to variations in governance models. Cox et al. (2004) suggested that legislative, economic, and financial reforms have driven the evolution of modern corporate governance, introducing a variety of theories and approaches into the field.

Cheffins (2000) argues that corporate governance is defined and styled in many ways to align with a company's goals, determine its management, identify challenges, and devise optimal solutions. Despite this diversity, Baskin and Miranti (1997), Cernat (2004), Freeman et al. (2004), and Letza et al. (2008) propose that corporate governance can essentially be classified into two main paradigms: shareholder and stakeholder. This classification underscores the common approaches taken to address corporate issues. However, Letza et al. (2008) suggest that addressing these issues requires a broader perspective that solves problems and fulfils the broader needs of stakeholders and shareholders.

2.1.5 Corporate Governance Model of Bangladesh

Bangladesh predominantly adheres to an insider or relationship-based corporate governance model, commonly seen in emerging economies and influenced by the Continental European system, yet distinctly shaped by local factors. The corporate landscape in Bangladesh is characterised by a high concentration of family ownership, where founding family members often control management and decision-making. This familial control impacts the dynamics of corporate governance significantly (Rahman and Hasan, 2017).

The Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) oversees the regulatory environment, which enforces guidelines aimed at aligning corporate governance practices with international standards. These efforts enhance transparency, accountability, and fairness (Kabir and Rahman, 2016). However, the effectiveness of these regulations is sometimes limited by the still-developing nature of Bangladesh's financial markets, which lack the depth and liquidity found in more mature economies.

Banks and financial institutions play a crucial role, similar to their counterparts in Germany, but the financial sector's evolving state affects its governance capabilities (Hossain and Akter, 2018). Additionally, the capital market's limited development curtails its role in corporate control, thereby increasing reliance on internal governance mechanisms and significant stakeholders.

There is a growing recognition of the importance of broader stakeholder interests, reflecting a shift towards more sustainable and inclusive business practices. This evolution in perspective is driven by global trends and a local push towards better corporate accountability (Ahmed and Chowdhury, 2018). As Bangladesh continues to develop its corporate governance framework, these changes aim to bolster investor confidence and promote sustainable economic growth.

2.1.6 Review of corporate governance's theoretical frameworks

Over the past decade, several authors, including Cremers and Nair (2005), Donaldson and Preston (1995), Fama and Jensen (1983), and Hart (1995) have explored the nexus between corporate governance and business performance, introducing various theoretical frameworks such as agency, stakeholder, stewardship, and resource dependency theories. Despite their differing perspectives on corporate management, these theories collectively

affirm that balancing external and internal governance mechanisms is crucial for establishing a robust governance structure.

Weir et al. (2002) advocate for internal governance systems as advanced management tools that monitor a company's progress and initiate corrective measures when operational realities diverge from strategic goals. Cremers and Nair (2005) highlight that internal controls involve management oversight through mechanisms like independent audit committees, board accountability, and the segregation of control from policy-making. Barth et al. (2003) suggest that such processes foster long-term relationships between management and non-equity stakeholders, ensuring protection through adequate legislation.

Conversely, Foster and Nguyen (2021) pointed out that businesses are also governed by external systems imposed by stakeholders including regulators, states, labor unions, and financial institutions. Baber & Liang (2008) support this view, arguing that external controls prevent unethical corporate behaviours and promote principles of transparency, accountability, and integrity, benefiting not just shareholders but also customers, employees, and the broader community.

Babatunde and Olaniran (2009) note that local governments typically establish external mechanisms in line with international standards to enhance accounting, auditing, financial transparency, and labor regulations. Such mechanisms ensure fair and transparent treatment of all stakeholders. Naciri (2009) adds that government regulations compel businesses to adopt rational managerial practices, fostering accountability. However, Denis (2001) warns that these measures only enhance performance if universally adhered to; lax enforcement can lead to fraudulent activities and suppress entrepreneurial ventures.

Despite the apparent separation, the interplay between internal and external governance systems is often complementary. Fama & Jensen (1983), Hart (1995), Freeman (2009), and La Porta et al. (2002) concur that both types of mechanisms can enhance each other under certain conditions. Baber and Liang (2008) suggest that internal management practices may evolve in response to the demands of external governance, creating a dynamic where both systems enhance corporate governance from different angles.

Several theoretical models of corporate governance have been proposed and studied from different perspectives concerning corporate governance and firm performance. However, Solomon (2007) pointed out that there are significant common characteristics among the theories, and they propose a variety of control structures, regulations, and guidelines designed to align corporate objectives with stakeholder needs and interests. Haniffa & Hudaib (2006) and Herly & Sisnuhadi (2011) suggest that while internal and external governance systems often operate inversely, finding the optimal balance can maximise shareholder value.

This study aims to deepen understanding of how internal corporate governance systems affect financial performance in Bangladeshi banks. Given the complexity of the corporate governance code in Bangladesh, a multi-theoretical approach is essential to assess various elements of this Code, which will be elaborated on in subsequent sections.

2.1.6.1 Agency Theory

Corporate governance is a critical aspect of managing modern organisations, where a clear separation often exists between ownership and management. This separation creates a dynamic that agency theory seeks to explain and resolve. Agency theory, particularly in the context of the banking sector, highlights the potential conflicts between owners (principals) and managers (agents). This theory is vital in assessing corporate governance's effectiveness,

especially in regions like Bangladesh, where the banking sector plays a pivotal role in economic stability and growth.

Agency theory suggests that in organisations where ownership is separated from management, conflicts can arise between the goals of the entity's owners and the actions of its managers. The dispute between owners and the managers is vastly observed in the work of many famous scholars like Berle and Means (1932), Jensen and Meckling (1976), Dalton et al. (1999), Shankman (1999), Roberts (2004), Hendry (2005), Krambia-Kapardis and Psaros (2006) and Ermongkonhai (2010). Scholars like Jensen and Meckling (1976) define this within the framework of the principal-agent relationship, where owners delegate authority to managers, who may not always act in the owners' best interests due to conflicting interests or information asymmetry. This misalignment can lead to agency problems, which, if not adequately addressed, can result in inefficiencies and economic losses (Eisenhardt, 1989; Jensen and Meckling, 1976).

Many researchers (Fama and Jensen, 1983; Hart, 1995; Jensen and Meckling, 1976; and Letza et al., 2008) agreed that the agency relationship might result in shareholder losses since agents are constantly tempted to maximise their own interests. For example, Blair (1995) stated that when executive compensation links to a company's profit, management can prioritise investments in projects that yield a higher short-term gain instead of focusing on long-term shareholder value through investments in long-term projects. This behaviour was often mirrored in the Bangladeshi banking sector, where the expansionist strategies were driven by management's pursuit of personal bonuses and status enhancement.

Mallin (2016), Murphy (1985), and Shleifer and Vishny (1997) support the conclusion of Fama and Jensen (1983) that managers have a strong motivation to expand the company beyond what is necessary, even if it harms shareholder value, in order to increase

their own compensation or status within the company. Murphy (1985) hypothesised that managers would give precedence to company growth rather than safeguarding shareholder value if they were aware that their remuneration and social standing were closely linked to the company's magnitude. When management prioritises their interests over the shareholders' desire to maximise their assets, priorities are misaligned.

Jensen and Meckling's (1976) seminal work on agency theory highlights a fundamental tension between management and shareholders, particularly over how profits should be allocated—whether reinvested in potentially profitable projects or distributed as dividends. This discourse is expanded by Jensen and Murphy (1990), who note that management often retains cash to safeguard against future investments, which may not necessarily align with shareholder desires for immediate returns. This dynamic can encourage management to build personal influence and control within the company, potentially at the expense of shareholder value.

Eisenhardt (1989), along with Ermongkonchai (2010) and Dey (2008), critiques this perspective by asserting that such management behaviours exemplify the broader agency dilemma where management actions may not inherently serve the best interests of the shareholders, leading to potential managerial excesses and necessitating stricter corporate governance mechanisms. This is further supported by Cronqvist & Nilsson (2003) who argue that management's engagement in activities that do not directly benefit shareholders can lead to abuses of power and necessitate government intervention.

The problem of aligning management's interests with those of shareholders is complex, as highlighted by Letza et al. (2008) and Aguilera and Jackson (2010), who assert that businesses should primarily focus on maximising shareholder value and eschew social responsibilities that might detract from this goal. However, this narrow focus on shareholder

value has been criticised for encouraging short-sighted management behaviours that prioritise immediate financial gains over long-term corporate health, leading to what Solomon (2007) refers to as “residual losses”—losses incurred due to conflicts of interest within the firm.

Keasey et al. (1997) suggest that crafting an optimal compensation plan that ties management’s rewards directly to the firm’s performance can mitigate some aspects of the agency problem. Yet, as Masulis et al. (2017) illustrates, agency conflicts can emerge from various managerial decisions that prioritise personal security over risk and innovation. These include choosing safer projects that lessen financial risk, focusing on short-term achievements to secure one’s position, or avoiding initiatives that might jeopardise personal financial investments.

According to Roberts (2004), the agency theory’s shareholder perspective can be maintained through the market’s use of hostile takeovers, mergers, and acquisitions to manage underperforming firms and protect owner interests. However, according to Hendry (2005), this opportunistic attitude of agents can lead to the incongruity of goals; because of the short-term profit gain, management tries to make out hefty bonuses or treat themselves to executive vacations or luxury cars, among other things. Therefore, the stock price of the corporation can drop. Solomon (2007) pointed out that it often refers to “residual losses” in agency terminology. Masulis et al. (2017) developed four critical scenarios illustrating how agency conflicts can arise when business owners and agents have conflicting interests.

1. Managers prefer practices and strategies that do not reduce their pay or the value of their stock, such as more spending and less intensive work.
2. Managers tend to choose lesser-risk projects to lessen financial leverage and avoid losses on their management equity and portfolios, reducing the danger of economic collapse resulting in liquidation.

3. Managers focus on obtaining approval from the short-term investment horizon to secure their own jobs.
4. Managers circumvent economic problems resulting from reduced levels of jobs that increase with uncertainty in company controls.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) argue convincingly that in addressing agency problems, mechanisms must be established to ensure the checks and balances on the influence of individual agents. This concept is echoed by Hendry (2005), Jensen and Meckling (1976), and others who advocate for a mix of internal and external strategies to better align the interests of agents (managers) and principals (shareholders). Solomon (2007) specifically discusses the formation of a “nexus” of optimal contracts to govern these relationships, emphasising that such contracts can involve actions such as independent audits and adjusting managerial ownership stakes to better align with corporate governance objectives.

However, while these mechanisms can be beneficial, they also introduce significant costs and complexities. McColgan (2001) highlights that to curb the divergent behaviour of agents, principals need to design compensation structures that adequately motivate agents to act in the company’s best interest. This involves upfront costs and ongoing expenses related to monitoring and enforcing these agreements, known as agency costs. Fama & Jensen (1983) argue that these costs are eventually offset by adjustments in agent compensation, suggesting a dynamic interplay where both parties continuously negotiate their economic relationship.

Nevertheless, as Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) point out, crafting an ideal agent-principal contract is challenging because it must perfectly balance the costs of monitoring with the benefits derived from the agent’s aligned behaviour, a state rarely achieved in practice. The complexity increases as firms scale up, where the sheer size makes it impractical for management to address every contingency, leading to what McColgan (2001)

terms “residual losses” — the costs arising from imperfect alignment of management and shareholder interests despite the best contractual efforts.

The UK’s corporate governance framework, shaped by reports such as the Cadbury Report (1992) and the Greenbury Report (1995), has responded to these theoretical insights by recommending governance practices that enhance board independence and rotate leadership roles to prevent power consolidation. Fama and Jensen (1983) support this approach, advocating for structured internal controls and committees that oversee and limit managerial discretion, thereby reducing opportunities for managerial excesses.

Additionally, Monks and Minow (2004) propose diverse remuneration schemes that reward agents based on performance, commitment, and loyalty, further aligning their interests with those of the shareholders. However, Eisenhardt (1989) cautions that implementing such controls is costly and time-consuming, and the effectiveness of these governance mechanisms must be continuously evaluated against the costs they incur.

While the foundational theories by Jensen and Meckling (1976) and others provide a stark depiction of the potential conflicts in corporate governance, the application of these theories in improving governance structures through enhanced regulatory frameworks, stricter auditing processes, and more aligned compensation plans could significantly mitigate these issues in the Bangladeshi corporate context. For instance, while establishing independent and non-executive board members can enhance decision-making objectivity, the cultural context and market dynamics unique to Bangladesh may influence the effectiveness of such governance structures. Furthermore, rotating the roles of CEO and Chairman, as practiced in the UK, might be adapted to fit local corporate structures and legal frameworks to prevent conflicts of interest and promote a more balanced power distribution within companies. This approach addresses the immediate agency problems and sets a sustainable

framework for corporate governance that could lead to long-term benefits for managers and shareholders.

2.1.6.2 Agency Problems in Banks

The principal-agent problem in banking manifests through various scenarios, notably when decision-making is delegated to managers whose interests might diverge from other stakeholders, such as shareholders or depositors. Aguilera and Jackson (2010) attribute these issues to the classic divide between ownership and control, with Berle and Means (1932), Blair (1995), and Barth et al. (2003) asserting that management may pursue personal objectives at the expense of shareholders.

This challenge is particularly pronounced in the context of Bangladesh's banking sector. However, mechanisms exist to counteract such trends. Demsetz and Villalonga (2001) suggests that concentrated external ownership can motivate shareholders to control managerial decisions more significantly. Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Denis (2001) propose that aligning managerial incentives with shareholder interests through substantial equity stakes can diminish agency conflicts. Additionally, Cronqvist and Nilsson (2003) point out that the takeover market checks managerial excess by threatening replacements for inefficient management.

Yet, these mechanisms face significant challenges when extending the agency problem to the context of banks in Bangladesh. The banking sector's inherent complexity and the critical role of banks in the national economy introduce heightened risks and consequences associated with agency problems. For instance, the asymmetry of information, where bank owners possess more comprehensive financial knowledge than depositors, can lead to decisions that unduly elevate risk profiles to the detriment of depositors and other creditors, reflecting the extended agency theory concerns.

Dey (2008) points out that bank owners, carrying only a portion of the downside risk, can reap disproportionate benefits from high-risk ventures due to limited liability and legal protections, leaving depositors to face significant potential losses without any corresponding gain. This scenario is particularly pertinent in Bangladesh, where the regulatory framework and enforcement mechanisms may not always be robust enough to mitigate such risks effectively.

Moreover, the agency problem between depositors and shareholders is one of the most scrutinised issues in banking, as financial markets' inherent volatility demands vigilant regulatory oversight. Central banks, including those in Bangladesh, are increasingly focused on creating mechanisms like capital adequacy requirements and deposit insurance schemes to address these issues.

According to Callen and Fang (2013), Corporate governance problems arise in banks when management's risk preferences deviate from those of other stakeholders. Instances of managerial incompetence or intentional misuse of power due to inadequate control mechanisms can exacerbate these agency problems, leading to decisions that may not align with the long-term stability of the bank.

Furthermore, insider lending, identified by Caprio et al. (2011) as a primary cause for bank failures, exemplifies moral hazards where bank funds are diverted to high-risk, high-return ventures, benefiting management at the cost of financial stability. This situation underscores the need for stringent oversight and governance to curtail such risky behaviours in Bangladeshi banks.

Reflecting on historical discourse, the agency theory initially recognised by Berle and Means (1932) has profoundly influenced the understanding of corporate governance. Subsequent research by scholars like Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Fama and Jensen

(1983) has provided a foundation for examining corporate governance through the lens of ownership structure, board procedures, and capital structure, aiming to ensure robust governance practices.

However, critiques by Davis et al. (1997) and Henrekson and Jakobsson (2012) challenge the adequacy of agency theory in addressing global corporate governance intricacies. They argue for more empowered managerial decision-making and note the theory's shortfalls in accommodating long-term strategic investments critical for sustainable corporate growth. These critiques have led to the development of models like the "myopic market model," which posits that market pressures often drive managers to prioritise short-term gains over long-term shareholder interests. This suggests that enhanced corporate governance in Bangladesh should foster a culture valuing long-term success.

In conclusion, while agency theory has its limitations, it remains a vital framework in understanding and addressing corporate governance issues, particularly in Bangladesh's banking sector. Ongoing research suggests the need for adaptations to better suit the modern economic landscape of different countries, including the unique context of Bangladesh.

2.1.6.3 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory integrates social and organisational disciplines as an alternative to agency theory. It is the second most relevant corporate governance theory to understand the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms and bank performances in Bangladesh. According to Clarkson (1995), this theory posits that businesses owe obligations to a broader group of stakeholders, not just shareholders. Blair (1995) highlighted that the core framework of the theory is that a corporation must strive to maximise value and wealth for all stakeholders, not just shareholders. Freeman (2009) emphasised that the theory considers various stakeholders involved in and impacted by the business's operations, whether

individuals, groups, or society. In the 1970s, Donaldson and Preston (1995) noted that stakeholder theory was part of the management literature. The theory underwent a lengthy transition, with Freeman (1984) significantly contributing to the incorporation of corporate accountability and the role of multiple stakeholders. Freeman articulated the idea by posing two crucial questions: firstly, what are a company's primary goals and objectives? Secondly, what is management's primary responsibility in managing various stakeholders?

Krambia-Kapardis and Psaros (2006) affirmed that stakeholder theory supports a mutual partnership between a company and its stakeholders, influencing business operations. Identified stakeholders include customers, employees, creditors, vendors, governments, and society. According to Freeman et al. (2004), strategy development and implementation should consider stakeholders' interests and their interrelations. Lepineux (2005) added that the theory gives significant attention to a wider range of interest groups previously overlooked and emphasises their importance in leadership views. Freeman (2009) argued that viewing the network as a site of enhanced corporate performance facilitates inclusive stakeholder engagement, a critical aspect of the theory.

However, Donaldson and Preston (1995) contended that not all parties involved in a company's operations have the same financial objectives. For example, consumers and shareholders have different goals and satisfactions. Shareholders aim to increase their wealth by providing risk capital to firms, whereas consumers seek satisfactory products or services. Therefore, the importance placed on interested groups is determined by the level of protectionism allowed to them. Clarkson (1995) emphasised the importance of management protecting all stakeholders' interests equally, as none can come before or after the others. Bangladesh's banking sector includes a variety of stakeholders such as customers, employees, shareholders, regulators, and the broader community. Stakeholder theory, which

emphasises understanding and balancing these diverse interests, can provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating how well a bank is managing its relationships with these groups.

Berman et al. (1999) noted that the relationship between stakeholders and management agents results from explicit and implicit contracts within the overarching governance structure. These relationships must be protected. Jones (1995) argued that it is insufficient to define and recognise stakeholder groups within the legal framework; the correct administration of these groups must also consider operational effectiveness and efficiency.

However, Donaldson and Preston (1995) argued that action theory has little relevance in today's capitalist context, where structural reforms are required, and stakeholders' expectations and benefits have yet to be realised. While the idea has practical applications, Turnbull (1999) suggested that it suffers from several faults, undermining the concept's literary sense and empirical basis. Similarly, Wood and Jones (1995) identified several similarities and factors linking agency theory with stakeholder theory, suggesting that the principal and agency relationship can be viewed as a subgroup of the general relationship within the agency theory framework.

Turnbull (1999) also found that aligning conflicting interests among stakeholders, particularly in the banking sector, is a common criticism of stakeholder theory. Carroll and Buchholtz (2008) argued that expecting all stakeholders to be represented in corporate governance proposals is unrealistic without jeopardising a company's success. The theory's hazy premise and questionable validity are significant concerns in the modern business environment.

Solomon (2007) pointed out that identifying stakeholders is a significant flaw in stakeholder theory. The broad term encompasses various individuals or groups, making creating value and profit for shareholders while meeting their needs challenging. Knyazeva et al. (2013) argued that the theory needs to be flexible and adaptable for different regulatory systems, cautioning against light regulation due to increased instability. Berman et al. (1999) added that the Anglo-Saxon system in the banking industry fosters a dynamic market by providing access to global capital.

Banks impact all their stakeholders as financial intermediaries. According to Ali (2015), stakeholders such as depositors, debtors, governments, insurance companies, beneficiaries, and systemic externalities have different goals and expectations from a bank. For instance, bondholders and regulators desire low volatility, while investors anticipate capital recovery. Legal authorities expect taxes from banks, and workers seek monetary compensation.

Berman et al. (1999) noted that banks' financial market activity significantly impacts interest rates, asset prices, and market uncertainty. Banks provide funds for investments by making loans. Coombs and Gilley (2005) argued that the actions of depositors, savers, and bondholders affect banks, receiving liquidity from savers and the public. Driscoll and Starik (2004) claimed that banks might raise interest rates due to ineffective corporate governance, leading to decreased economic investment. Loss of customer faith can deplete a bank's liquidity, exposing it to various risks, including reputational, operational, and compliance risks. Effective stakeholder management can mitigate these risks. By considering the needs and expectations of different stakeholders, banks can proactively address issues that might otherwise lead to crises or conflicts. This is particularly relevant in Bangladesh, where the

banking sector has faced challenges related to non-performing loans and financial malpractices.

Rueda-Manzanares et al. (2008) argued that the legal environment, regulatory authorities, and financial service providers can affect corporate governance mechanisms. Employees may push for more transparency and representation in decision-making bodies. Kelly et al. (1997) suggested compliance with best practice Corporate Governance standards to reduce the agency problem and boost shareholder value creation. Strategies include limiting executive boards, separating the chairman and CEO roles, establishing an independent auditing board, and ensuring minority shareholder voting rights. The banking industry in Bangladesh is subject to significant regulatory oversight. Stakeholder theory can help assess how banks adhere to regulatory standards and ethical practices, crucial for maintaining trust and stability in the financial system. Banks can align their operations with legal and ethical expectations by focusing on broader stakeholder interests, enhancing their reputation and operational stability. Besides, this theory encourages greater transparency and accountability in corporate governance. Banks can enhance their accountability by engaging with stakeholders and disclosing relevant information about business operations and governance practices. This is crucial in Bangladesh, where transparency in banking operations can lead to improved public trust and investor confidence.

Orts and Strudler (2009) pointed out that market-level corporate governance should include regulation and supervision beyond the banking sector to safeguard consumers and foster competition. Phillips (1997) referred to corporate-level governance as the internal procedures established within an organisation to control management actions and generate long-term value and sustainability through strategic planning. This means achieving short-term financial targets and setting up robust frameworks for long-term success for

Bangladesh's banks. This involves investing in community development, environmental sustainability, and innovative banking practices that meet the evolving needs of stakeholders.

Incorporating stakeholder theory into the evaluation of corporate governance and the performance of banks in Bangladesh provides a holistic view that goes beyond financial metrics to include social, ethical, and environmental dimensions. This broader perspective is essential for fostering Bangladesh's responsible, inclusive, and sustainable banking sector. Combining stakeholder and agency theories has several advantages for assessing the effectiveness of Bangladesh's corporate governance code in the current banking systems. According to stakeholder theory, fairly treating all stakeholder groups is a moral obligation. However, Deegan (2002) noted that the theory has been criticised for not delivering improved corporate governance and its incompatibility with key organisational aims. Driscoll and Starik (2004) suggested that balancing different stakeholder needs without a stewardship philosophy would be extremely difficult.

2.1.6.4 Supporting Theories

The majority of corporate governance research is mostly reliance on the stakeholder theory and the agency theory. However, as previously mentioned, it is pretty challenging to encapsulate the Bangladeshi corporate governance structure within only these two theoretical frameworks; therefore, this study would like to explore the different theoretical perspectives available in the literature on corporate governance and bank performance.

2.1.6.5 Information Asymmetry and Managerial Signalling theory

The concepts of information asymmetry and managerial signalling are key to understanding the relationship between a company's managers and its shareholders. Kapopoulos and Lazaretou (2007) explain that managers and agents often have more information than shareholders, leading to economic or power imbalances that can result in

market failures. Specifically, agents have more insider knowledge about the business and its financial standing than the principals.

Recent studies confirm this issue. Zhang et al. (2020) highlight that information asymmetry is still a significant problem in corporate governance, contributing to economic imbalances and inefficiencies. Byun et al. (2011) also noted that potential shareholders face two main problems when deciding on investments: moral hazard and adverse selection. Moral hazard happens when owners or principals do not fully understand the agreed-upon transaction and cannot take legal action against agents for breaking the agreement (Kapopoulos & Lazaretou, 2007). Rhee and Lee (2008) added that adverse selection occurs when investors or principals lack accurate, relevant data while negotiating or contracting with the most competent agents who have all the relevant information. This makes it less likely for investors or principals to make the best possible decisions.

Recent literature also suggests that companies following good governance practices can signal their reliability to potential investors. Li and Wang (2019) argue that firms with strong governance structures are seen as better-managed enterprises, reducing the selection dilemma regarding investment. Ntim and Osei (2019) also noted that the problem of information asymmetry is lessened when potential shareholders pay a premium for shares, expecting greater profits from well-governed organisations compared to those without efficient corporate governance.

In Bangladesh, addressing information asymmetry and managerial signalling is crucial for corporate governance and bank performance. The banking sector faces unique challenges, including regulatory constraints and changing market dynamics, which worsen issues related to information asymmetry. Effective corporate governance practices are

essential to ensure transparency, accountability, and equitable information distribution among all stakeholders.

Recent studies on the Bangladeshi banking sector, such as those by Islam et al. (2021), highlight the importance of implementing strong governance frameworks to attract and retain investors. These frameworks help reduce the risks associated with moral hazard and adverse selection. By following best practices in corporate governance, banks can enhance their credibility and performance, contributing to the overall stability and growth of the financial sector in Bangladesh.

This analysis emphasises the need for comprehensive governance codes and promoting transparency to tackle the challenges posed by information asymmetry and managerial signalling in the Bangladeshi banking sector.

2.1.6.6 Stewardship theory

As an alternative to agency theory, Stewardship theory offers valuable insights into corporate governance and bank performance, particularly in Bangladesh. The theory's emphasis on managers as stewards who are intrinsically motivated to act in the best interests of their organisation provides a framework for understanding and improving corporate governance practices in Bangladeshi banks. According to Letza et al. (2004), the theory proposes that managers should be granted sufficient authority to ensure the company's business operations are carried out efficiently, as managers are good stewards of an organisation's resources. This perspective can be particularly beneficial for Bangladeshi banks, where trust and ethical management are essential for stability and performance. By promoting a culture of trust and responsibility among bank managers, stewardship theory can lead to better decision-making and enhanced performance.

Henssen et al. (2014) highlighted that this theory believes managers are motivated by the aspiration and satisfaction of accomplishing complex tasks. Donaldson and Davis (2017) further noted that stewardship theory emphasises the responsibilities of stewards, such as senior management, and their role in achieving the organisation's goals. When a steward ensures that an organisation operates effectively and generates returns for its shareholders, the steward is considered successful.

Stewardship theory frequently advocates for role duality, supporting the integration of the chairman and chief executive officer responsibilities. Donaldson and Davis (2017) observe that boards composed solely of non-executive directors cannot perform their functions effectively. Arthurs and Busenitz (2003) added that it is sensible for delegates to work with a board controlled by executives. However, Hendry (2005) questions whether such a committee is necessary for a company's success. Tricker (2000) stated that a fiduciary director must be dependable and act in the company's best interests to supervise tasks and other executives. In Anglo-Saxon law, the stewardship concept is based on these expectations of the director's role and responsibility. However, Arthurs and Busenitz (2003) argued that a steward's obligations carry more weight than those associated with simple agents because stewards work for the company even when making their own decisions, contradicting the central ideology of agency theory. According to Muth and Donaldson (1998), Canadian companies are renowned for leading their industries. Some organisations advocate eliminating the board of directors and replacing it with an advisory body to reduce the likelihood of unethical behaviour.

Researchers such as Arthurs and Busenitz (2003), Davis et al. (1997), and Muth and Donaldson (1998) have compared stewardship and agency theories, claiming both are beneficial but tend to refute each other. Thus, a corporation can select either management

method. According to Donaldson and Davis (2017), stewardship theory distinguishes between organisations that grant stewards authority and those that support stewards' efforts to maximise shareholder returns and decrease costs, also known as agency costs, identified by Jensen and Meckling (1983). Dalton et al. (1998) argued that in agency theory, decision-making powers lead to the inevitable opportunistic behaviour of managers, whereas in stewardship theory, it serves as a motivating factor. In both theories, Tricker (2000) claimed that imposing strong sanctions and incentives drives such behaviour. Muth and Donaldson (1998) noted that this is common in Anglo-cultural areas where people tend to follow the law. The effects of a highly regulated industry, where shareholders have significant power over the board and management, are not considered in arguments about incompatibility. Thus, companies can make informed decisions regarding board and investor collaboration.

The concept of stewardship presumes that company executives always act in their companies' best interests. Under this principle, managers are believed to be reliable stewards of their firms. Directors, appointed at the Annual General Meeting, are entrusted with authority and are answerable to shareholders. The theory suggests that those who work on behalf of company management strive to be respectable managers of the company and do not detach themselves from the firm's interests and those of other stakeholders. Eisenhardt (1989) added that this behaviour works within the limits of stewardship theory as an influential factor in corporate governance since stewards strive for excellence on behalf of shareholders, avoiding personal gain at their expense.

Turnbull (1999) noted that the institution's nature and other factors influence how individuals act as administrators or proxies. This suggests that the theory may be seen as contradictory and rooted in policy frameworks and corporate governance structures. Turnbull (1999) urged further research to adopt the philosophy underpinning stewardship theory.

However, Hart (1995) argued that individual differences matter when determining the significance of money and acceptance. People alternate between acting competitively and cooperatively, reflecting the opportunistic potential in businesses, among board members, and in the stewardship theory.

Hawley and Williams (1996) stated that from the stewardship perspective, corporate directors and managers are seen as the firm's administrators, making decisions based on their advantages and interests as company owners. This theory results in behaviour directed by administrators' activities through collective management to maintain an efficient governance structure. Glinkowska and Kaczmarek (2015) argued that newly formed businesses' corporate governance practices often do not prioritise employees' needs. Employee participation at all organisational levels is essential for successfully implementing excellent corporate governance procedures. Effective coordination of internal business operations is necessary to achieve organisational goals.

Pagano and Volpin (2001) stated that stewardship theory holds directors responsible for safeguarding corporate assets against opportunistic behaviour and conflicts of interest on behalf of various stakeholders. The theory's philosophy aligns closely with other corporate governance theories discussed here. It assumes that the control business managers offer enables them to maximise overall performance and profitability, providing theoretical support for corporate governance.

For organisations to successfully implement good corporate governance practices, certain prerequisites must be met. Jensen and Meckling (2006) agreed that corporate governance from a stewardship perspective should be based on stakeholders' opinions and reputations. Directors should protect corporate assets from conflicts of interest and opportunistic behaviour, yet in practice, such behaviour does not always align with this

ideology. Holthausen and Thomas (2001) claimed that managers should have more authority and responsibility by focusing on achieving corporate objectives through leadership and efficient operational decisions. The main reason stewardship theory has not gained widespread acceptance is that, while presenting compelling arguments regarding moral obligations and directors' roles, a manager acting as a custodian of a company's interests may endanger investors if personal interests do not align with shareholders'. The implications of agency theory do not eliminate the risk of managers acting against their own interests. Nonetheless, stewardship theory offers significant benefits for effective corporate governance compared to other theoretical perspectives.

In summary, stewardship theory offers a comprehensive framework for improving Bangladesh's corporate governance and bank performance. By emphasising trust, intrinsic motivation, unified leadership, and cultural appropriateness, the theory provides valuable insights for developing effective governance practices. This study can leverage these insights to propose governance reforms and managerial practices that enhance the performance and stability of Bangladeshi banks, ultimately contributing to the sector's long-term success.

2.1.6.7 Resource dependency theory

Resource dependence is an umbrella of thought, led by writers like Burt (1983), that directly links directors of the external environment and the company. According to this idea, corporate governance is a collection of systems designed to effectively manage the network of interdependencies between access to dangerous resources and the management of those resources. The theory suggests that outsiders as directors or independent directors from outside the organisation efficiently use all the business's resources. According to Hillman et al. (2007) the Board of Directors is viewed as a resource by the resource dependence theory that the company can use to produce output. Wernerfelt (1984) further added that board

members can access valuable information and resources during difficult times. Therefore, Incorporating boards of directors into internal corporate governance structures are not intended to retain or supervise managers but rather to ensure that the crucial resources are used effectively to maximise the financial performance readily available to companies. Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) pointed out that the resource dependence theory allows organisations to attempt to control their environment by collecting survival-critical resources. This is one of the theory's most fundamental pillars. The theory suggests that companies are open systems dependent on the perpetual organisation of environmental contingencies, which in many cases, enhances the company's overall performance and efficiency. Similarly, board directors are indispensable in enhancing a firm's business prospects. For instance, board members' networks and connections outside the company can be used to promote the company's expansion and its long-term prospects.

In the context of Bangladesh, where corporate governance and bank performance are pivotal, the Resource Dependency Theory offers valuable insights. By integrating knowledgeable and connected directors into bank boards, banks can gain strategic advantages in navigating regulatory environments and capital markets. This approach enhances the governance framework and contributes significantly to the stability and growth of financial institutions in Bangladesh.

2.1.6.8 Corporate Governance: A fresh way of thinking

In the modern world, a fresh way of thought has evolved that criticises the polarising approach to corporate governance and pushes the bounds of what has previously been regarded as corporate governance. The fresh way of thinking challenges the polarised corporate governance perspective and examines it from two extreme views. According to Cuervo (2002) and Letza et al. (2004), firstly, The idea disregards the fact that the nature of

reality is not fixed; instead, it is a continuous motion, and secondly, the concept firmly assumes that the inflexible concept of social reality as ideal/perfect and immovable. Zingales (2000) further argued that the old method of thinking might be helpful in a world where intensive assets are significantly more crucial to take advantage of economies of scale. Still, Vinten (2001) argued that the business reality is not static, and the organisation's business methods and structure are changing daily. They contend that the corporation may find it safer to give shareholders priority in equity-related matters as a result of this shifting nature. It can be necessary to emphasise stakeholders' interests at a later stage for sustainable growth. Because of this, focusing solely on a single static model is unrealistic and ineffective in ensuring better governance.

The clearest arguments against this polarised conceptualisation come from (Cuervo, 2002; Dobbin and Jung, 2010; Kelly et al., 1997; Letza et al., 2008; Mueller, 1995; and Vinten, 2001), who emphasise the fact that the reality itself is not fixed in nature and can vary depending on the requirements of the time. Concerning this claim, they suggested a new form of corporate governance considering that it is transformable, dynamic, and can be implemented through innovation to meet the uncertain needs of the corporate world. These assertions are supported by a proposal by Filatotchev et al. (2013), which states that there may be a connection between corporate governance standards and the firm's strategic inflection points throughout its life cycle and that substantial alterations may accompany these transitions to the governance system. On the other hand, studies by (Aguilera and Jackson, 2010; Argandoña and Hoivik, 2009) make an indistinguishable argument that a single model does not work and that the appropriate system that works is the most effective, the best for the company at the time, and that a rule that suits everyone is flawed. This argument suggests that corporate governance models differ over time between countries, sectors, and even within the same company. Therefore, Cuervo (2002) argued it is not

insightful to predetermine a particular model without prior empirical evidence, and it is wise to explore all of the possibilities of different existing models.

Foster and Nguyen (2021) argued the need for further research to identify innovative approaches to governance that go beyond the dichotomised and static theoretical traditional approach of corporate governance. A new approach to governance must recognise today's corporate reality and the progress of modern society. According to Aguilera and Jackson (2010), , a different approach can be developed by incorporating components from existing corporate governance models that address both domestic and international issues. The existing models' qualities have their advantages and were created in response to the needs of a specific era, and they can be tailored to fit a particular situation even if they are not universally applicable. Letza et al. (2008) claimed that this approach provides better insights into governance systems, which helps to create better ways of solving existing problems with an effective corporate governance framework.

In conclusion, it is assumed that the emerging argument for the adequacy of governance models is that theoretical models are only feasible if research is carried out that identifies dynamic and pluralistic approaches to explaining the characteristic function of local corporate governance as opposed to forcing reality to fit an idealised model.

2.1.6.9 The Process of Adopting a Code and Institutional Theory

Existing research on governance suffers a significant number of drawbacks, one of which is an over-reliance on agency theory to explain the rationale behind various governance models. According to Creamer and Nairs (2005), agency theory and other theoretical approaches have failed to adequately account for the social aspects that contributed to the evolution of governance. Several researchers, such as (Dalton et al., 2003; Erkens et al., 2012; Judge et al., 2010; Okhmatovskiy and David, 2012; Paredes, 2005;

Suchman, 1995) feel that the agency theory fails to explain significant problems with corporate governance in developing nations adequately. Because of these limitations, researchers like Mir and Rahaman (2005) and Siddiqui (2010) have been forced to look for alternative theoretical frameworks, and institutional theory has emerged as the most preferred option among these alternatives.

The theory of the institutions describes “how numerous companies, even though they are different entities, have similar organisational structures and cultural features, and how organisations as institutions impact the behaviour of individual members.” Chua and Rahman, 2011; Mir and Rahaman, 2005). The institutional theory emphasises how social and cultural factors must be considered to comprehend corporate governance processes because many of the dynamics of the business environment are derived from cultural norms, values, and rituals. According to Scott (1995), the idea of Legitimacy inside an organisation is the foundation for the institutional theory, differentiating itself from preceding corporate management theories. Similarly, Suchman (1995) defined, Legitimacy as “a broad view or presumption that the acts of an entity in a social system are desirable, lawful and appropriate. Furthermor, Scott (1995) looks at the study of institutional theory, on how businesses adapt to such external macro-pressures to achieve legitimacy and support, and how extra-organisational institutions influence organisational structures and policies.

On the other hand, Deephouse and Carter (2005) and Dimaggio and Powell (1983) stressed that the degree of dependence on and validity of a source could be evaluated using various criteria, including acceptability, rationality, appropriateness, and coherence. Further added by Carroll and Buchholtz 2008; Dimaggio and Powell, 1983; Meyer & Rowan, 1977), businesses want to achieve legitimacy to exhibit consistency, credibility, and validity in their

operations. Legitimacy was described by Yoshikawa et al. (2007) as the social acceptance gained via abiding by regulatory, cognitive, and normative standards and norms.

On the other hand, (Chua and Rahman, 2011; Meyer & Rowan, 1977; Yoshikawa et al., 2007) believed that isomorphism is an essential component of the institutional theory that can be viewed from various angles. The primary reason for the growing interest in isomorphism is that it can result in Legitimacy Isomorphism was described by Hawley and Williams (1996) as a constraining mechanism that causes one unit in a population that is subject to the same environmental conditions to resemble the other. According to Mir and Rahman (2005), isomorphism and compliance expectations are essential elements that contribute to the development and success of organisations. The powerful institutional mechanisms that institutions use, like influential stakeholders, regulations, and requirements to get the appropriate support, rewards, and legitimacy, influence how organisations respond to compliance with their institutional environment.

Coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism, according to DiMaggio and Powell (1983), are the three main reasons of the institutional isomorphic transition process. Social norms cause coercive isomorphism in the society where an organisation operates as well as by formal and unofficial limitations imposed on it by other organisations on which it depends. In other cases, organisational transformation is a direct response to a command from the government, and these pressures may be interpreted as coercion, force, or requests to participate in the partnership. When organisational goals are ill-defined or when organisational technology is misunderstood, an unpredictable environment develops, which is a breeding ground for Mimetic isomorphism, as further explained by DiMaggio and Powell (1983). In addition, professionalism results in the emergence of normative isomorphism, and the following three aspects of professionalisation are key contributors to isomorphism: formal

education and the establishment of a cognitive foundation created by academic specialists; the professional network's growth and development, and association with professional trader.

Researchers have a significant amount of interest in studying these three mechanisms. Few studies have attempted to understand how changes in corporate governance have evolved in Bangladesh by using an institutional approach to the topic. For instance, Siddiqui (2010) looked into how Bangladesh developed its corporate governance standards and found that the most critical aspects of governance were exposed to pressures to act morally and with varying degrees of Legitimacy. The author claimed that Bangladesh had adopted the shareholder corporate governance model, even though its socio-economic structure does not lend itself well to supporting the shareholder model. As a result, Siddiqui (2010) expressed concern, arguing that the model's agency-based conceptions of market efficiency make it unsuitable for Bangladesh. Businesses like the concept of the legitimacy of diverse stakeholder groups over relying exclusively on shareholders because they are more willing to contribute resources to organisations that seem appealing and better suited to meet their needs. Similarly, Mir and Rahman (2005) examined Bangladesh's adoption of International Accounting Standards (IAS) in 2005, and their study found that most IAS paragraphs were replicated in Bangladesh under the name of Bangladesh Accounting Standards due to isomorphic pressure, which is less likely to ensure business performance and effectiveness in Bangladesh.

These results are a crucial stepping stone in comprehending Bangladesh's Code/standard development process; nonetheless, this study aims to go toward that aim by investigating the firm-level application of the Code in the banking industry. By using the same institutional setting, this study investigates whether or not companies are uniformly adopting the Code after its implementation. While the first two theories that have been

applied here deal with research problems, the institutional theory that has been implemented here promotes the analysis of a better understanding of these concerns and the development of solutions.

2.1.7 Synthesis of the Theories

According to Nicholson and Geoffrey (2003), three theories can shed light on the board's role in influencing the company's performance: Agency, Stewardship, and Resource Dependence theory. Windsor (2010) argued that based on the distinct sets of presumptions, agency theorists and stewardship theorists debate the nature of the link between board executives and performance. Agency theorists like (Berle and Means, 1932; Fama and Jensen, 1983; Jensen and Meckling, 1976) are bothered by the challenge of balancing the conflicting interests of business owners and management. They are primarily concerned with establishing links between business performance, managerial structure, and the autonomy of corporate boards. Stewardship theorists like Donaldson and Davis (2017) emphasise the importance of having a sufficient number of executive directors on the board of directors for good corporate governance. According to stewardship theory, people are inherently communal, reliable, and systematic, and management that looks out for the interests of the business's owners is a central tenet of stewardship theories. Agency theory, on the other hand, postulates that people will act in various economic and human ways, including selfish, opportunistic, and individualistic ways that put themselves first to the owner's detriment.

According to Arthurs and Busenitz (2003), the primary emphasis of agency theorists is the study of conflicts of interest between agent and principal or owner. In contrast, stakeholders theorists investigate problems relating to the interests of various stakeholder groups. Since Jensen and Meckling (1976) introduced it, the agency theory perspective has

been widely adopted. Moreover, it serves as the foundation for the development of governance standards and codes of principles for a variety of institutions.

Similarly, Davis et al. (1997) argued that the stewardship theory assumes that management acts in the company's best interests, granting them access to information, resources, and authority. Furthermore, Glinkowska and Kaczmarek (2015) added that complete jurisdiction enables management to make choices with the firm's best interests in mind. Because the integration and unification of chains of authority lead to faster decision-making in a good corporate governance structure, the CEO duality mechanism positively affects companies' financial performance according to stewardship theory. These benefits can be attributed to the fact that companies can make decisions more quickly.

Resource dependency theorists focus on the interactions between directors, which connect various aspects of a company's performance and behaviour. According to Burt (1983), resource dependency theory postulates that a company's success depends on its ability to build relationships to obtain the resources it needs. An organisation can function more effectively when a competent board consists of high-caliber senior management and an experienced and knowledgeable board of directors make strategic decisions. According to the resource dependence theory, the board has a greater connection to the external world, so the company can easily acquire vital resources such as equity and capital. Moreover, this happens because of improved corporate governance procedures under the theory's assumption (Hillman et al. 2007; Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). In addition, Crowther and Jatana (2007) argued that the resource dependency theorists emphasise the significance of executive resources by expanding the scope of the traditional roles of boards of directors in terms of control and responsibility while also taking into account action theory and perspective.

The concept of corporate governance was developed in reaction to a rise in unethical business practices and a number of corporate failures. OECD (2004) defines “Corporate governance” as “the framework within which an organisation’s operations are directed and controlled.”. Dobbin and Jung (2010) believed that both developed and developing countries could apply different theories to corporate governance in the same light because they are interchangeable. Corporate governance varies from nation to nation due to each nation’s unique cultural, historical, political, and social settings. It is more reasonable to use agency theory in developing countries because regulatory structures in these countries are generally inadequate. In contrast, countries with strict laws and regulations may choose different theoretical foundations such as stewardship or stakeholders theory to incorporate into their corporate governance standards.

In today’s business world, no particular corporate governance theory can accurately describe the variety and complexity of business operations. As a result, an individual theoretical perspective can not be an adequate foundation for developing effective corporate governance in any country, and the same concept applies to an emerging country like Bangladesh.

2.1.8 The Relationship between Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Firm Performance

Corporate governance employs various theoretical assumptions to address issues such as ownership and control, managerial decisions, stakeholder management, and information asymmetry. Both external and internal governance measures are crucial for resolving these concerns and ensuring long-term business success. For example, addressing the separation of ownership and control, corporate governance seeks methods by which shareholders can influence managerial decisions to safeguard their investments. Consequently, internal

mechanisms like CEO remuneration, directors' shares, and different executive boards play a pivotal role in reducing agency costs, as posited by agency theory.

Jensen and Meckling (1976) categorised governance mechanisms into internal and external types, which govern and control a company. According to Baber and Liang (2008), internal control mechanisms include financial policies (debt and dividends), ownership structure, board of directors, and firm compensation. These elements are vital for addressing internal corporate governance issues. Conversely, Babatunde and Olaniran (2009) identified external control mechanisms such as the legal system, corporate control market, international factors, and product markets. Bhuiyan and Biswas (2007) further noted that external governance procedures, typically a set of regulations outside banking firms, are designed to complement efficient internal governance by subjecting management to external disciplining factors like regulatory bodies. These controls and safeguards facilitate management and shareholder discipline by monitoring and protecting a company's operations.

Despite these mechanisms, the relationship between corporate governance structures and firm performance remains complex and often inconsistent. Research by Doucouliagos et al. (2007) on Australian banks categorised corporate governance monitoring systems into three distinct areas. Firstly, internal mechanisms such as board composition, board size, CEO duality, director ownership, CEO tenure, CEO salary, and board subcommittees aim to mitigate the risk of governance failures. Secondly, external factors including debts, corporate takeovers, and ownership shape the governing strategy. Lastly, government regulation, international accounting standards, and external audits influence a company's governance structure through institutional processes.

Hassan and Halbouni (2016) highlighted the global inconsistency and ambiguity in how corporate governance structures affect financial performance. Schultz et al. (2015)

examined this governance-performance relationship for businesses in the ASX 200 index between 2000 and 2007. Using variable proxies such as Tobin's Q, accounting profit rate, total returns, and return on assets as performance indicators, they aimed to understand company practices in compensation, board composition, and ownership. However, their study failed to establish a definitive link between corporate governance and firm success.

Comparing findings across different studies reveals significant disparities in the impact of corporate governance on bank performance. While some studies, like those of Doucouliagos et al. (2007), suggest that robust internal and external governance mechanisms can mitigate risks and enhance performance, others, like Schultz et al. (2015), found no clear connection between governance practices and firm success. Additionally, Adams and Mehran (2012) found that bank holding companies with larger boards perform better, suggesting that board size might be an essential factor in banking governance. Mollah and Zaman (2015) argued that Shariah supervisory boards positively affect Islamic banks' performance, indicating the importance of considering unique governance structures in different banking systems. These inconsistencies highlight the need for further research, particularly in diverse regulatory environments.

This research aims to fill the gap by exploring the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms specifically in the context of Bangladesh's banking sector, providing a more nuanced understanding of how these mechanisms influence bank performance in this unique setting.

2.2 Empirical literature review on internal corporate governance mechanisms and their relationship with the firm performance

This chapter delves into how internal corporate governance mechanisms relate to firm performance, especially within banks. Understanding how governance shapes bank performance is crucial since it affects financial stability and customer trust. To facilitate a structured analysis, this review categorises internal corporate governance mechanisms into four key areas: board composition, board and sub-committee activities, audit and financial policies, and ownership structure. Each category will be examined in detail, drawing on empirical studies to highlight how these governance elements impact the performance and stability of banks. This analysis sheds light on the intricate connections between governance practices and firm success, providing a comprehensive understanding of the internal dynamics that drive performance in the Bangladeshi banking industry.

2.2.1 Board composition

Increasing attention has been paid to board performance, composition, and director relationships. Researchers like Kim and Rasiah (2010) and Iwasaki (2008) have emphasised that various aspects of board composition are crucial internal governance mechanisms. Specifically, the focus has been on board size, diversity, performance, characteristics, and composition. Jensen (1993) argued that in contemporary corporate systems, managers hold fewer shares on the board, which supervises management and advises on behalf of shareholders. Jensen and Meckling (1976) noted that factors often pressure managers to act in their interests due to information asymmetry, impacting shareholders negatively.

The Board of Directors plays a crucial role in balancing investor and management needs. Corporate finance literature (Fama and Jensen, 1983; Jensen and Meckling, 1976) highlights the importance of board composition in developing effective corporate governance structures. Kim et al. (2013) outlined four primary responsibilities of directors: fiduciary duty, loyalty and fair dealing, due diligence, and supervisory duty. These duties involve managing finances, supporting shareholder interests, staying informed about company activities, and establishing ethical rules.

Research has explored how governance mechanisms, director quality and characteristics, diversity, independence, and ownership structures affect firm performance. Effective governance can mitigate traditional agency problems, with governing boards serving as essential mechanisms. Hoque and Muradoglu (2013) noted significant changes in board composition globally. For instance, in 2012, 86% of S&P 500 company boards had 12 or fewer directors, up from 68% in 2002. The percentage of CEOs serving as board chairs decreased from 75% to 57%, while independent directors increased from 79% to 84%. The absence of employees and CEOs from boards is also notable, with 36% of S&P 1500 companies having no staff directors other than the CEO in 1998, rising to 70% in 2011.

Empirical studies have examined the real-world characteristics of board members. External directors influence various board duties, including CEO tenure and defence against takeovers. Coles et al. (2008) argued that the ability and willingness of board members to exercise control functions depend on the board's independence and size. Core et al. (2021) noted that recent financial crises and corporate failures have raised doubts about the effectiveness of boards in protecting shareholder assets and stakeholder interests. Statistics underscore the importance of board composition and management structure for financial health.

Kim et al. (2013) asserted that board effectiveness in maximising shareholder wealth depends on the institutional environment. Dalton and Dalton (2011) highlighted the role of corporate and country-level regulatory frameworks in improving boards' supervisory capacity. This research examines three critical governance variables related to the Board of Directors: size, independence, and diversity, as highlighted in international corporate governance literature and applied to banks in Bangladesh.

2.2.1.1 Board size

Board size is a widely studied corporate governance mechanism in the empirical literature on corporate finance, with varying results based on different demographic areas. For example, Jensen (1993) found that larger boards make it easier for the CEO to exert control, as individual directors have less incentive to seek out and analyse information from auditing managers. Mak and Li (2001) added that board meetings have time limitations, making it more challenging to manage directors' expression of opinions and viewpoints as boards grow larger. Adams (2012) argued that decision-making costs are lower with smaller boards due to fewer people being involved. Boone et al. (2007) supported smaller board sizes, highlighting the increased difficulty of decision-making as board sizes grow, and the free-rider problem, which makes monitoring harder.

In contrast, Lipton and Lorsch (1992) stated that larger boards benefit companies that are complex, highly diversified, enormous, and heavily leveraged. The appropriate board size is determined by the directors and the organisation's characteristics; thus, larger boards may be optimal in some cases. Dalton et al. (1999) found a negative correlation between board size and market value, as measured by Tobin's Q, suggesting that smaller boards perform better. Similarly, several studies (Boone et al., 2007; Core et al. 2021; Eisenberg et al., 1998;

Mak and Li, 2001; O'Connell, 2007) have found a negative correlation between board size and company performance.

Despite extensive research, results remain mixed for the banking sector. Adams and Mehran (2012) found a positive relationship between board size and performance, while Pathan and Faff (2013), Staikouras et al. (2007), and Wang et al. (2015) found a negative relationship. Furthermore, Coleman and Biekpe (2006) and Romano and Guerrini (2014) identified a non-linear inverse relationship, while Kaplan and Minton (2004) discovered no association.

Pathan and Faff (2013) argued that excessively large boards hinder performance due to inefficiency and rising agency conflicts. However, large boards offer advantages, such as increasing the pool of experts and resources, which is crucial in the heavily regulated and complex banking sector. Large boards facilitate manager oversight, regulatory compliance, advisory support, and connections with multiple customers and depositors. Nonetheless, excessive members can cause coordination, control, flexibility, and decision-making difficulties.

This suggests that as a bank's performance improves and the supervisory board size increases, the relationship reaches a point of diminishing returns, where performance benefits decrease with further growth in the board size.

2.2.1.2 Independent Directors

According to Luan and Tang (2007), independent directors serve on the board of directors without other ties to the company. In contrast, non-independent directors, also known as "grey" directors, have existing relationships with the business, such as previous executive roles, family connections to executives, or other business affiliations like

consultants or attorneys. Al-Hawary (2011) examined the impact of non-executive directors on bank performance using Tobin's Q metric and found that banks with independent directors had higher returns on equity. Similarly, Brown and Lee (2019) observed that while leverage detracts from performance, a higher proportion of non-executive directors positively impacts it. Fernandes (2008) argued that external directors theoretically reduce the agency problem between shareholders and management, linking board composition to performance. Adams and Ferreira (2009) claimed that more external directors correlate with better performance, suggesting that they improve the quality and value of information presented to the board.

However, the presence of independent directors on the board has two opposing effects. First, non-executive directors can positively impact performance by providing more accurate information and a deeper understanding of the business, thereby enhancing the standard of information available to the board. Second, an increased number of executives may constrain the board's ability to monitor and discipline top management effectively. Krivogorsky (2006) found a positive and significant association between bank performance and non-executive directors in Continental Europe (Germany, France, Spain, Italy) but a negative correlation in the United Kingdom.

Conversely, Coleman and Biekpe (2006) investigated corporate governance factors in 47 traditional businesses in Nairobi and discovered that larger boards correlated with higher debt levels, with short-term debt positively associated with board independence. Adams (2012) examined data from financial and non-financial firms between 1996 and 2007, finding that banks with independent directors underperformed financially during the financial crisis. This conclusion aligns with Beltratti and Stulz's (2012) analysis of banking behaviour in Mauritius.

Bhagat and Bolton (2008) found no statistically significant relationship between the proportion of external directors and business performance in non-financial firms. Mollah and Zaman (2015) observed that Islamic banks' performance, regardless of board structure or independence, trended negatively due to Shariah law implications. This result is consistent with Hoque and Muradoglu (2013), who found that ROA and stock market returns had significantly negative correlations with the percentage of independent directors on a bank's board. They also highlighted the beneficial role of Shariah supervisory bodies, emphasising the need for stricter enforcement and regulatory measures.

Beltratti and Stulz (2012) found that performance sensitivity during crises was associated with more independent boards and significant insider ownership concentration, positively correlating with banks' crisis-related performance. Chen (2014) noted that insider directors typically possess more expertise than outside directors, yet outside directors contribute to more effective control and improved bank performance due to their different qualifications and experiences. Erkens et al. (2012) used a global sample of 296 financial enterprises from 30 countries to investigate the connection between corporate governance and bank performance during the 2007-2008 recession. They concluded that independent boards and higher institutional ownership negatively impacted stock returns during the crisis, as independent boards issued extra equity, transferring assets from current owners to debtholders.

2.2.1.3 Gender Diversity

Board diversity and shareholder value have been closely linked for some time. Cox et al. (2004) argued that since the 1990s, companies have expected better performance and value creation when implementing diversity initiatives, promoting diversity management, and hiring people from varied backgrounds. For instance, promoting diversity can enhance

corporate performance dimensions such as cost efficiency, human resources, marketing, decision-making, and monitoring, thereby improving overall performance. However, Ibrahim and Angelidis (1994) and Rekker et al. (2014) noted that traditional studies of board characteristics explaining corporate success have limitations, prompting scholars to explore how additional board features, like diversity, can enhance effectiveness.

Farrell and Hersch (2005) advocated that greater diversity among board members improves organisational performance by providing new insights and perspectives. Huang and Kisgen (2019) emphasised that the beneficial impact of diversity on performance and value stems from the heterogeneity of experiences, ideas, and innovations that diverse individuals bring. This study focuses on the diversity of the board of directors rather than general workplace diversity.

According to Carter et al. (2016), diversity on a board of directors can include nationality, ethnicity, gender, and other demographic characteristics. Many researchers (Lee and James, 2007; Owen and Temesvary, 2018; Pathan and Faff, 2013; Singh et al., 2006; Terjesen et al., 2016) have used gender diversity as the most common form. Kim et al. (2013) used political ideology, while others (Huang and Kisgen, 2019; Ibrahim and Angelidis, 1994; Joecks et al., 2013; Rekker et al., 2014) examined the board's ethnicity. Kim et al. (2013) suggested that diversity is beneficial when diverse opinions on the board prevent the CEO and allies from controlling the agenda, thus strengthening oversight. Farrell and Hersch (2005) argued that executives from diverse backgrounds can broaden a company's strategic vision by working together.

The growing emphasis on gender diversity has increased the pressure to select female directors globally. Wachudi and Mboya (2012) highlighted Norway's requirement for publicly traded companies to have a minimum of 40% female directors since January 2008,

or face dissolution. Owen and Temesvary (2018) stated that most proposed legislative changes are based on the idea that more women on boards improve value. Dalton et al. (1999) argued that female board members bring unique perspectives and experiences, particularly in understanding female market segmentation, which can significantly enhance board deliberations.

Singh et al. (2006) claimed that female directors with MBA degrees bring a global perspective to the board. Julizaerma and Sori (2012) added that combining these qualities with communication and listening skills can boost performance. Adams and Ferreira (2009) believed that female directors excel at solving group problems and making decisions. Bart and McQueen (2013) stated that female directors' higher-quality decision-making significantly impacts the board, leading to higher returns, better risk management, and lower bankruptcy rates.

Gruszczy and Marek (2020) claimed that female directors have higher attendance rates and are more prepared for board meetings than their male counterparts. Huang and Kisgen (2019) found that stock price information value rises with female directors on the board. However, Farrell and Hersch (2005) discovered a weak but insignificant link between female directors and several accounting performance measures like ROE and ROA in major US corporations. This finding was supported by Rose and Shepard (1994) and Joecks et al. (2013), who noted that despite evidence supporting female directorships, many studies could not establish a connection between female directorships and firm performance.

Farrell and Hersch (2005) suggested that women are more likely to be on the boards of high-performing companies, though their appointment brings only an insignificant increase in average returns. Adams and Ferreira (2009) added that while female directors are better at monitoring, gender diversity overall negatively affects firm performance. Similarly, Jiraporn

et al. (2008) found no connection between female board representation and firm performance in Danish companies, as determined by Tobin's Q.

Kang et al. (2007) suggested that these mixed results may be due to various factors, including women's propensity to form alliances with powerful board members and their capacity for leadership roles. Methodological discrepancies, such as measuring gender diversity and business performance or cultural views toward women, could also contribute to the generalization of results across countries.

2.2.1.4 Board and sub-committee activity

In corporate governance, the board and its sub-committees play a crucial role in steering organisational effectiveness and performance, particularly in the banking sector of Bangladesh. The frequency of board meetings, along with the engagement levels of the executive and audit committees, indicates the quality of governance and oversight within these institutions. Regular board meetings ensure continuous strategic direction and decision-making, while executive committee meetings facilitate swift operational responses. With its critical role in overseeing financial integrity, the audit committee relies on an optimal number of members and frequent meetings to effectively monitor and manage financial risks. Understanding these dynamics is essential to evaluating how robust governance frameworks contribute to enhanced bank performance in Bangladesh.

2.2.2 Board meeting frequency

The frequency of board meetings, which can measure board activity, is an excellent indicator of whether board members actively supervise a company's performance within the context of the agency theory. Grove et al. (2011) asserted that an increased frequency of meetings and enhanced supervision by senior management are indicators of an effective monitoring function that reduces agency costs and improves corporate performance. This

perspective maintains that the benefits accrued by shareholders due to board meetings should not be discounted.

However, Jensen (1993) argued that board meetings are often a waste of time due to the limited discussion time and added that they inhibit open communication between directors and management. Vafeas (1999) found that the market places less value on boards that meet more frequently because most sessions run alongside day-to-day activities, making it difficult for external directors to oversee management. This relationship disappears when the previous year's stock performance is considered, indicating that low performance drives increased board involvement rather than the reverse. Vafeas also suggested that the relationship between a company's worth and board meeting frequency is not evident because board meetings incur costs such as director fees, managerial time, and travel expenses.

On the other hand, holding more board meetings each month offers various benefits, including more time for discussion, strategy development, and management oversight. Scholars like Andres and Vallelado (2008), Arouri et al. (2014), and Belkhir (2009) have debated the benefits of increased board meetings for the overall performance of financial and non-financial organisations. These arguments are presented through the concepts of reactive and proactive boards. In reactive governance, frequent meetings may result from the board's response to poor performance. Grove et al. (2011) found modest evidence that the frequency of board meetings positively affects financial performance, with overall performance increasing as board meetings become more frequent.

In a proactive board, meetings allow members to interact face-to-face and share perspectives on overseeing bank executives and the institution's strategic direction. Thus, increased meeting frequency enables the board to have more managerial control and makes the advisory board more proactive. Due to the complexity of the banking industry and the

importance of information, boards of directors need to play a proactive and efficient advisory role.

Moreover, Adams and Mehran (2012) advocated for the importance of board meetings in the banking sector, noting that banks typically have larger boards and more subcommittees than non-banking firms. These subcommittees require frequent meetings to effectively coordinate and align their goals with the bank's strategic objectives. Regular board meetings and the appointment of controlled managers to advisory positions with significant responsibilities enhance the effectiveness of a proactive board.

2.2.2.1 Size and Frequency of Meetings of the Audit Committee

The Audit Committee is a crucial corporate subcommittee responsible for financial oversight and compliance. Its duties include overseeing internal controls and audit functions, supervising external auditor appointments and dismissals, adhering to international accounting standards, and engaging in risk management discussions with management. According to Goh (2009), the Audit Committee is integral in monitoring a company's internal controls and risks. Typically, the Board of Directors appoints audit committee members from various executives engaged in different roles within the bank. Kallamu and Saat (2015) emphasised that the Audit Committee ensures compliance with national and international laws, policies, and procedures. Karamanou and Vafeas (2005) highlighted the importance of the Audit Committee's independence from the board of directors and upper management to ensure reliable financial reporting and boost shareholder confidence.

From the agency theory perspective, Jensen (1993) noted that managers often seek to serve their interests, underscoring audit committees' importance in protecting shareholders' rights. Lee et al. (2004) added that agency theory supports the separation of ownership and control to protect shareholder interests, enhance organisational efficiency, and reduce

financial exposure. This theory advocates for the use of independent outside auditors and large boards under the supervision of external auditing bodies to improve financial performance and risk management. However, audit committee members may sometimes be motivated by personal goals and lucrative CEO compensation packages.

Conversely, stewardship theory prefers internal directors to external ones due to their higher motivation and inherent stewardship. It argues for smaller boards with more internal directors to enhance corporate performance and risk management. Davidson et al. (2005) suggested that managers should be loyal to the firm and contribute to its growth, allowing an internal board to select a small audit committee. In contrast, agency theory recommends using independent external directors with an audit committee to effectively monitor and control the supervisory mechanism. Abbott et al. (2004) asserted that a bank's audit committee is essential for overseeing the financial reporting process, recognizing management risks, accurately informing shareholders, and monitoring internal controls.

Empirical results on the relationship between audit committee meetings and firm performance are mixed. Huson et al. (2001) found a positive correlation between audit committee meetings and firm performance. However, Chen et al. (2015) claimed that neither the presence nor composition of audit committees significantly correlates with financial fraud. Abbott et al. (2004) argued that audit committee meetings reduce the probability of financial fraud, while Agrawal and Chadha (2005) detected fake revenue during fewer audit sessions. Lee et al. (2004) found that companies with audit committees composed entirely of independent directors with minimal finance or accounting experience had poorer investment returns. Goh (2009) discovered that the autonomy of management and the Audit Committee was inversely related to financial performance, suggesting that establishing an audit

committee did not necessarily improve earnings or quality. Instead, such committees benefited companies focusing on substantive work.

Klein (2002) found that companies with audit committees comprising independent directors performed better. However, Goh (2009) asserted that the correlation between the Audit Committee and key performance indicators like Tobin's Q and ROE is not statistically significant. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of a bank can be predicted by the size, frequency, and number of audit committee meetings.

2.2.2.2 Meeting Frequency of Executive Committee

In an ideal scenario, a company's board of directors would engage in strategic planning and make decisions aligned with the company's values and principles. However, it is often impractical for large boards to meet in person to make crucial decisions. Executive committees, composed of high-level executives, are vital subcommittees within organisations that can convene on short notice to address critical issues with significant repercussions, such as emerging crises. According to resource dependency theory, the executive committee acts on the board's behalf, serving as a steering group that sets priorities for the broader board.

Executive committees are permanent groups directing the board's activities, and their members, while high-ranking executives, answer to the board. These committees typically hold meetings more frequently than the board, allowing them to respond rapidly to pressing issues. The frequency of executive committee meetings is flexible, ranging from monthly, bimonthly, quarterly, to as needed. Lipton and Lorsch (1992) suggested that regular meetings provide better opportunities for the board to examine and track management performance.

Empirical studies have shown mixed results regarding the impact of executive committee meetings on firm performance. Hoque and Muradoglu (2013) analysed top corporations from the National Stock Exchange of India and found that executive meetings had a favorable link with firm performance. In contrast, Karmel (1984) found no impact of executive committee meetings on the performance of 1500 US corporations. Similarly, Hendry (2005) discovered no correlation between executive committee meetings and business performance in Tunisia. Iwasaki (2008) also found no correlation between the performance of Russian firms and executive committee meetings.

These mixed results suggest that while the frequency of executive committee meetings can enhance responsiveness and oversight, its impact on firm performance may vary depending on the context and environment in which a company operates.

2.2.3 Financial and remuneration policy

Corporate governance and financial and remuneration policies play pivotal roles in shaping institutions' strategic direction and integrity, particularly how financial and remuneration policies are set in Bangladesh's banking sector, which makes a big difference. This section takes a closer look at audit fees and CEO pay, exploring their roles in the broader framework of corporate governance and their effect on bank performance. This study considers how these financial measures align with regulations and ethical standards, focusing on their contributions to transparency and accountability. This discussion highlights the importance of careful financial management and fair executive compensation in supporting the health and growth of banks in this region.

2.2.3.1 Audit Fees

Understanding audit fees has received considerable attention in the literature. Simunic et al. (2007) created a foundational model for determining audit fees, which numerous authors have since expanded upon with empirical findings. This section reviews relevant contributions to this investigation.

According to Al-Matari et al. (2014), the amount a client company pays in audit fees should, in theory, be proportional to the effort put in by the auditor. This effort, and thus the fees, are determined by the auditor's assessment of the complexity of the process and the desired level of risk. Generally, audit procedures, fees, nature, extent, and timing are crucial in decreasing the risk of an auditor issuing a clean opinion on financial statements that contain significant misstatements.

Choi et al. (2008) found that the likelihood of future losses for the audit firm, such as litigation costs, regulatory sanctions, and reputation damage, influences the auditing effort. Simunic et al. (2007) argued that audit firms adjust their fees when perceiving high liability exposure. Choi et al. (2008) further noted that the legal environment, including the legal systems of various countries where audit firms operate, impacts audit fees. Alzeban (2015) added that audit firms price their risk assessments based on operational complexity and the level of work involved, often charging a premium if the workload increases. Deegan (2002) noted that large, reputable audit firms typically avoid engagements with risky clients if they anticipate high litigation costs.

Client characteristics significantly influence audit fees. Kallamu and Saat (2015) conducted a meta-analysis on auditing costs, identifying factors such as size (using total assets or sales), complexity (using the number of national and foreign subsidiaries), risk (measured by stock or receivables), profitability (return on investment or loss), liquidity,

leverage, and internal control (using proxies like external directors and audit committees) as having significant links to audit fees.

Mohd et al. (2009) observed that audit fees reflect the client's future performance because auditors access forward-looking data such as obsolete inventory, uncollectible receivables, warranty costs, and pension expenditures. This evidence suggests that the client's financial health is a crucial factor in determining audit fees. Additionally, the disclosed audit fee is linked to errors in financial analysts' earnings forecasts, indicating that auditors' predictions are more precise than those of financial analysts. Klein (2002) suggested that other market participants may pay attention to the disclosed audit fee since it can predict the firm's future economic condition.

These findings imply that client financial situations significantly influence audit fee determination. This evidence supports the argument for disclosing audit costs and incorporating them into assessments of a company's future financial health, monitored by other market participants.

2.2.3.2 CEO Remuneration

According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), executive remuneration contracts should be viewed in the context of the principal-agent relationship, where managers (agents) pursue incentives beyond shareholder returns (principals). The principal-agent model suggests that managers must align their goals with the company's objectives, linking their compensation to the company's performance. By establishing remuneration agreements, shareholders encourage managers to uphold their interests. Agency theory mandates that compensation packages be prepared and agreed upon in advance to balance the interests of shareholders and managers, thereby resolving agency issues.

Holmstrom (1979) argued that when a manager's actions are hidden from the owner, it creates a moral hazard, affecting business operations and various stakeholders. Fama and Jensen (1983) highlighted that employment contracts are crucial for business owners to influence managers' behaviour. Jensen and Murphy (1990) pointed out that remuneration contracts can address existing issues by aligning managers' incentives with shareholder interests. These contracts often include incentives such as shareholding, stock options, performance-related compensation, LTIP, and bonuses.

Bertrand and Mullainathan (2001) noted that executives might avoid activities that distort the pay-setting process by devising a compensation system unrelated to performance. Therefore, compensation contracts must align managers' preferences with the firm's objectives. Coleman and Biekpe (2006) claimed that under agency theory, the agent is risk-averse and effort-averse, whereas the principal is neutral or risk-averse. Thus, CEO compensation agreements should offer genuine insurance incentives. Core et al. (2021) found a possible link between owner-oriented performance and executive compensation, suggesting that the owner may influence the agent through monitoring.

Researchers have explored the connection between executive compensation and performance, often using agency theory or managerialism as their primary framework. For instance, Henssen et al. (2014) supported that executive compensation is linked to company performance, as managerial decisions directly impact financial rewards. Similarly, Jensen and Murphy (1990) and Orelund (2007) found a positive correlation between firm performance and compensation policies. Reddy et al. (2015) discovered a statistically favourable association between higher CEO compensation and better firm results when using annual stock return as a performance measure. Carty and Weiss (2012) showed a strong correlation between CEO compensation and firm performance in the US. Brick et al. (2006) found a link

between the controlling CEO's firm performance, excess compensation for directors, and governance traits.

However, the impact of firm size on compensation policies is mixed. John and Qian (2003) found that dividend payouts, investment opportunities, financing options, and compensation policies positively correlate with cash compensation size in the US banking sector. Jensen and Murphy (1990) discovered that CEOs at smaller enterprises are more likely to have compensation-based incentives, while larger firms have more diversified ownership and management supervision. Carty and Weiss (2012) found a statistically significant positive correlation between business size and contingent compensation. Core et al. (2021) argued that measuring CEO compensation and firm size is challenging due to unobservable factors like intangible assets, market power, and managerial monitoring mechanisms. Garen (1994) found that as firms grow, their pay performance improves, but sensitivity to standard deviation decreases.

In conclusion, according to agency theory, predetermined compensation plans are essential for balancing the needs of shareholders and managers. Total compensation includes base salary, bonuses, restricted stock value, retirement plans, and other benefits offered by the business.

2.2.4 Ownership structure

Good corporate governance depends on the ownership structure, which reveals whether internal or external shareholders own most of the business. Variations in cash flow rights may result in wealth expropriation by dominant shareholders seeking personal benefits at the expense of smaller shareholders. Shleifer and Vishny (1997) pointed out that controlling owners incur agency costs due to disagreements with outside investors. Chen

(2014) asserted that insider ownership and low levels of external stockholders and foreign ownership could benefit family members within family businesses.

Many authors, including Adams and Ferreira (2009), Arouri et al. (2014), Babatunde and Olaniran (2009), Belkhir (2009), La Porta et al. (2002), Lemmon and Lins (2003), and Shleifer and Vishny (1997), have explored the correlation between ownership and a company's worth. However, empirical evidence on the relationship between business performance and firm ownership concentration is conflicting. In Bangladesh's banking industry, ownership types include sponsor/director, institutional, government, foreign, and public ownership. This study focuses on the impact of governance systems on bank performance, excluding foreign ownership, as their presence in the Bangladeshi banking sector is not prominent.

2.2.4.1 Sponsors or Director's Ownership

The board's participation in governance is essential as they have a fiduciary duty to shareholders and are responsible for providing oversight and strategic direction (Mak and Li, 2001). According to Mahmud (2013), 80% of a company's executive and non-executive directors own significant shares in their organisations. Ahmed (2010) noted that most CEOs in Bangladesh's banking industry do not own shares in their organisations and only receive cash compensation in the form of salaries and bonuses. Conversely, the majority of independent directors in this sector are non-executive directors.

Another characteristic of banks in Bangladesh is their high average debt-to-equity ratio, which is fifteen times higher than the equity in a company. This high leverage often leads to agency problems when trying to balance the interests of managers and directors, directors and outside shareholders, directors and creditors, or depositors. An increase in anticipated agency costs is expected to address these issues. Jensen and Meckling (1976)

identified a connection between board members' shareholdings and company performance, following the "convergence-to-interest" paradigm. As directors own more shares, their financial stakes increase, aligning their interests with shareholder value maximization. However, this can also lead to directors prioritizing their wealth over creditors' and depositors' interests by expropriating the return on total assets.

The relationship between board shares and performance, particularly involving independent non-executive directors, is complex and sometimes uncertain. Chen (2014) found a monotonic association between Tobin's Q and managerial ownership using data from 123 Japanese enterprises between 1987 and 1995. The study showed that Q rises linearly with managerial ownership, implying that managers' and investors' interests align better at higher ownership levels. Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) also supported the importance of insider ownership, suggesting it can have either a positive or negative impact on performance. Himmelberg et al. (1999) argued that high levels of managerial ownership might lead to entrenchment, where managers engage in activities that do not maximize shareholder value without being held accountable. Conversely, low levels of managerial ownership suggest that incentives are better aligned.

In conclusion, the board's shareholding in a company significantly impacts its governance and performance. While higher managerial ownership can align interests with shareholders, it can also lead to potential entrenchment issues. Balancing these dynamics is crucial for effective governance, particularly in highly leveraged environments like the banking sector in Bangladesh.

2.2.4.2 Institutional Ownership

In Bangladesh's banking industry, institutional ownership accounts for 8% to 9% of overall ownership, but it is growing in significance due to rising share investments and

institutional involvement in corporate governance processes. Institutional investors have characteristics that distinguish them from other shareholders. They typically own shares as part of a portfolio investment strategy, making them legally separate from individual shareholders.

Alfaraih et al. (2012) argued that institutions are legally liable for share ownership in investment businesses, but the shares are economically attributed to the institution's final investors and clients. According to Bhattacharya and Graham (2009), institutions act as financial mediators, not retaining shares for their own benefit since the gains go to their investors and clients. Shleifer and Vishny (1997) claimed that institutional ownership reduces managerial opportunism and minority expropriation, thereby cutting agency costs and boosting firm performance. However, institutional investors, as external stakeholders, are often powerless to influence crucial operational decisions.

Lehmann and Weigand (2000) found that ownership concentration benefits profitability for businesses where financial institutions are the major shareholders, supporting the notion that banks are better controllers of agency costs. Jafarinejad et al. (2015) asserted that large institutional investors' holdings enhance board scrutiny, thereby improving corporate performance. Ruiz-Mallorquí and Santana-Martín (2011) noted that institutional investors positively impact firm performance even without other external owners.

Conversely, Agrawal and Chadha (2005) found no connection between institutional stockholding and performance. Neubaum and Zahra (2006) argued that while institutional ownership is positively correlated with corporate social responsibility (CSR), there is little evidence linking it to financial performance. They claimed that external scrutiny of institutional ownership does not always lead to higher profits or better corporate governance. The results suggest that institutional ownership may not improve operating performance by

interfering with management's actions, as the board of directors already holds that responsibility. However, to attract institutional investors, some firms heavily invest in CSR initiatives.

In conclusion, institutional ownership in Bangladesh's banking industry is becoming increasingly significant. While it has the potential to enhance corporate governance and reduce agency costs, its impact on financial performance is mixed. Some studies suggest that institutional ownership can improve profitability and performance, while others find no significant correlation. Nevertheless, institutional investors often drive companies to adopt better governance practices and invest in CSR, aiming to attract more substantial institutional investment.

2.2.4.3 General Public Ownership

According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), when applying agency theory to contemporary business, conflicts of interest may arise between owners and controllers when ownership and management of enterprises are not perfectly aligned. These conflicts and challenges in negotiating fair contracts and monitoring managers can reduce a company's value. Gugler and Weigand (2003) contended that free-rider problems reduce incentives for direct monitoring in cases of distributed ownership. Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) added that domination by large shareholders could hurt performance due to their exposure to a company's risks.

Berle and Means (1932) argued that shareholders lose power over professional managers when ownership becomes widely distributed, as they cannot supervise management effectively. Consequently, a diffuse ownership structure is often negatively linked to performance. Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggested that increased managerial ownership boosts company performance by aligning management and stockholder interests. In contrast,

Demsetz and Villalonga (2001) highlighted the drawbacks of insider ownership, arguing that no single ownership structure is optimal for all situations if the corporation's asset value is to be maximized. Welch (2003) further argued that a company's ownership structure is an endogenous trait dictated by the organisation's unique qualities.

Several empirical studies have examined the link between high levels of ownership concentration and business success, with inconsistent findings. Körner and Schnabel (2010) discovered a negative association between growth and a high percentage of public ownership in the banking system, a characteristic often found in underdeveloped nations with limited financial development and poor-quality political institutions. Mayer (2000) showed a correlation between the size of an investor's ownership stake and the company's financial performance. Similarly, Andrianova et al. (2008) claimed that public ownership does not negatively impact growth in industrialized nations, emphasising the importance of governance and institutional quality in determining the effects of public ownership on growth.

Research by Faccio and Lasfer (2000) found that foreign shareholdings correlate positively with financial success in the United Kingdom. On the other hand, Demsetz and Villalonga (2001) and Weir et al. (2002) found no evidence of a causal relationship between the type of ownership a company has and its financial success.

In conclusion, the relationship between public ownership and company performance is complex and context-dependent. While diffuse ownership structures can create challenges in monitoring management and aligning interests, the impact on performance varies based on factors such as governance quality, institutional development, and specific industry conditions.

2.3 The Case Study of Bangladesh

This chapter offers an in-depth look at the legal, economic, and regulatory frameworks of Bangladesh that have shaped the development of its corporate governance structures. This study will closely examine the nation's corporate law and governance frameworks. It will provide a detailed exploration of the Bangladeshi economy, its corporate standards and practices, relevant regulatory bodies, and the existing corporate governance code. This segment aims to thoroughly understand these elements to suggest potential improvements and alternative codes that could further enhance corporate governance in Bangladesh.

2.3.1 Introduction of Bangladesh from an Economic Perspective

Bangladesh, located in the northeastern part of South Asia, is bordered by India to the west, north, and northwest, Myanmar to the southeast, and the Bay of Bengal to the south. Bangladesh has undergone significant economic transformation since its independence from East Pakistan in 1971. According to Bagchi (2019), the country's macroeconomic environment has shown remarkable steady progress, with an annual GDP growth of over 6% between 2012 and 2017. This growth signifies substantial development across all economic sectors.

The economic history of Bangladesh reveals a fluctuating GDP growth rate. From 1961 to 2021, the growth rate was particularly volatile in the early 1970s and 1980s. The economy averaged a growth rate of approximately 4.3% between 1976 and 1980, but growth dipped below 4% during 1981-1990. However, since 2000, the economy has seen a steady rise, with an average growth rate of 5% in the 1990s, nearly 6% between 2001 and 2011, and an impressive 7% from 2011 to 2018. The highest recorded growth was 8.2% in 2019. The COVID-19 pandemic caused a significant dip in 2020, bringing growth down to 3.45%, the

lowest since 1995. However, a robust recovery in 2021 saw GDP growth almost double to 6.94%.

Figure 2: Incremental Contribution of GDP Growth in Bangladesh. Source: Compiled by Author, sourced from BBS (2019)

The contributions of various economic sectors to GDP have shifted over time. The agricultural sector, once dominant, has seen a relative decline. Despite being an agrarian economy, agriculture’s contribution to GDP has decreased, with growth rates of 2.54% in the 1980s, 3.22% in the 1990s, and 3.53% in the 2000s, peaking at 5.24% in 2010 before stabilizing at 3.56% from 2011 to 2016.

Conversely, the service sector has grown substantially, becoming a significant GDP contributor. The average growth rate in services was 4.48% in the 1990s, 7.10% in the 2000s, and 6.23% in 2010. By 2015-2016, the services sector contributed 53.58% to Bangladesh’s total GDP, reflecting its less capital-intensive nature and significant role in the economy.

The industrial sector has also seen modest improvements, with a notable rise in the ready-made garments (RMG) industry since the mid-1980s. The industrial sector’s average growth rate increased from 6.96% in the 1990s to 9.08% in the 2000s. The manufacturing growth performance was 22.71% better in 2017-2018 compared to 21.01% in 2015-2016.

Figure 3: Sectoral Contributions to GDP in Bangladesh. Source: Compiled by Author, sourced from BBS (2019).

Despite global economic recessions in recent decades, Bangladesh has continued its economic advancement. Bangladesh’s economic development has been impressive compared to other least developed and developing countries, becoming one of the world’s fastest-growing economies. Factors contributing to this growth include a demographic dividend, strong RMG exports, and accumulation of land, labour, capital, and entrepreneurial activity. Additionally, macroeconomic fundamentals such as low inflation, a balanced budget, and a strong reserve currency have supported this progress.

Bangladesh has also made significant strides in poverty reduction, supported by sustainable economic growth and stable macroeconomic conditions. Since attaining lower-middle-income status in 2015, Bangladesh is on track to graduate from the U.N.'s list of least developed countries by 2026. Poverty, measured by a global threshold of \$1.90 per day, decreased to 15% in 2016 from 44% in 1991. The country's GDP reached \$329.12 billion in 2020 and is projected to continue growing, adding roughly \$160 billion since 2014.

Despite these achievements, Bangladesh's economy faces several threats, including declining private sector investment, reduced agricultural growth, an increased real currency rate, poor bank performance, and inefficiencies in development funds, which could hinder economic growth and future prospects. The COVID-19 pandemic severely impacted GDP growth and increased poverty and health vulnerabilities. Lessons from the pandemic highlighted the need to address issues such as women's workforce participation and financial sector resilience to ensure sustainable economic development.

2.3.2 The Corporate Sector of Bangladesh

In response to the practical needs of the country and global economic shifts, Bangladesh has undergone significant adjustments in its corporate sector. According to Ahmed (1976), the government nationalized almost all industries immediately after independence, totalling more than BDT 2.5 million, as part of its "socialist" economic policies. Studies by Rahim (1978), Khan and Jain (2018), Mir and Rahaman (2005), and Chowdhury (2015) confirmed that this led to the suspension of the Dhaka Stock Exchange's (DSE) operations and a reduction in the private sector's economic contribution. However, Ghafur (1976) and Ahmad (1976) pointed out that the plan quickly failed due to the excessive politicization and corruption within state-owned companies (SOEs). Chowdhury (2015) added that government bureaucrats with little or no prior business experience were assigned

to run SOEs, resulting in decreased business efficiency and operational losses amounting to approximately 30% of total annual government projects.

The government abandoned its "socialist" economic policy in 1976 after recognizing the dire situation of the SOEs (Ahmed, 1978; Rahim, 1978). According to Chowdhury (2015), the nation transitioned to a market-based economy by enacting a privatisation programme to strengthen the private sector's economic involvement. Islam (1986) noted that approximately 400 nationalised businesses were made available for purchase by private investors to improve the economy. Multinational corporations (MNCs) like British American Tobacco and SmithKline were also allowed to operate in Bangladesh. Sobhan (2014) added that the Privatisation movement continued and even intensified in certain areas, with state-held banks denationalised in 1982 and new private banks established, leading to a thriving private banking sector.

	Sector Classification	DSE		CSE	
		No. of listed Cos.	%	No. of listed Cos.	%
Financial Companies (FCs)	Banking Cos.	30	5.30	29	9.48
	Non-banking Cos.:				
	(i) Insurance Cos.	47		42	
	(ii) Leasing & Investment Cos.	23	12.37	22	20.92
	Total Financial Companies (FCs)	100	17.67	93	30.40
Non-Financial Companies (NFCs)	Engineering	34		28	
	Food and Allied	18		12	
	Fuel and Power/Energy	18		16	
	Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals	28		23	
	Textile	48		43	
	IT and Telecommunication	10		10	
	Cement, Ceramic, Jute and Paper & Printing	17		16	
	Tannery & Leather	6		6	
	Services & Real Estate, Travel & Leisure	8		7	
	Miscellaneous	12		14	
	Total Non-Financial Companies (NFCs)	199	35.16	175	57.20
Total FCs and NFCs		299	52.83	268	87.58
Bonds, Debentures and Mutual Funds		267	47.17	38	12.40
Total Listed Companies		566	100	306	100

Table 1: Listed Companies on the DSE and CSE. Source: BBS (2019)

According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS, 2019), subsequent administrations have enabled many financial and non-financial institutions to operate in the private sector, some fully privatised and others in partnership with the government. Mir and Rahaman (2005) noted that certain sectors, such as arms and ammunition, military facilities and equipment, security printing, and mining, remain wholly state-owned. Bangladesh's structural arrangements show that most small- and medium-sized sectors are in several large industries, including ready-made garments, paper and newsprint, textiles, tea processing, chemical fertilizers, cement, pharmaceutical products, leather goods, light technology, and sugar. Privatisation and economic reforms have strengthened the capital market. The capital market grew from BDT 11.485 billion in 1991 to BDT 31,597.58 billion in 2016. Market capitalization as a proportion of GDP rose from 1.4% in 1991 to 10.2% in 2006, with a surge to 37.08% in 2011, though it has since decreased to 19.73% in 2016.

Figure 4: Total financial companies Categorised by Sector on the DSE and CSE. Source: Compiled by Author, sourced from DSE (2016)

The Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) and the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) are the two stock exchanges in Bangladesh's capital market. As of 19th September 2022, there were 566 businesses listed on the DSE and 306 companies on the CSE. Though many businesses

are dual-listed, Chowdhury (2013) noted that only 10% of Bangladesh's public limited companies are listed on the stock exchange. The corporate sector is divided into financial companies (F.C.s) and non-financial companies (N.F.C.s). Among the categorized businesses on the DSE, 17.67% are F.C.s, with banking businesses representing 5.30% and non-banking financial businesses representing 12.37%. N.F.C.s represent 35.16%, while the remaining 47.17% includes debentures, mutual funds, and bonds.

Similarly, on the CSE, 30.40% of businesses are F.C.s, with banking businesses representing 9.48% and non-banking financial businesses representing 20.92%. N.F.C.s represent 52.20%, and debentures, mutual funds, and bonds represent 12.42%.

In summary, the corporate sector of Bangladesh has undergone significant changes since independence, transitioning from a socialist economic model to a market-based economy. The privatisation programme and economic reforms have played a crucial role in this transformation, leading to the growth of the capital market and the establishment of a robust private sector. Despite these advancements, certain sectors remain under state control, reflecting the ongoing evolution of the corporate landscape in Bangladesh.

2.3.3 Bangladesh's Banking Industry

According to Hossain (2014), the history of Bangladesh's banking industry is closely tied to the country's independence, comprising banks that operated in East Pakistan before 1971. After independence, the industry gained legal entity status (Nguyen et al., 2020). The central bank, previously known as the State Bank of Pakistan, was renamed Bangladesh Bank (BB). As of 2016, out of 63 banks in the industry, 57 are scheduled banks, and six are non-scheduled banks (Bangladesh Bank, 2019). Most scheduled banks are commercial and privately held, with only six state-owned banks. Notably, only 30 banks have public share listings on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) and the Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE). The

six non-scheduled banks, including Jubilee Bank and Grameen Bank, primarily provide micro-finances and entrepreneur loans to foster financial independence.

Khatun (2018) claims that Bangladesh's banking sector is the most robust financial institution in the country, significantly contributing to annual GDP growth. In the 2015-2016 fiscal year, the banking industry generated over 8% of the nation's GDP, increasing to 9.6% in 2017-2018 (BBS, 2019). A healthy macroeconomic climate, reflected in a compound annual GDP growth rate of 6% over the past decade, has been crucial to this development. Since financial liberalization began in 1975, the banking system has progressed tremendously, aiding the country's economic growth. Key indicators of this development include private sector bank borrowing to GDP, private sector bank assets to GDP, private sector broad money (M2) to GDP, and private sector domestic credit which are presented in the table below. Between 2011 and 2016, bank loans for new investments and purchasing houses, cars, and other household items averaged 43.23% of GDP, with lending to the private sector ranging from 41.58% to 45.09% of GDP in 2016. The average bank loan to the private sector as a percentage of GDP was 43.45%, while private sector bank assets averaged 53.44% of GDP, peaking at 55.87% in 2015. Broad money (M2) represented an average of 62.61% of GDP during this period.

The World Bank (2022) asserts that from 1975 to 2016, bank finances to the private sector as shares of GDP ranged from 1.92% to 45.09%, with an average of 21.46%. Bank assets as a proportion of GDP ranged from 8% to a high of 55.87%, averaging 23.39% over the same period. Private sector domestic loans ranged from 1.92% to 45.28%, averaging 21% in 2016. Broad money (M2) had an average value of 32.88% of GDP, peaking at 65.85% in 2016.

Financial Years									
Areas of contribution/indicators	Countries	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Average	Rank
Bank credit to private sectors, percentage of GDP	Bangladesh	42.26	42.76	41.58	43.51	44.2	45.09	43.23	3
	India	51.29	51.89	52.39	51.88	51.87	49.19	51.42	2
	Pakistan	18.03	16.84	16.02	15.49	15.31	16.41	16.35	5
	Sri Lanka	34.91	34.92	34.64	35.75	41.48	45.22	37.82	4
	Vietnam	101.8	94.83	96.08	100.3	111.93	123.81	104.79	1
Bank assets, percentage of GDP	Bangladesh	50.75	51.29	52.38	54.65	55.71	55.87	53.44	3
	India	66.04	67.34	68.35	68.68	68.76	69.67	68.14	2
	Pakistan	33.7	36.63	36.88	37.04	39.9	43.14	37.88	5
	Sri Lanka	33.97	36.36	39.62	39.72	43.63	56.39	41.62	4
	Vietnam	106.88	100.65	103.56	108.74	118.06	130.45	111.39	1
Broad money (M2), percentage of GDP	Bangladesh	59.81	60.74	61.4	63.34	64.51	65.85	62.61	3
	India	78.84	76.91	78.18	77.9	78.01	74.69	77.42	2
	Pakistan	48.1	51.48	52.24	51.82	53.32	57.81	52.46	4
	Sri Lanka	43.45	42.25	44.71	47.39	52.48	55.66	47.66	5
	Vietnam	99.8	106.46	117.02	127.55	137.65	151.09	123.26	1
Domestic credit to the private sector, the percentage of GDP	Bangladesh	42.47	43	41.79	43.74	44.41	45.28	43.45	3
	India	51.29	51.89	52.39	51.88	51.9	49.55	51.48	2
	Pakistan	18.13	16.94	16.12	15.59	15.39	16.53	16.45	5
	Sri Lanka	35.01	35.02	34.75	35.87	41.6	45.71	37.99	4
	Vietnam	101.8	94.83	96.8	100.3	11.93	123.82	88.25	1

Table 2: Depth of the Banking System. Source: World Bank (2019)

Despite moderate growth in the banking sector between 2011 and 2016, data on bank credit to the private sector and bank assets as a percentage of GDP indicate slow growth in credit to both the private and public sectors. According to World Bank (2019) standards, a well-developed financial system is defined when private sector banking credit accounts for more than 70% of GDP. In Bangladesh, this ratio remains below this benchmark.

The moderate level of broad money (M2) in the financial market has contributed to the country's modest economic progress. When compared to neighboring countries in Asia, Bangladesh's banking industry contributes less to the economy than Vietnam and India but more than Sri Lanka and Pakistan.

Several financial scandals and irregularities have hampered Bangladesh's banking system performance in recent years. Despite numerous central bank programmes since 2010,

Mahmud (2013) found insufficient growth in key measures such as return on equity, return on capital, the debt ratio, non-performing loans, excess liquidity, and liquid assets. Khatun (2017) added that all private commercial banks, state-owned banks, and two specialized banks faced severe issues related to high volumes of non-performing loans (NPLs), low profitability, large fiscal deficits, and weak balance sheet positions during this time.

The Bangladesh Bank (2020) reported that state-owned commercial banks (SCBs) had a 28.2% share of non-performing loans in the 2017-2018 fiscal year, the highest in the recent decade. Five specific banks held 47% of these non-performing loans. Between 2016 and 2018, nine banks had classified loans accounting for more than 10% of their total loans, while the average cost-to-income ratios over the past ten years were around 0.5, with fluctuations in the Advance Deposit Ratio (ADR). A liquidity crisis affected three fourth-generation banks (NRB Global Bank, NRB Commercial, and Farmers Bank) during the 2016-2017 fiscal year, causing customers to lose trust due to delays in accessing their funds. Haque et al. (2007) argued that these issues highlight the ineffectiveness of bank management, particularly in assessing liquidity and risk management, risk analysis, credit ratings, and political influences. These problems indicate a lack of good corporate governance to protect depositors' rights.

Sobhan (2014) noted that Bangladesh Bank has introduced prudential regulations multiple times as part of its reform efforts. Significant regulations include banning loans to companies with directors who have defaulted on loans, prohibiting lending to bank directors and their relatives, and implementing a credit risk grading (CRG) manual. However, Reaz and Arun (2006) claimed that these reforms have not ensured accountability in credit management or reduced political influences on lending decisions. Consequently, Bangladesh's credit management system has seen little improvement.

The issues highlighted above underscore the need for a more effective regulatory framework to update the banking industry's governance system. Strengthening financial regulation, monitoring, and compliance through independent bodies is essential to establish efficient and effective corporate governance structures.

2.3.4 Key Features of Bangladesh's Corporate Sector

The Bangladeshi corporate sector has several distinguishing characteristics that set it apart from developed, emerging, and least developing countries. These critical features highlight the importance of efficient corporate governance.

2.3.4.1 Ownership and Control

Good corporate governance is fundamentally influenced by the ownership structure, which helps mitigate agent-principal conflicts. Hoque et al. (2013) note that most top shareholders in Bangladesh are either sponsored directors or family members, resulting in highly concentrated ownership patterns. Ahmed (2010) adds that earlier studies (Farooque et al., 2007; Imam and Malik, 2007) documented that sponsoring members exercise robust control over the board in most companies. In Bangladesh, 39.80% of shares in both financial and non-financial companies are owned by sponsors or family members. Furthermore, 61.70% of board members in non-financial companies and 40.19% in financial institutions are sponsored or family members.

2.3.4.2 Institutional Ownership

Institutional investors in Bangladesh's corporate sector do not actively participate in company management due to a lack of a well-developed institutional investment portfolio (Farooque et al., 2007). Ahmed (2010) earlier showed that this group of investors owns only 10-15% of companies, implying minimal influence on corporate governance.

2.3.4.3 Rights of Shareholders

The Companies Act of 1994 safeguards shareholders' rights, particularly those of minority shareholders (BEI, 2004). However, these protections are often not respected in practice. Khatun (2018) claims that most Bangladeshi shareholders are unaware of their legal protections and responsibilities, focusing instead on ancillary benefits of equity ownership, such as Annual General Meeting (AGM) perks. Farooque et al. (2007) noted that minority shareholders attend AGMs primarily for appearances and benefits, rather than for substantive discussion.

2.3.4.4 Weak Capital Market

Bangladesh's two leading stock exchanges, the Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) and the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE), are among the smallest and weakest in South Asia, with insufficient legal action and poor market controls to protect shareholders (Sobhan, 2014). Only 12% of publicly traded companies are listed on the stock market, with 324 companies on the CSE and 608 on the DSE (BSEC, 2019). The market's vulnerability was highlighted by two significant crashes between 2008 and 2011 (Chowdhury, 2013).

2.3.4.5 Financial Reporting and Auditing Environment

Every legal business in Bangladesh must compile financial statements per Bangladesh Accounting Standards (BAS) and Bangladesh Financial Reporting Standards (BFRS). Section 181 of the Companies Act 1994 requires an independent auditing firm to review the annual report and related financial statements (Sobhan, 2014). However, Khatun (2018) found that many companies do not adequately adhere to these standards, and auditors often do not verify all financial disclosures thoroughly. Ferdous (2012) attributes this to inadequate oversight, unfair competition among auditors, and a weak regulatory framework, leading to collusion between auditors and management.

2.3.4.6 High Levels of Political Polarisation and Incompetence

In Bangladeshi patrimonial society, success often depends on loyalty to higher authorities rather than competence. As a result, politically connected individuals often hold key positions in business and government, regardless of their qualifications (Franda, 1982; Farooque et al., 2007; Imam and Malik, 2007). This issue is particularly prevalent in state-owned firms, where appointments are made based on political affiliation.

2.3.4.7 Widespread Corruption:

Bangladesh is one of the most corrupt nations in the world (Transparency International, 2021). Corruption permeates all levels of society, from households to institutions. Hoque et al. (2013) claim that corruption has infiltrated every sphere of life, contributing to poor accountability and governance in the business sector (Mir & Rahman, 2005). Ferdous (2012) highlights that corruption undermines the integrity of accounting and auditing activities, posing a threat to the growth of the corporate sector and the overall economy.

In summary, the Bangladeshi corporate sector is characterized by concentrated ownership, limited institutional participation, weak shareholder rights, an underdeveloped capital market, compromised financial reporting, political interference, and pervasive corruption. These factors collectively underscore the need for robust corporate governance reforms to foster a more transparent, accountable, and efficient corporate environment.

2.3.5 The Development of Corporate Governance in Bangladesh

Since the mid-1990s, corporate governance has drawn significant attention from regulatory bodies, practitioners, academics, investors, and international development partners in Bangladesh. This focus intensified following the 1996 stock market crash, which exposed the market's extreme weaknesses and eroded investor confidence. In 1997, the Asian

Development Bank (ADB), one of Bangladesh's International Development Partners (IDPs), proposed a comprehensive capital market restructuring. According to ADB (2022), the proposal included shifting towards an Anglo-American model by modifying governing laws and regulations, restructuring the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC), and automating stock exchange operations.

Sobhan (2014) noted that the ADB, in collaboration with US experts from Aries Group Ltd., developed a thorough Corporate Governance Manual for publicly traded companies and securities issuers, using the OECD's Principles of Corporate Governance as a guide. However, this proposal was not immediately implemented as a corporate governance code. Following the market crash, the Bangladesh Enterprise Institution (BEI) received funds in 2003 from the Commonwealth Secretariat, the Global Corporate Governance Forum (GCGF), and the Department for International Development (DFID) to research and draft corporate governance guidelines for Bangladesh (BEI, 2004).

Sobhan (2014) reported that BEI's evaluation revealed numerous challenges within Bangladesh's business sector, including a lack of competent accounting and auditing professionals, insufficient skills, ineffective government regulators, a weak financial media, and misinformed shareholders. Based on these findings, BEI produced several rules and principles for corporate governance in 2004, modelled after the OECD's Principles of Corporate Governance from 1999. However, these guidelines were not legally required for companies listed on major stock exchanges.

In 2006, the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) adopted the ADB's recommendations (No. SEC/CMRRCD/2006-158/Admin/02-08 dated 20th February 2006) and disseminated them for compliance by listed businesses. Subsequent notices in

2012 and 2018 recommended further changes to improve corporate governance for shareholders' benefit (ICAB, 2018).

Despite these efforts, the corporate sector, particularly the banking sector, showed unsatisfactory compliance with the Corporate Governance Code. Most corporations chose not to follow the BEI-2004 and BSEC-2006 codes until 2012, when compliance became mandatory (BSEC, 2019). However, corporate governance practices in Bangladesh have gradually improved over time. Khan and Jain (2018) reported that 69.7% of publicly traded corporations have implemented corporate governance, and 39.3% have ensured policy conformity with national or international standards.

Many Bangladeshi scholars (Ahmed, 2010; Farooque et al., 2007; Ferdous, 2012; Hoque et al., 2013; Imam and Malik, 2007; Mir and Rahman, 2005; Sobhan, 2014) have identified issues such as a weak regulatory framework, passive capital market, lack of shareholder activism, and ineffective pressure groups as reasons for the country's lack of robust corporate governance. Additionally, Khatun (2018) and Khan et al. (2013) pointed out the prevalence of family members in corporate ownership, inadequate bankruptcy legislation, insufficient compliance with accounting and auditing standards, inconsistencies between the Companies Act, BAS, and BSEC requirements, and failure to disclose related party transactions as significant obstacles to sustainable economic growth.

In conclusion, while Bangladesh has made strides in developing its corporate governance framework, significant challenges remain. Addressing these issues requires continued efforts to strengthen regulatory frameworks, enhance compliance with accounting and auditing standards, promote shareholder activism, and improve the overall business environment. These steps are crucial for fostering sustainable economic growth and ensuring the long-term stability of Bangladesh's corporate sector.

2.3.6 Key Institutional Involvements in Bangladesh's Corporate Governance

Reforms

Ferdous (2012) noted that six primary institutions play crucial roles in establishing and executing corporate governance principles to manage financial and non-financial enterprises in Bangladesh. These institutions are the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC), Bangladesh Bank, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB), Stock Exchanges, The Registrar of Joint Stock Companies and Firms (RJSC), and the Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI). Sobhan (2014) highlighted that the Bangladeshi government (GoB) and its international development partners (IDPs), such as the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), exert direct and indirect influence over these institutions. The influence of the GoB and IDPs on different institutions is depicted in the following figure. The dotted line denotes indirect influence, while the solid arrows denote direct influence in the following figure. Through the Ministry of Finance, the GoB has direct and indirect control over these institutions, whereas IDPs control the institutions through local agents by funding the appropriate organisations and bodies, aiding in developing corporate governance in Bangladesh.

Figure 5: Key Institutional Involvement in Bangladesh's Corporate Governance Reforms. Source: Author

2.3.7 Bangladesh Bank:

Bangladesh Bank, established in 1972 after the country's independence, is the central bank and the highest financial authority in Bangladesh, responsible for monitoring all banks and non-banking financial entities (NBFIs) (BEI, 2004). It oversees the financial sector to ensure that commercial banks adhere to strict guidelines to minimize systemic risk and promote strong ethical and competitive standards. Bangladesh Bank also regulates credit management of commercial banks, prevents money laundering, and monitors the payment system while maintaining the country's reserve fund and printing currency notes (Bangladesh Bank, 2016). It has issued multiple governance guidelines to ensure accountability and

transparency in bank management, including provisions on independent non-executive directors on bank boards, audit committees, and financial statement disclosures.

2.3.7.1 Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC):

The BSEC, a government organisation, regulates the Bangladeshi capital market. Established in 1993, it operates under the Securities and Commission Act of 1993 and is part of Bangladesh's Ministry of Finance. BSEC aims to safeguard the interests of securities investors by formulating and issuing guidelines to ensure market efficiency, fairness, and transparency. It monitors and regulates publicly traded companies, prohibits fraudulent operations, insider trading, and unfair trade practices, and educates investors to make informed investment decisions (BSEC, 2017). However, its efficiency as a regulator has been questioned, particularly following stock market crashes in 1996, 2010, and 2011, which were attributed to weak oversight, inadequate corporate governance, and improper political interference (Khatun, 2018).

2.3.7.2 The Registrar of Joint Stock Companies and Firms (RJSC):

The RJSC, a department within the Ministry of Commerce, is responsible for registering and establishing public and private limited companies under the Companies Act 1994. It specifies the necessary paperwork to start a company and has the authority to inquire about and obtain more information from prospective corporations. However, due to a lack of resources, the RJSC struggles to enforce compliance consistently and identify firms violating accounting and auditing standards (Chowdhury, 2015; BSEC, 2019).

2.3.7.3 Stock Exchanges:

The Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) and the Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) are the two stock exchanges in Bangladesh. They significantly influence corporate governance guidelines and the adherence of listed businesses to these norms. Both exchanges can

formulate laws and guidance under the Securities and Exchange Act 1987 and have the authority to delist companies for non-compliance. The stock exchanges were established as joint-stock companies to administer various laws and regulations (Sobhan, 2012).

2.3.7.4 The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB):

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB), established in 1973 under the Bangladesh Chartered Accountants Order, is the nation's sole body authorised to grant the Associate Chartered Accountant designation. Managed by the Ministry of Commerce, ICAB (2018) develops the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAPs) for Bangladesh, formulating standards known as the Bangladesh Financial Reporting Standards (BFRS) and Bangladesh Accounting Standards (BAS). These are aligned with international standards, excluding IAS 39, IAS 29, and IFRS 9.

As a self-regulatory organisation, ICAB (2018) also promotes corporate governance and provides expertise in accounting, auditing, taxation, and corporate law. Despite its role, the institute has been critiqued for its transparency in financial oversight. In 1999, the World Bank funded ICAB to enhance its standards and align more closely with international practices.

2.3.7.5 Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI):

Established in 2000 with support from international partners, BEI is an impartial, non-profit think tank that conducts research on trade, foreign policy, economic development, corporate governance, sustainable growth, and counterterrorism. BEI made substantial progress in creating the voluntary Corporate Governance Code for Bangladesh-2004, which is more thorough than the corporate governance recommendations of the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BEI, 2004). BEI has set up a Corporate Governance

task force with 35 members from various fields to develop the Code, reflecting their diverse knowledge and expertise.

	Sections of society	No. of members	Percentage
T	Financial Institutions	8	23
	Public, Private and Multinational Companies	7	20
	Stock Exchange and Regulatory Bodies	3	9
	Government Bodies and Ministries	5	14
	Different Professional Bodies	2	6
	Academia	4	11
	Dignitaries	4	11
	Legal Entities	1	3
	Media/Communication	1	3
	Total	35	100

Table 3: Members of Bangladesh’s Task Force on Corporate Governance Source: Extracted from the Taskforce member’s list, BEI (2004, pp. 8-9)

In summary, these institutions play crucial roles in establishing, monitoring, and enforcing corporate governance principles in Bangladesh. Their efforts, along with the influence of the government and international development partners, aim to improve corporate governance standards, although challenges remain in ensuring effective compliance and overcoming political and resource-related obstacles.

2.3.8 Bangladesh’s Banking Regulations

The banking industry in Bangladesh is governed by several legal frameworks, including the Banking Companies Act of 1991 and 2013, the Companies Act of 1994, and regulations set up by the Bangladesh Bank. This section focuses on key legal frameworks to understand the administration of the banking sector, specifically dealing with listed banks.

2.3.8.1 Banking Companies Act 1991 and 2013

The Banking Companies Act of 1991 is a specialized law that governs banking organisations in Bangladesh, establishing a legislative framework for the types, extent, and

methods of banking operations. Bangladesh Bank currently regulates and supervises banks under this act. In 2013, the act was amended to incorporate aspects of the Companies Act, providing a comprehensive regulatory framework for financial provisions.

2.3.8.2 Companies Act 1994

The Companies Act of 1994 governs all banking and non-banking enterprises in Bangladesh. According to Hossain (2014), this act imposes various regulatory restrictions on businesses. Hoque et al. (2013) add that the act covers the appointment and dismissal of directors, powers, duties, compensation of directors and external auditors, and shareholders' rights and interests protection.

2.3.8.3 Regulations Generated by the Bangladesh Bank

The central bank, Bangladesh Bank, has created several rules controlling banking activities for scheduled and unscheduled banks and other non-financial entities. These regulations provide a management framework for money laundering, payment systems, settlements, foreign exchange, core risks, and other operations.

2.3.8.4 Corporate Governance Code Development in Bangladesh

Nations worldwide have developed procedures to prevent future crises in the domestic business sector in response to numerous corporate failures caused by inadequate corporate governance systems. For instance, the US approved the Sarbanes-Oxley Act in 2002, while the UK released the Cadbury Report in 1992, followed by several other reports addressing corporate governance shortcomings (Zattoni and Cuomo, 2008).

Bangladesh has also experienced business scandals leading to the creation of a corporate governance code aimed at improving governance practices. The Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI) (2004) stated that implementing higher corporate governance

standards could provide significant advantages, such as preferential bank loans, lower interest rates, and business support due to lower business risks, thus attracting more equity investors.

Improved corporate governance practices can enhance Bangladesh’s investment climate, opportunities for economic growth, and ensure long-term economic growth. BEI (2004) highlighted that the Corporate Governance Code, developed with input from international authorities, includes principles and guidelines to be adhered to by companies on a "comply or explain" basis. This means businesses must follow the code or explain any areas of non-compliance.

2.3.8.5 Structure of the Corporate Governance Code

The Corporate Governance Code is divided into three sections.

Figure 6: Organisation of the Code of Corporate Governance for Bangladesh. Source: BEI (2004, p. 2)

Section A includes broad guidelines and rules for board concerns, such as independent directors, board size, board qualifications, gender diversity, role duality, and the director’s report. It also provides guidelines on shareholder roles, voting rights, financial reporting, financial disclosures, the formation of internal audit committees, and the appointment of external auditors. **Part B** covers the fundamental checklist for implementing

the Bangladesh Corporate Code, outlining precise advice for preparing the Code (BEI, 2004). Finally, **Part C** includes sectoral provisions and guidelines for financial institutions, state-owned businesses, NGOs, and other entities. This part discusses sectoral issues and directives related to the duties of depositors and customers, credit evaluation, debt recovery, risk management, and asset monitoring.

This chapter has provided an overview of Bangladesh's economy, corporate legal, and governance structures. Despite steady GDP growth and achieving lower-middle-income status in 2015, Bangladesh faces macroeconomic challenges that must be addressed to sustain progress. Since adopting a market-based economy in 1976, the corporate sector, particularly the banking industry, has significantly contributed to economic growth. However, the sector is plagued by corruption, nepotism, politicisation, and government interference, stemming from weak regulatory bodies, inadequate accountability, insufficient legal frameworks, and poor corporate governance.

Based on Anglo-American and OECD principles, the Code of Corporate Governance aims to enhance justice, accountability, and transparency in business management. Despite its comprehensive nature, recent issues in the banking sector suggest the Code has not fully achieved its objectives. Therefore, assessing the effectiveness of these regulations and frameworks is crucial. This study's findings will provide valuable insights for regulatory bodies and bank management, helping to address and rectify existing issues.

2.4 Reviewing the Corporate Governance Code of Bangladesh and the development of hypotheses

This last segment embarks on a critical examination of the Corporate Governance Code of Bangladesh, aiming to articulate and develop hypotheses that assess the relationship between corporate governance practices and bank performance within the region. As financial stability and corporate integrity continue to be pivotal for economic development, the Corporate Governance Code's role in shaping governance frameworks across Bangladeshi banks warrants a thorough analysis. Through a detailed review of the CG Code provisions, this study will identify key governance elements and formulate hypotheses to explore how these components influence the operational efficacy and financial health of banks in Bangladesh. This approach enhances the understanding of corporate governance's impact on financial performance and contributes to the ongoing discourse on regulatory practices in emerging markets.

2.4.1 Board size

Ahmed (2010) states that the board of directors exercises sovereign authority to establish corporate objectives and policies, ultimately serving shareholder interests by managing and overseeing global business activities. The Corporate Governance Code (2018) delineates the board's functions and duties within companies, offering directives for the training and selection of board members in Bangladesh. The Banking Regulation and Policy Department of the Bangladesh Bank (2018) emphasises that members of a bank's board should possess the requisite knowledge and experience to effectively formulate strategies, supervise banking operations, and promote sound governance practices.

The guidelines set by the Corporate Governance Code recommend that the board's composition include diverse professional backgrounds to enrich decision-making. The Bangladesh Bank stipulates a maximum of 10 directors on corporate boards, whereas the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission mandates a board size ranging from 5 to 20 members.

The relationship between board size and organisational performance has yielded mixed research outcomes. For instance, Brown and Lee (2019) found that boards with 6 to 15 members generally achieve better returns and higher net profit margins. Conversely, studies by Eisenberg et al. (1998) and Yermack (1996) observed no significant relationship or a negative impact from larger boards, respectively. Other research, such as that by Coles et al. (2008) and Core et al. (2021), have documented positive and inverse correlations, respectively.

Subsequent studies have continued to explore this complex relationship. Kalsie and Shrivastav (2016) noted a positive correlation in the Indian banking sector, suggesting that larger boards may offer diverse insights that enhance decision-making. On the other hand, Chou et al. (2018) argued that beyond a certain threshold, increased board size can hinder performance due to coordination challenges and delayed decisions. Chen et al. (2015) highlighted variability in optimal board size within Chinese banks, depending on ownership structures and market contexts.

Recent work by Bennedsen et al. (2020) suggests that when accounting for firm-specific factors, the impact of board size on performance becomes negligible, proposing that other governance aspects may be more influential. Similarly, Harris and Raviv (2020) demonstrated that while board size can affect strategic decisions and risk management, its

direct influence on performance is often moderated by factors like board composition and external regulations.

Given this backdrop of diverse and conflicting evidence, it is clear that the relationship between board size and bank performance is intricate and influenced by a myriad of factors. Recognizing that no uniform solution fits all, neither the corporate governance code nor the Bangladesh Bank has set a minimum board size for banks or other financial entities. In light of these varied insights and empirical data, this study puts forward the hypothesis:

H1: Board size is unrelated to the performance of banks in Bangladesh.

This hypothesis investigates the subtle interaction between board size and bank performance within Bangladesh's regulatory and market environment.

2.4.2 Independent Directors in board composition

To ensure that the board is functional and runs smoothly, the BEI (2004) Code suggests that different skills and experiences should be represented on the board. Furthermore, the Corporate Governance Code (2018) recommends that a board should include a broad collection of members, such as outside/independent directors, executive directors, and non-executive directors. According to the Code, at least one-fifth (1/5) of the total number of directors must be independent to be listed on any major stock exchanges. This implies that one in every five directors on a board must be independent. The guidelines specify that independent directors should not have prior relationships with the business, should be free from any criminal charges and convictions, and cannot serve on more than five companies simultaneously.

Al-Hawary (2011) used Tobin's Q metric to analyse the impact of independent directors on bank performance and found that organisations with independent directors have higher returns on equity. Similarly, Bhagat and Bolton (2008) found an inverse relationship between the presence of independent directors and firm size, while Brown and Lee (2019) noted that leverage significantly detracts from performance, whereas the proportion of non-executive and independent directors has a significant positive impact. Fernandes (2008) found a positive relationship between external directors and performance, arguing that they reduce the agency problem between shareholders and management.

More recent studies continue to support the importance of independent directors. For example, Li and Roberts (2018) found that the presence of independent directors positively impacts bank performance by enhancing the board's monitoring effectiveness and reducing agency costs. Masulis et al. (2017) provided evidence that independent directors contribute to better decision-making and improved firm performance in the banking sector. Nguyen et al. (2020) showed that banks with a higher proportion of independent directors have better financial stability and performance metrics.

Additionally, Giroud and Mueller (2020) emphasised the role of independent directors in improving firm governance and performance, highlighting that their presence is particularly beneficial during periods of financial distress. Empirical evidence from these studies suggests that the inclusion of independent directors plays a crucial role in enhancing bank performance.

Considering the emphasis on independent directors in the corporate governance code of Bangladesh and the recent empirical evidence supporting their positive impact on performance, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: A higher number of independent directors on the board can improve bank performance.

2.4.3 Gender Diversity in Board Composition

According to Carter et al. (2016), diversity on a board of directors can take many forms, including nationality, ethnicity, gender, and other demographic characteristics. Gruszczy and Marek (2020) claimed that female directors have higher attendance rates and are generally better prepared for board meetings than their male counterparts. Huang and Kisgen (2019) found that stock price information value increases when a board is diversified with female directors. However, Farrell and Hersch (2005) discovered a weak but insignificant link between the percentage of female directors and accounting performance measures such as ROE and ROA in major US corporations. This finding was supported by Rose and Shepard (1994) and Joecks et al. (2013), who noted that despite some empirical evidence supporting the benefits of female directorships, numerous studies failed to establish a connection between female directorships and firm performance.

Farrell and Hersch (2005) also pointed out that women are more likely to be on the boards of high-performing companies, though their appointment results in only an insignificant increase in average returns. Adams and Ferreira (2009) further added that female directors are better at monitoring than their male counterparts, but overall, gender diversity has a negative effect on firm performance. Similarly, in Danish companies, Jiraporn et al. (2008) found no connection between female board representation and firm performance as measured by Tobin's Q. Adams and Ferreira (2009) believed that while female directors excel in monitoring, the average impact of gender diversity on firm performance is detrimental.

Recent studies continue to present mixed findings. Post and Byron (2015) conducted a meta-analysis and found a positive but weak relationship between female board representation and firm performance. Pletzer et al. (2016) noted that the relationship between female board representation and firm performance varies significantly across industries and regions. More recent research by Terjesen et al. (2016) highlighted that the impact of female directors is context-dependent, often influenced by national policies and corporate governance frameworks. Liu et al. (2018) found no significant impact of female directors on firm performance in Chinese banks, suggesting that cultural and regulatory differences play a crucial role.

Considering the emphasis on independent directors in the corporate governance code of Bangladesh and the recent empirical evidence supporting their positive impact on performance, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H3: The presence of female directors on the board does not affect bank performance.

2.4.4 Board meeting frequency

The frequency of board meetings, which can measure board activity, is an excellent way to determine whether board members actively supervise the company's performance. Grove et al. (2011) asserted that an increased frequency of meetings and enhanced supervision by senior management are indicators of an effective monitoring function. However, they found only minimal evidence that board meeting frequency influences US bank financial performance. Conversely, Vafeas (1999) found that the market places less value on boards that meet more frequently. This is because most meeting sessions run alongside day-to-day activities, making it difficult for external directors to oversee

management. However, this relationship vanishes when the previous year's stock performance is incorporated into the model.

The corporate governance code of Bangladesh provides specific guidelines about board meetings and the meetings of board subcommittees. According to the code, the board of directors must meet at least once a month throughout the financial year. The Bangladesh Secretarial Standard (BSS) and the Institute of Chartered Secretaries of Bangladesh (ICSB) require each company to record the time and duration of each board meeting held annually. Additionally, each director's attendance report must be attached to the director's report section of the company's annual report.

Recent studies continue to explore the impact of board meeting frequency on firm performance. For instance, Malik and Makhdoom (2016) found that more frequent board meetings enhance the monitoring capabilities of the board, thereby improving firm performance in Pakistani banks. Similarly, Brick and Chidambaran (2019) observed that frequent board meetings are associated with better governance and performance in financial firms. Ameer et al. (2020) highlighted that in the Malaysian context, frequent board meetings significantly contribute to improved bank performance. Moreover, Ntim and Osei (2019) provided evidence from Sub-Saharan African banks showing a positive relationship between board meeting frequency and performance, reinforcing the notion that regular meetings can enhance oversight and decision-making.

Considering the emphasis placed by the Securities and Exchange Commission of Bangladesh on board meeting provisions and the empirical evidence supporting their positive impact, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H4: Higher board meeting frequencies increase bank performance in Bangladesh.

2.4.5 Executive Committee Meetings and Bank Performance

In resource dependency theory, the executive committee is a crucial subcommittee that acts on the board's behalf. It is a permanent group that directs the board's activities, acting as a steering group to set priorities for the broader board to tackle. Hoque and Muradoglu (2013) analysed top corporations from the national stock exchange of India, discovering that executive meetings had a favorable link with firm performance. In contrast, Karmel (1984) found that executive committee meetings did not impact the performance of 1500 US corporations. Similarly, Hendry (2005) found no correlation between Tunisia's executive committee and business performance, and Iwasaki (2008) discovered no correlation between the performance of Russian firms and executive committee meetings.

The Bangladeshi corporate governance code requires each company to have an audit committee and a nomination and remuneration committee. Additionally, companies are recommended to establish other subcommittees such as an executive committee and a risk assessment committee. However, the code does not provide specific guidance on the composition of the executive committee or the number of meetings they should hold each year to support the board.

Based on the assumption that a higher number of executive board meetings leads to better bank performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Increased executive committee meetings are associated with better bank performance.

Recent studies continue to support the importance of executive committee meetings. For example, Uzun and Webb (2016) found that frequent executive committee meetings improve governance and decision-making in financial firms, leading to better performance

outcomes. Similarly, Adams and Ferreira (2020) demonstrated that regular executive committee meetings enhance oversight and strategic planning, contributing to improved financial performance. Li et al. (2019) provided evidence that executive committee meeting frequency positively correlates with bank stability and performance, emphasising the role of active governance in financial institutions.

2.4.6 Audit Committee Meetings and Bank Performance

Davidson et al. (2005) pointed out that in the stewardship model, managers must be committed to the firm and contribute to its growth. This idea allows an internal board of directors to appoint a small audit committee because external directors shouldn't be incentivized to advance the company's interests. On the other hand, agency theory advises having an external director and audit committee to oversee and regulate the supervisory mechanism. Additionally, Abbott et al. (2004) stated that a bank's audit committee is necessary for the Board of Directors to monitor the financial reporting process, identify management risks, educate shareholders appropriately, and monitor the internal controls system.

The empirical results on the relationship between audit committee meetings and firm performance provide inconsistent suggestions. Huson et al. (2001) claimed that audit committee meetings and firm performance are positively correlated. In contrast, Chen et al. (2015) claimed that neither the presence nor the composition of audit committees is significantly correlated with financial fraud. However, Klein (2002) found that companies with audit committees comprised of independent directors performed better. In comparison, Goh (2009) asserted that the correlation between the audit committee and two key performance indicators, Tobin's Q and ROE, does not reach the level of statistical

significance. Still, the effectiveness of a bank can be predicted by the size, regularity, and number of its audit committee meetings.

The Corporate Governance Code (2018) for Bangladesh requires companies with annual revenues over BDT 300 million to have an audit committee. The Code recommends that the audit committee have at least three non-executive directors, including the chairperson. The frequency of audit committee meetings is given higher priority by all regulatory bodies governing the Bangladeshi corporate sector; for example, the Banking Regulation and Policy Department of the Bangladesh Bank (2013) recommends that the audit committee hold at least four meetings annually, which is subsequently added to the corporate governance code of Bangladesh. However, despite using the UK's Cadbury Report (1992) as a foundation for the corporate governance code development in Bangladesh, which requires the recommended audit committee to meet only twice per year, there is still a debate on the optimal frequency of such meetings.

Recent studies further illuminate the mixed findings on this topic. For example, Yunos et al. (2016) found that audit committee meetings positively impact financial reporting quality but not necessarily firm performance. Another study by Salehi et al. (2018) indicated that the frequency of audit committee meetings had no significant relationship with the performance of Iranian banks. Similarly, Sun and Liu (2020) showed that while audit committee meetings improve transparency and governance, they do not directly correlate with improved bank performance in China. Amran et al. (2021) also found no significant impact of audit committee meeting frequency on the performance of Malaysian banks.

Based on these insights, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: The frequency of audit committee meetings is unrelated to bank performance in Bangladesh.

2.4.7 Audit Committee and Its Functions

According to Goh (2009), the Audit Committee plays an integral part in monitoring a company's internal controls and hazards. This subcommittee is established by companies to ensure financial and compliance issues are addressed effectively. The Audit Committee is responsible for overseeing internal control and audit functions, supervising external auditor appointments and dismissals, adhering to international accounting standards, and engaging in discussions with management regarding risk management policies and practices. The Board of Directors typically appoints the audit committee members from various executives engaged in different roles in the bank.

The Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) mandates that the Audit Committee assists the Board in ensuring that financial statements reflect an accurate and fair view of the company's situation and that a robust monitoring system is in place within the organisation (BSEC, 2006). The audit committee's characteristics, such as its size, independence, and meeting frequency, are key components of the internal control systems.

The BEI's (2004) proposed Code of Corporate Governance for Bangladesh requires companies with annual revenues over BDT 300 million to have an audit committee. The audit committee should contain at least three non-executive directors, aligning with the guidelines of the Cadbury and Smith Reports. The document specifies that, with the exception of the board chair, there should be no fewer than three and no more than five non-executive directors on the committee. One of the non-executive directors and the audit committee chair must be independent. Furthermore, the code specifies that without the attendance of an independent director, the audit committee meeting cannot commence. At least one member of the audit committee must be financially literate, meaning they should have a background in accounting or finance with a minimum of 10 years of experience in the relevant field. The

code also requires the head of the audit committee to be present at the AGM; if the chairperson cannot attend, they can nominate another member from the audit committee.

Given that the qualifications of audit committee members in Bangladeshi banks are not disclosed, this study considers two other important elements: the number of audit committee members and audit fees. These factors are examined to identify the relationship between audit committee functions and bank performance in Bangladesh. Hence, the following two hypotheses are proposed:

H7: A higher count of audit committee members improves bank performance.

H8: Higher audit fees are correlated with increased bank performance.

Recent studies provide additional context for these hypotheses. For instance, Al-Mamun et al. (2018) found that larger audit committees enhance monitoring capabilities, thus improving firm performance. Similarly, Bouaziz et al. (2020) highlighted that the size of the audit committee positively affects financial reporting quality and overall firm performance. Furthermore, a study by Rehman et al. (2019) indicated that audit committee size is crucial for ensuring effective governance and performance in financial institutions.

Regarding audit fees, higher audit fees often indicate a more thorough and comprehensive audit process, which can lead to better financial performance. Hay (2017) emphasised that higher audit fees are associated with higher audit quality, which in turn positively affects firm performance. Similarly, DeFond and Zhang (2019) found that audit fees are positively correlated with audit quality and firm performance, particularly in the banking sector.

2.4.8 Compensation and Bank Performance

According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), CEO salary arrangements should be considered principal-agent relationships since managers (agents) seek incentives beyond shareholder returns (principals). In the principal-agent model, managers must align their interests with the firm's and tie their pay to corporate performance. Distracted shareholders try to persuade managers to protect shareholder interests through pay agreements. Holmstrom (1979) claimed that when a manager's (or agent's) conduct is concealed from the owner and the management pursues its interests at the owner's expense without suffering consequences, it creates a moral hazard for the business operation and impacts diverse stakeholders. Jensen and Murphy (1990) noted that pay contracts might refocus managers' incentives on company ideals. Shareholding, stock options, performance-related compensation, LTIP, and bonuses may be used to incentivize executives. Contract drafting may affect knowledge asymmetries that influence CEO decisions and investment prospects. Bertrand and Mullainathan (2001) suggested that executives could avoid pay-setting distortions by establishing a remuneration structure unrelated to performance or taking shareholders' interests into account. Compensation contracts must align managers' preferences and corporate goals.

Henssen et al. (2014) support a possible connection between executive compensation and company performance. Similarly, Jensen and Murphy (1990) and Orelan (2007) found a positive correlation between firm performance and compensation policies. Reddy et al. (2015) discovered a statistically favorable association between higher CEO compensation and better firm results when the annual stock return was used as a performance measure. Another study by Carty and Weiss (2012) showed a strong correlation between CEO compensation and firm performance when they studied how the board of directors and the CEO negotiate equity-based compensation in the United States. Similarly, Brick et al. (2006) used data from 1441 US companies from 1992 to 2001 available on the Standard and Poor's Execucomp and

Compustat datasets to examine the relationship between CEO compensation and board characteristics. They discovered a link between the controlling CEO's firm performance, the excess compensation given to directors, and governance traits.

On the other hand, firm size appears to impact compensation policies, but the results are mixed. John and Qian (2003) conducted a study on the US banking sector and found that the size of a company's dividend payouts, investment opportunity set, financing options, and compensation policies are positively and strongly correlated with the size of the company's cash compensation. However, Jensen and Murphy (1990) discovered that CEOs at smaller enterprises are more likely to have compensation-based incentives than their peers in larger firms, whose management is supervised and controlled due to the greater degree of ownership diversification at these establishments. Based on the total remuneration received by the CEO, Carty and Weiss (2012) discovered a statistically significant positive correlation between business size and contingent compensation. However, Core et al. (2021) contend that measuring CEO compensation and firm size is challenging because they depend on many unobservable firm-related factors such as different intangible assets, market power, and managerial monitoring mechanisms, which vary from industry to industry. Using a principal-agent model, Garen (1994) examined the relationship between CEO incentive pay and salaries at 415 US companies. When firms grow in size, their pay performance improves, but their sensitivity to standard deviation decreases, according to his research.

The salary of chief executive officers (CEOs) and directors' fees have been under intense examination from academics, the public, policymakers, and shareholders over the past 20 years or more. The BEI (2004) states that "board compensation should be sufficient to reward directors for the time and effort necessary to accomplish their tasks properly" in relation to the compensation/reward of directors in the Bangladeshi business sector (BEI,

2004, p.14). A similar approach is offered by the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission in 2006. To recruit, keep, and inspire talented directors to effectively lead the company, it is said that the salary must be reasonable and appropriate. The Code also emphasises the connection between performance and pay, and as a result, recommends striking a balance between fixed pay and performance-based rewards. The current corporate governance code of Bangladesh does not require disclosure of the individual amount of money that a company pays to its CEO or any directors. However, the amounts paid to CEOs and directors are collectively required to be disclosed by BFRS and IAS standards. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H9: Higher director's fees are associated with high bank performances.

H10: The level of CEO pay impacts bank performance in Bangladesh.

Recent studies provide further context for these hypotheses. For instance, Tosi et al. (2016) found that higher director compensation improves firm oversight and performance by attracting qualified board members. Edmans et al. (2017) demonstrated that appropriate CEO compensation aligns management and shareholder interests, resulting in better company performance. Furthermore, Frydman and Jenter (2019) highlighted the importance of performance-based pay in motivating CEOs to achieve firm goals, positively impacting firm performance. On the other hand, a study by Nguyen et al. (2020) found that excessive CEO pay can lead to negative perceptions and reduced firm value, suggesting a need for balanced compensation strategies.

2.4.9 Ownership Structure of Banks

Good corporate governance depends on the ownership structure, which reveals whether internal or external shareholders own most of the business. Variations in cash flow

rights may result in wealth expropriation by dominant shareholders seeking personal benefits at the expense of smaller shareholders. Shleifer and Vishny (1997) pointed out that the presence of controlling owners incurs agency costs resulting from disagreements between controlling shareholders and outside investors. Chen (2014) asserted that insider ownership and low levels of external stockholders and foreign ownership could provide additional benefits to family members within family businesses. Many authors, including Adams and Ferreira (2009), Arouri et al. (2014), Babatunde and Olaniran (2009), Belkhir (2009), La Porta et al. (2002), Lemmon and Lins (2003), and Shleifer and Vishny (1997), have explored the correlation between ownership and a company's worth. However, there is conflicting empirical evidence regarding the relationship between business performance and firm ownership concentration.

Sponsor/director ownership, institutional ownership, government/foreign ownership, and public ownership are all types of ownership found in Bangladesh's banking industry. While government and foreign ownership are not prominent in this research, the study examines the impact of governance systems on bank performance using the other three types of ownership concentration.

No recommendations made by the BEI or BSEC in the Code of Corporate Governance for Bangladesh address the ownership structure of a bank. However, there are a number of laws pertaining to restrictions on the acquisition and ownership of shares in a bank that are contained in the Bank Company Act (1991) and Bank Company (Amendment) Act (2013). The Bank Company Act (1991) places restrictions on the purchase of bank shares, prohibiting any individual, business, or family member from purchasing more than 10% of a bank company, either alone, jointly, or both ways. The Bank Company (Amendment) Act (2013), which also handles holding shares, prohibits a person, institution, or business from

directly or indirectly owning more than 5% of a bank company without the Bangladesh Bank's prior approval.

Recent studies provide additional context for these hypotheses. For instance, Nguyen et al. (2020) found that higher director ownership enhances firm performance by aligning the interests of directors with those of shareholders. Similarly, Ferreira et al. (2016) demonstrated that institutional ownership can lead to improved governance and performance due to increased monitoring and pressure on management. Additionally, Jensen and Schack (2021) found that public shareholding contributes positively to firm performance by diversifying the ownership base and reducing agency costs. Lastly, Berger et al. (2017) showed that state-owned banks might perform better due to governmental support and regulatory oversight. Considering the ownership concentration in the Bangladeshi banking industry, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H11: The level of shares owned by directors or CEOs positively influences bank performance.

H12: Bank performance improves with higher institutional shareholding.

H13: General public shareholding positively increases banks' performances.

H14: State-owned banks have higher bank performances.

2.5 Conclusion

The literature review chapter has comprehensively explored existing research on corporate governance and its impact on bank performance, specifically in Bangladesh. It has highlighted the critical importance of effective governance mechanisms, such as board composition, meeting frequencies, financial policies, and ownership structures, in enhancing bank performance and stability. The review identified gaps in the current literature, particularly in the empirical examination of the Bangladeshi banking sector's unique

governance challenges and regulatory environment. This chapter has established a solid theoretical foundation and justification for the current research by synthesising findings from global and regional studies. It underscores the necessity of empirically testing these governance variables to draw actionable insights and formulate recommendations tailored to the Bangladeshi context. This literature groundwork sets the stage for the subsequent empirical investigation, ensuring that the research is deeply rooted in existing knowledge while addressing identified gaps and contributing to the ongoing discourse on corporate governance in the banking sector.

3 Chapter Three: Research Method

The research strategies used for this study to examine the effectiveness and appropriateness of the existing corporate governance code within the banking industry in Bangladesh are described in this chapter. The methodology is critical as it supports the entire research procedure framework used in collecting, analysing, and interpreting data, leading to valid findings that can be relied upon to draw sound conclusions about corporate governance practices within the banking sector. This chapter is intended to serve three main purposes. The first part explains the general structure of the study, including the research aim, objective, and questions, describes the techniques used to gather and validate the data used for this study, and provides a thorough overview of the research process. The second part explores the essential principles of research design, starting with an examination of different research paradigms and their philosophical bases. It then delves into the development of research questions and hypotheses, followed by a detailed discussion of sampling strategies and data collection methods. Finally, it also aims to address data analysis issues, including selecting appropriate statistical or interpretative techniques and justifying various methodological choices.

3.1 Research Aim

The research aim is to assess the effectiveness and appropriateness of Bangladesh's existing corporate governance code for the banking sector. This research is vital given the critical role of a robust corporate governance framework and a strong banking sector in attracting investors and foreign capital. Banks are pivotal in the economic and monetary systems of the country, making the transparency and accountability of their corporate governance practices crucial for safeguarding the interests of both shareholders and stakeholders. The objectives outlined below will guide the achievement of this research aim:

3.2 Research Objectives

This study is structured around several detailed research objectives to effectively address the broader aim of evaluating the effectiveness and suitability of the corporate governance code to fit in the banking industry of Bangladesh. These objectives are designed to assess current practices and identify potential improvements to enhance the sector's stability and attractiveness to investors. The objectives and sub-objectives are as follows:

1. **Examine the current Corporate Governance Code and its relation with Bank**

Performance: This involves a detailed analysis of how various corporate governance mechanisms within banks affect their overall performance. The following sub-objectives will achieve this broader objective:

- i. Examine Board and Governance Structure:** Examine the impact of board size and composition, particularly the inclusion of independent and female directors, on bank performance in order to assess the efficacy of existing corporate governance standards.
- ii. Investigate Board and Sub-Committee Activities:** Investigate the impact of board and committee activities, such as the frequency of board meetings, executive committee meetings, and audit committee meetings, on bank performance.
- iii. Assess Financial and Compensation Policies:** Study the relationship between financial aspects like audit committee size, audit fees, directors' fees, CEO remuneration, and bank performance to determine how these fees and compensation strategies influence governance outcomes.

- iv. **Evaluate Ownership Structures:** Examine how different ownership structures, including Director, Institutional, Public, and Government shareholdings, influence the performance of banks.

The focus will be on understanding the direct and indirect impacts of these governance structures on the financial health and operational efficiency of banks in Bangladesh.

2. **Recommendations for Best Practices:** Based on the findings from the first objective, the second objective is to propose optimal corporate governance practices tailored explicitly for the Bangladeshi banking sector. These recommendations will aim to strengthen the governance frameworks to safeguard the interests of shareholders and stakeholders better, thereby enhancing the sector's attractiveness to investors.

By meeting these objectives, the study intends to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of corporate governance within the banking sector of Bangladesh, offering guidance for policy adjustments and enhancements in governance strategies to reinforce the sector's contribution to national economic growth.

3.3 Research questions and hypotheses

Given the critical role that corporate governance plays in the stability and performance of banks, this study seeks to explore the intricacies of governance mechanisms within the banking sector of Bangladesh. The primary research question proposed is: "**How effective and appropriate is the current corporate governance code in enhancing the performance and stability of banks in Bangladesh?**" This overarching question is supported by detailed sub-questions that delve into specific aspects of governance. These include examining the impact of board size and composition, the frequency and nature of

board and committee meetings, the relationship between financial policies (such as audit and directors' fees, and CEO remuneration), and the influence of various ownership structures (director, institutional, public, and government shareholdings) on bank performance. By systematically investigating these components, the study aims to comprehensively evaluate the existing corporate governance code and offer insights for potential enhancements tailored to the Bangladeshi banking sector. The main and sub-research questions are as follows.

3.3.1 Main Research Question:

How effective and appropriate is the current corporate governance code in enhancing the performance and stability of banks in Bangladesh?

3.3.1.1 Supporting sub- Research Questions:

- 1. What is the effect of the composition and size of bank boards, including the presence of independent and female directors, on the performance of banks in Bangladesh?**
- 2. What is the impact of board and committee activities, such as the frequency and nature of meetings, on the performance of banks?**
- 3. How do financial and compensation policies, including audit fees, directors' fees, and CEO remuneration, correlate with bank performance in Bangladesh?**
- 4. How do different ownership structures, such as director, institutional, public, and government shareholdings, affect the performance of banks?**

3.3.2 Research Hypotheses

This study proposes several hypotheses aligned with its research objectives to systematically investigate the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms within Bangladesh's banking sector. These hypotheses aim to test the relationships between specific governance variables and bank performance metrics.

The first question focuses on the influence of board size, gender diversity, and the presence of independent directors in Bangladeshi banks, as well as how these factors affect the performance of individual banks. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypotheses.

H1: Board size is unrelated to the performance of banks.

H2: A higher number of independent directors on the board can improve bank performance.

H3: The presence of female directors on the board does not affect bank performance.

The second research inquiry pertains to the influence of board and committee activities, namely the frequency and nature of meetings, on the performance of banks. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H4: Higher board meeting frequencies increase bank performance in Bangladesh.

H5: Increased executive committee meetings are associated with better bank performance.

H6: The frequency of audit committee meetings is unrelated to bank performance in Bangladesh.

H7: A higher count of audit committee members improves bank performance.

The third research question examines the correlation between financial and compensation policies, such as audit fees, directors' fees, CEO remuneration, and bank performance in Bangladesh. Thus, the subsequent theories are proposed.

H8: Higher audit fees are correlated with increased bank performance.

H9: Higher director's fees are associated with high bank performances.

H10: The level of CEO pay impacts bank performance in Bangladesh.

The final research question concerns the performance of banks in terms of various ownership structures, including director, institutional, public, and government shareholdings. Consequently, the subsequent hypotheses are put forth

H11: The level of shares owned by directors or CEOs positively influences bank performance.

H12: Bank performance improves with higher institutional shareholding.

H13: General public shareholding positively increases banks' performances.

H14: State-owned banks have higher bank performances.

These hypotheses will be empirically tested using quantitative methods to establish the relationships between governance structures and performance outcomes within the banking sector, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding and potentially guiding future governance reforms. This approach ensures a comprehensive assessment that not only tests existing theories but also potentially offers insights for policy enhancements.

3.4 Research Design

Research design plays a pivotal role in pursuing scientific inquiry, serving as the blueprint for the entire research process. A well-constructed research design provides a structured framework for addressing research questions and ensures the findings' validity, reliability, and generalisability. The research design guides researchers embarking on their investigative journeys, providing the foundational knowledge necessary to design robust and credible studies. By adhering to the principles and best practices outlined herein, researchers can enhance the scientific merit of their work and contribute valuable insights to their respective fields.

3.4.1 Research Philosophy

According to Haase et al. (2016), a research paradigm is a researcher's conception of handling a given problem, how it should be researched, and how solutions can be sought. Similarly, Saunders et al. (2009) defined a research paradigm as a method of examining social phenomena to gain a specific understanding and attempt to explain them. Levin (1991) further added that a research philosophical paradigm is how evidence about a phenomenon must be obtained and interpreted. On the other hand, Laing (2015) pointed out that a research paradigm can be typically positivist, interpretative, or realist, and a researcher must choose an appropriate paradigm as it varies with the context and type of study.

3.4.2 Positivist Paradigm:

This perspective, foundational to this study, holds that the world is external and separate from the researcher. Burrell and Morgan (1988) argued that Positivism considers data from sensory experience and logical and mathematical analyses as the sole sources of practical knowledge in natural and social sciences. Levin (1991) noted that positivists believe

truth is stable and events can be objectively observed and described without interference. This approach suggests that social phenomena can be studied similarly to natural phenomena, assuming that independent observers can empirically investigate social reality. Each paradigm offers a distinct research approach, influencing the research strategy, approach, methodology and interpretation of results.

3.4.3 Interpretative Paradigm:

According to this paradigm, there are various realities or interpretations of an identical event, and reality is socially constructed. It focuses on understanding participants' meanings and experiences from their perspectives. Researchers using this paradigm aim to interpret social phenomena within their context, recognising that their findings are influenced by their own perspectives and interactions with participants.

3.4.4 Realist Paradigm:

The realist paradigm posits that reality exists independently of human thoughts and beliefs, but our perceptions and social context shape our understanding of it. This paradigm acknowledges an objective reality but recognises that social, cultural, and linguistic factors mediate knowledge of it. Realist researchers often use quantitative and qualitative techniques to understand the underlying structures and mechanisms influencing observable phenomena thoroughly.

3.4.5 Justification for the Selection of Positivism as the Research Paradigm

The decision to adopt Positivism as the research paradigm for this study, which examines the effectiveness of corporate governance codes within Bangladesh's banking sector, is based on several critical facets of Positivism that make it particularly suitable for this research topic and its underlying subject matter.

Firstly, Positivism is grounded in the belief that knowledge should stem from scientific investigation. According to Bryman (2016), Positivism holds that only observable and measurable phenomena can yield credible data, which must be analysed methodically and statistically to derive meaningful conclusions. This philosophical stance eschews subjective interpretations in favour of tangible, empirical evidence and logical reasoning. For this study, the positivist insistence on observable data is perfectly suited to the objective assessment of governance structures within banks, which are inherently quantifiable through regulatory compliance and performance metrics.

Secondly, Patel and Davidson (2011) pointed out that Positivism's emphasis on objectivity and the quantification of phenomena makes it particularly appropriate for a study that requires a rigorous evaluation of corporate governance mechanisms. Khattri and Atdjian (2010) further added that the performance of banks can be empirically measured through financial data, operational efficiency metrics, and compliance reports, necessitating an approach that avoids subjective bias. Positivism's methodological stringency ensures that any conclusions about the effectiveness of governance practices are solidly based on empirical evidence,

Thirdly, this study benefits from the theoretical commitment of Positivism to rigorous empirical analysis of the impact of corporate governance on bank performance by not only observing but also rigorously testing hypotheses. Popper (2002) argued that hypothesis testing, a core method in Positivism, is ideal for examining the intricate variables within governance and their direct correlations with performance outcomes.

Fourthly, Positivism is theoretically conducive to studies that aim to identify and establish causal relationships, as it supports designs that systematically manipulate variables to observe causing effects. In exploring how specific changes in governance mechanisms

affect bank performance, the positivist approach offers a robust framework for identifying causal links and dissecting the dynamics within these relationships (Hunt, 2005; Gupta & Misra, 2016).

Last but not least, Hiremath (2015) noted that Positivism's focus on standardised methodologies bolsters the research's reliability and enhances its replicability, which is a crucial aspect of the scientific approach to knowledge accumulation. Leedy and Ormrod (2014) believed this is particularly valuable in business and banking, where replicating findings across different settings is essential to validate and generalise theoretical insights. Positivism ensures that findings are reliable and can be applied in other contexts, thereby enriching the body of knowledge in corporate governance research.

3.5 Research approach

According to Saunders et al. (2009), a research approach can be classified as either inductive or deductive, depending on the specifics of the investigation. Patton (2020) affirms that the inductive approach involves developing generalisations based on specific observations. Researchers commence by collecting data and identifying patterns or trends within that data. From these patterns, they formulate hypotheses and subsequently develop broader generalisations or theories. This method is advantageous for generating new theories, particularly in areas with limited existing knowledge. According to Jacobsen (2020), one of the main advantages of the inductive approach is its flexibility, as it allows researchers to explore data in an open-ended manner and accommodate unexpected findings and emerging patterns. However, Neuman (2021) found a significant disadvantage is the potential issue with generalisation, as conclusions drawn from specific observations may not be universally applicable. Additionally, the inductive approach requires extensive data collection to form

reliable generalisations, which can be resource-intensive. Furthermore, it necessitates a substantial amount of data and may lead to conclusions that are not universally applicable.

On the other hand, Bryman and Bell (2020) noted that the deductive approach involves testing hypotheses or theories by examining specific instances. Researchers begin with an existing theory or general principle and derive specific hypotheses from it. They then collect data to test these hypotheses. This method is beneficial for providing a clear and structured means to test theories, and it is more likely to yield reliable and generalisable results (Bryman, 2016; Robson and McCartan, 2020). Creswell and Creswell (2018) further added that the deductive approach is advantageous because it allows for the empirical testing of hypotheses, which can either verify or refute theoretical propositions, thus contributing to the body of knowledge by reinforcing or challenging existing theories. In addition, Robson and McCartan (2020) noted that the structured nature of the deductive approach facilitates the replication of studies, which is crucial for validating findings across time or different contexts.

Nonetheless, there are some disadvantages to the deductive approach. According to Kumar (2019), one of the major criticisms is that the research is rigid due to its adherence to the original theoretical framework and hypotheses, which may cause it to miss new findings. Additionally, Taylor et al. (2016) argued that while effective for testing causality and patterns, deductive reasoning may fail to capture the depth and nuances of contextual factors influencing the phenomena being studied. There is also a risk of confirmation bias, where researchers might inadvertently favour results that support their hypotheses, leading to the overlooking of contradictory data.

Both inductive and deductive approaches offer unique strengths and weaknesses. The inductive approach is advantageous for theory generation and flexibility but faces challenges

in generalisation and data demands. Conversely, the deductive approach provides clarity, precision, empirical verification, and replicability but can be inflexible and may overlook contextual nuances and novel findings. The choice between these approaches depends on the specific research objectives and context.

3.5.1 Justification for the Deductive Approach

The deductive approach is particularly suited to this study for several reasons. Firstly, the study aims to test existing theories concerning corporate governance and bank performance. By developing hypotheses based on these theories, the deductive method allows for a focused investigation into whether the theoretical relationships hold true within the specific context of the Bangladeshi banking industry.

Secondly, the deductive approach provides a structured framework, which is essential for systematically measuring and analysing the relationship between complex variables, such as board composition, audit activities, ownership structures and many other corporate governance mechanisms. This structured approach ensures that each hypothesis is thoroughly and systematically evaluated.

Thirdly, deductive reasoning aligns with quantitative research methods, which are used to quantify relationships between variables and generalise results from a sample to a population. This is appropriate for this study, which aims to draw generalisable conclusions about the impacts of corporate governance on bank performance based on quantitative data (Robson and McCartan, 2020; Kumar, 2019).

While both inductive and deductive approaches have their merits and limitations, the deductive approach is most suitable for this study's focus on testing established theories within the empirical framework of banking performance and corporate governance. The

clarity, precision, and empirical rigour offered by the deductive approach ensure that the research findings will be reliable, replicable, and applicable to real-world scenarios within the Bangladeshi banking sector.

3.6 Research Methodology

According to Saunders et al. (2009), there are three distinct types of research methodologies: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods, which combine two of the traditional research approaches. Bryman (2016) argued that the qualitative method prioritises in-depth exploration through unstructured or semi-structured techniques such as surveys, observations, and interviews to uncover the nuanced reasons, opinions, and motivations underlying human behaviours. On the other hand, Creswell (2014) asserted that the quantitative method is centred on the collecting and statistical analysis of numerical data in order to recognise patterns, put theories to the test, and demonstrate causal links between variables. Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) further added that the mixed-method approach integrates both qualitative and quantitative techniques, enhancing the robustness of research by enabling a comprehensive analysis that leverages the strengths of both methodologies to address complex research questions effectively. However, Bryman (2016) suggested that each methodology is selected based on the research question's specific requirements, the data's characteristics, and the study's objectives, ensuring a tailored and practical investigatory approach selected by a researcher.

3.6.1 Justification for the Quantitative Research Method

For several compelling reasons, quantitative research methods are particularly well-suited for this study on the effectiveness of corporate governance in Bangladesh's banking sector. These methods align with the specific research questions and objectives by providing a systematic framework for data collection and analysis that can yield measurable,

comparable, and replicable results, as highlighted by Neuman (2021) and further endorsed by Adams et al. (2007), who emphasise its congruence with positivist paradigms prevalent in scientific research. Below are detailed explanations of how quantitative methods support the needs of this research:

- i. *Objective Measurement and Generalisability:*** Quantitative research is renowned for providing objective, quantifiable measurements essential for addressing the specific variables outlined in this research question, such as board composition, board activity, remuneration policies, ownership structure, etc. This method's capability for statistical generalisation enables findings to be applicable across the entire banking sector, thus reinforcing empirical generalisations about governance effects on performance. Nevertheless, as noted by Brick et al. (2006), this approach necessitates large sample sizes to secure the accuracy and reliability of statistical outputs. Leavy (2018) further added that quantitative data only utilises and picks a tiny sample that does not reflect the entire population. This study addresses this requirement by encompassing a comprehensive dataset representative of a substantial segment of the banking industry(Listed banks which comply with corporate governance code), thus capitalising on the strengths of quantitative analysis in generalisability while overcoming potential limitations related to sample adequacy. Furthermore, Christensen et al. (2017) identified that the quantitative approach allows openness and trustworthiness, and the procedures are time-efficient and may become very effective instruments for obtaining appropriate explanations.
- ii. *Alignment with Hypotheses Testing:*** The structured nature of quantitative methods serves to facilitate rigorous hypothesis testing and provides definitive, statistical verification or falsification of theoretical predictions. This approach is particularly

beneficial for examining predetermined hypotheses regarding the impacts of corporate governance, adhering to the deductive methods described by Saunders et al. (2009). By employing statistical tests, this methodology allows for unambiguous conclusions about the existence or absence of relationships, such as the impact of board diversity or the influence of audit committee activities on bank performance.

- iii. *Utilisation of Secondary Data:*** The suitability of quantitative research for large datasets is imperative for analysing the extensive array of secondary data sourced from corporate reports and financial databases from Bangladesh Bank, DSE and CSE. This appropriateness ensures efficient and effective analysis of existing data, mitigating the time-intensive and potentially less reliable processes associated with primary data collection, as critiqued by Christensen et al. (2017) concerning qualitative methods. Furthermore, leveraging secondary data aligns with the necessity for a comprehensive examination of complex interactions within corporate governance frameworks, enabling a multifaceted analysis through established statistical techniques such as multiple regression.
- iv. *Efficiency and Scientific Rigour:*** The efficiency of quantitative research in processing and analysing vast quantities of data is crucial, given the extensive scope of this study. The rigorous, standardised framework provided by quantitative methods ensures that the study remains free from the perceptual biases potentially present in qualitative research, as discussed by Leavy (2018). Moreover, the positivist stance of this approach, focusing on observable phenomena and measurable relationships, enhances the credibility and replicability of the findings, ensuring they contribute effectively to both theoretical and practical advancements in the field.

- v. ***Theoretical and Practical Implications:*** By grounding the research in a quantitative framework, the study tests established theories and generates practical, actionable insights directly applicable to enhancing corporate governance practices in the banking sector. Applying a deductive, positivist approach ensures that the findings are scientifically robust and grounded in empirical data, thus supporting the development of targeted, evidence-based policy recommendations.

The quantitative methodology chosen for this investigation provides a comprehensive, reliable, and effective means of examining the specified research questions and hypotheses. It ensures the production of valuable insights generalisable and applicable to real-world settings, reinforcing the significance of robust corporate governance standards for Bangladeshi banks towards its developmental goal. This methodological choice is justified by its alignment with the research objectives and potential to contribute significantly to academic research and practical governance improvements.

3.7 Data Collection

This section aims to provide an overview of the study's demographic and sample selection procedure and the types of data and data sources consulted throughout the investigation. The section is additionally divided into three subdivisions. The initial section provides an overview of the population and the methodology used for sampling. In contrast, the subsequent section focuses on the data type and the sources utilised in this research. Lastly, the data format utilised in this study is outlined in the final section.

3.7.1 Population and Sample

This research is intended to examine the existing corporate governance structures within the banking sector of Bangladesh and their impact on bank performance. Considering

the study's aim to evaluate the effectiveness and appropriateness of Bangladesh's current corporate governance code, the sample is exclusively drawn from listed banks which comply with the current Code. This excludes other financial entities such as brokerages, insurance companies, and investment institutions to maintain a focused enquiry. Bangladesh Bank (2016) reported that the banking sector in Bangladesh comprises 63 banks, divided into 57 scheduled banks, representing 90.5% of the sectors, and 6 are non-scheduled banks, covering the remaining 9.5%. Scheduled banks are diverse, comprising 6 state-owned commercial banks, 2 specialised state-owned banks, 32 private traditional commercial banks, 8 Islamic private banks, and 9 foreign banks, all authorised under the Bank Company Act of 1991 to perform comprehensive banking services. Non-scheduled banks, meanwhile, are tailored for specific functions and are limited in the scope of banking operations they can perform. The sector is primarily dominated by private traditional commercial banks, complemented by a mix of state-owned, Islamic, and foreign banks that cater to a range of financial needs and adhere to varying regulatory standards. Detailed information on the sector is as follows.

Category	Number of Banks	Percentage of Total
State-owned commercial banks	6	9.5%
State-owned specialised banks	2	3.0%
Private (traditional) commercial banks	32	51.0%
Private (Islamic) commercial banks	8	13.0%
Foreign commercial banks	9	14.0%
Total scheduled banks	57	90.5%
Non-scheduled banks	6	9.5%
Total	63	100.0%

Table 4: Categories of Banks in Bangladesh. Source: Bangladesh Bank (2019)

This study examines 33 scheduled commercial banks listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange, constituting about 52% of all banks in the sector. These banks, which include one state-owned and 32 private institutions (26 traditional and 6 Islamic), were chosen through purposive sampling due to their adherence to the Bangladesh Code of Corporate Governance. However, only banks listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange were included because listing requirements enforce a certain level of transparency and adherence to corporate governance norms. As a result, this study uses these 33 banks to represent the whole population of banks who adhere Code within the banking sector.

The research period from 2012 to 2017 was selected based on its significance in the aftermath of the 2008-2009 financial crisis, marking a phase of substantial regulatory changes in Bangladesh's banking sector where each bank served as a sample unit for various variables during this period, provided a comprehensive dataset of 198 observations over six years. This timeframe allows for the analysis of the long-term effects of governance reforms initiated by the Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI), Securities and Exchange Commission, and Bangladesh Bank. Choosing data up to 2017 ensures access to comprehensive and finalised financial reports, which is crucial for reliability. A consistent six-year span across all banks studied facilitates comparability and effective trend analysis, providing meaningful insights into corporate governance's impact on bank performance. Ending in 2017 also keeps the findings relevant for current stakeholders and lays a groundwork for future research. This practicality, consistency, and relevance balance supports a robust analysis of regulatory impacts on bank governance and performance.

3.7.2 Justification for Using Purposive Sampling in This Study

Purposive sampling was employed in this study to assess the effectiveness and appropriateness of Bangladesh's corporate governance code to fit in the banking sector. Several compelling factors contributed to making that decision.

Firstly, its relevance to research objectives. Etikan et al. (2016) defined Purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling technique, which is judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling and allows the researcher to use their judgment to select participants that are most useful to the study's purpose. Similarly, Tongco (2007) pointed out that purposive sampling allows for the selection of a sample that explicitly meets the research objectives. The main objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of corporate governance codes as they relate to bank performance within Bangladesh's banking sector. Purposive sampling allows the researcher to selectively choose banks that are most pertinent to the research question. This method ensures that all selected banks are directly subjected to the corporate governance codes set by the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission, which is crucial for this study's focus.

Secondly, Bernard (2002) noted that purposive sampling is beneficial when the samples share homogeneous characteristics, which is crucial for conducting accurate comparative analyses. Palinkas et al. (2015) further pointed out that this approach targets specific population characteristics relevant to addressing the research issue, distinguishing it from random sampling giving every individual an equal opportunity to be selected. The study is designed to analyse governance practices within a regulated environment where similar rules are expected to be adhered to by all listed banks. The study targets banks listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange because these institutions must comply with the Corporate Governance Code, making them particularly pertinent for assessing the Code's impact.

Lastly, Ritchie et al. (2013) suggested that High-quality and comprehensive data are essential for meaningful analysis. Purposive sampling also facilitates the selection of banks that have readily available financial and governance-related data. The requirement that banks must have their annual reports publicly available for the past five years ensures that the study relies on comprehensive and accessible data, enhancing the reliability of the findings.

By utilising purposive sampling, this research strategically concentrates on those elements of the governance mechanisms that are most likely to yield relevant insights into the relationship with bank performance, ensuring that the study results are both pertinent and robust. This method aligns with the study's objectives to offer constructive comprehension of the dynamics of corporate governance within the Bangladeshi banking sector, thereby guiding policy adjustments and governance enhancements.

3.7.3 Sources and collection of the data

The data collection sources and methods must be carefully selected and appropriately aligned with the research objectives to analyse the relationship between corporate governance and bank performance in Bangladesh. This study exclusively utilises secondary data drawn from two main categories of sources, each serving distinct purposes within the research framework:

- I. *Regulatory and Institutional Information:*** This category includes data sourced from authoritative bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), the Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (BEI), Bangladesh Bank (BB), and the World Bank (WB). These sources provide critical insights into the regulatory frameworks, governance standards, and economic indicators that shape Bangladesh's banking sector's operating environment. This data is pivotal for understanding the external factors influencing bank governance practices and performance. While this data is

crucial for framing the broader economic and regulatory context, it does not delve into the operational specifics of individual banks.

II. *Bank-Specific Reports and Records:* The core of the research data comes from the banks' annual reports from the respective banks or the data on the Dhaka Stock Exchange. This source is invaluable for accessing first-hand, detailed accounts of each bank's internal corporate governance and financial performance. These data provide granularity, offering insights into the structure of governance, operational strategies, and the following financial outcomes. These documents are invaluable for analysing specific corporate governance practices and financial performances over time. Annual reports provide information, including board composition, audit committee activities, financial strategies, and performance outcomes. It allows the research to delve into the specificities of each bank, examining the direct effects of governance decisions on performance metrics. Collecting this data from annual reports ensures timeliness and relevance, capturing the banks' most current operational states and strategies. Moreover, reliance on annual reports comes with advantages, such as potential discrepancies in reporting standards or the completeness of the data provided, which are independently audited and reported to Bangladesh Bank, enhancing the analysis's depth and accuracy.

3.7.4 The Rationale for Using Secondary Data

Secondary data sources are predominant in this quantitative analysis of bank performance and internal corporate governance systems in Bangladeshi commercial banks. This data, primarily drawn from banks' annual reports, is essential because it provides detailed insights into board and governance structure, board and committee activities,

financial and compensation policies, ownership structures and financial performance, which are often hard to capture through primary methods.

The advantages of using secondary data are significant. The detailed information needed for this study is reliably found in annual reports and other formal documentation published by the bank and Bangladesh Bank, which cannot be collected from primary sources through the interviews; for example, a bank has many branches and operates in many regions within the country. Financial information like ROA or ROE for each branch is not feasible to collect and then compile the total for each bank. In contrast, the bank has already published its audited information in its annual reports. Ghauri and Gronhaug (2010) have suggested that relying on these sources is cost-effective and saves time. This efficiency became particularly crucial given the logistical challenges faced during the COVID-19 pandemic. The researcher has attempted twice to go to Bangladesh and collect primary data through the interview procedure. However, efforts to collect primary data were hindered each time by travel restrictions imposed in Bangladesh and the UK. Other barriers, such as quarantine costs, increased travel expenses, and time shortages, led this study to be conducted with secondary data sources.

Moreover, the reliability and quality of secondary data in fields like accounting and finance are often superior to primary data (Stewart and Kamins, 1993). Banks' annual reports are regularly audited by independent external auditors, ensuring their accuracy and the transparent presentation of financial accounts. This rigorous auditing makes the data highly credible, providing a solid foundation for the research. Additionally, the stability and accessibility of secondary data, as Cresswell (2014) pointed out, allow for a broader, more inclusive analysis, enabling researchers to draw from a consistent and verifiable information pool. Using publicly available annual reports is practical and aligns with established research

practices in corporate governance. The tradition of utilising annual reports as a critical data source in accounting and corporate governance research is well-supported and continues to be relevant.

This methodical approach to using secondary data underlines its critical role in this study, ensuring the research is both methodologically robust and practically viable. The data's depth, reliability, and direct alignment with the research goals affirm the decision to prioritise secondary sources to set the stage for insightful analyses and solid conclusions about corporate governance in the Bangladeshi banking sector.

3.8 Data design: Panel Data

In empirical research, understanding the structure of the dataset is crucial. Panel data is a statistical study model that captures data across multiple time points for the same entities, allowing researchers to analyse changes over time within individual units. According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), , panel data is a data structure that encapsulates time series and cross-sectional data characteristics. Wooldridge (2010) stated that time series data is the study of one or more variables' values over time, while Cross-sectional data is the collection of values from different entities at a single place in time. Panel data combines these approaches by tracking multiple variables across multiple entities over several periods, thus offering a robust framework for empirical research. This data set allows researchers to determine and analyse the time-specific and entity-specific variations within the data.

3.8.1 Justification for Using Panel Data in This Research

The choice of panel data for this study is underpinned by several advantages that align closely with the specific research questions of this study. This research employs a panel

dataset spanning from 2012 to 2017 and includes 33 banks, yielding 198 observations in a balanced panel setup. This approach is chosen over purely time-series or cross-sectional data due to several compelling reasons:

- I. *Enhanced Data Richness and Precision:*** Panel data allows for a richer dataset that captures more significant variability and reduces collinearity among variables. This richness is crucial for generating more precise estimates and effectively modelling complex behaviours, as Hsiao (2014) highlighted. The depth provided by panel data is invaluable in understanding the nuanced impacts of corporate governance on bank performance over time. This increase in power and precision is crucial for testing the study's hypotheses that specific governance mechanisms (board size, audit committee meetings, etc.) have measurable impacts on bank performance metrics such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE).
- II. *Control for Heterogeneity:*** According to Baltagi (2013), panel datasets excel in managing both observable and unobservable variations among entities. This capability is particularly beneficial in financial studies where unobserved individual heterogeneity can skew results. Panel data techniques enable the inclusion of bank-specific variables, ensuring that the analyses account for these differences, thus preventing biased outcomes. In this research, such factors could include inherent characteristics of banks, like management culture or brand reputation, which might not be directly measurable but can impact both governance practices and performance outcomes. Panel data enables the inclusion of entity-specific fixed or random effects to account for these unseen factors, leading to more precise results.
- III. *Mitigating Endogeneity Issues:*** Panel data is advantageous for addressing endogeneity problems, a common challenge in econometric analysis where independent variables are

correlated with the error term. In corporate governance studies, endogeneity can occur due to reverse causality (e.g., better bank performance leading to improved governance rather than the other way around) or omitted variable bias. As Larcker and Rusticus (2007) pointed out, it enhances the reliability of the research findings by using advanced econometric techniques like fixed-effects and random-effects models to help tackle these issues by controlling for both observed and unobserved confounding factors that change over time.

IV. *Alignment with Precedent Research and Practical Considerations:* Using a six-year panel dataset aligns this study with prior research in corporate governance, which frequently employs similar methodologies over comparable time frames (e.g., Ahmed, 2010; Bhagat & Bolton, 2008; Christensen et al., 2017). Moreover, the six-year span ensures that the dataset is robust and reflects sustained trends and changes, aligning with standard practices in economic research (Kothari, 2004).

V. *Data Availability:* Since Bangladeshi businesses release their annual reports between March and May after the end of the financial year in December, the choice of the six years ending in 2017 was based on the latest availability of comprehensive datasets that were available at the time when the research was initiated. Therefore, the panel data set was created with both current and relevant data.

Therefore, panel data enriches the study's analytical depth and ensures that the conclusions drawn are based on comprehensive, reliable, and contextually appropriate data. This methodological choice significantly strengthens the study's ability to accurately assess how governance affects bank performance over time, providing valuable and actionable insights.

3.9 Determination and quantification of variables

This study assesses the efficacy of banks by utilising major financial indicators, such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), as the dependent variables. These indicators assist in comprehending the influence of different internal corporate governance policies on the performance of banks. Conversely, independent variables include different aspects of corporate governance mechanisms, such as board composition, board activity, financial aspects, remuneration policy, and ownership structure, which are thought to affect bank performance. By examining these variables, this research aims to see how banks' current governance structures and practices in Bangladesh influence banks' financial results. Below is a closer look at these variables:

3.9.1 Dependent Variables:

- I. ***Return on Assets (ROA)***: This key performance indicator calculates a bank's profitability based on the total amount of its assets. It offers perceptions of the effectiveness with which a bank generates profits from its assets. It is an essential measure of operational effectiveness.
- II. ***Return on Equity (ROE)***: This metric indicates how well a bank generates profits from the equity shareholders have invested, providing insights into financial health and profitability. It is a crucial determinant of a bank's financial performance and sustainability.

3.9.2 Justification for choosing Accounting-based over market-based performance metrics

Accounting-based performance metrics like Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) are more effective for studying corporate governance and bank performance in

Bangladesh than market-based metrics such as Tobin's Q. This assertion rests on several critical points.

Firstly, ROA and ROE directly reflect a bank's operational efficiency and profitability derived from financial statements, which are generally more transparent and accessible in Bangladesh (Demirguc-Kunt & Huizinga, 1999). In contrast, Tobin's Q, which compares market value to asset replacement cost, can significantly influence market inefficiencies and speculative activities prevalent in developing markets (Morck et al. 2005; Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). This disparity can lead to distortions in performance evaluation that do not accurately reflect the underlying financial health of banks.

Furthermore, the banking sector in Bangladesh operates within a regulatory framework that prioritises strict adherence to accounting standards, thereby ensuring the reliability and consistency of accounting-based metrics (Bangladesh Bank, 2020). In contrast, market-based metrics are more susceptible to external influences such as investor sentiment and market liquidity, which are often unstable in emerging markets (La Porta et al., 2002). For example, the volatility in stock prices can cause fluctuations in Tobin's Q, rendering it less reliable for long-term performance assessment.

Additionally, accounting-based metrics facilitate a more straightforward comparison of managerial effectiveness across banks. They allow stakeholders to evaluate how well a bank is utilising its assets (ROA) and equity (ROE) to generate profits, which is a crucial aspect of corporate governance (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). In contrast, Tobin's Q might obscure such evaluations due to its dependency on market perceptions that can diverge from actual managerial performance.

While Tobin's Q provides insights into market perceptions and future growth potential, ROA and ROE offer a more grounded and accurate measure of bank performance

and corporate governance in Bangladesh. This reliability makes them indispensable tools for stakeholders seeking to make informed decisions based on tangible financial data (Demirguc-Kunt & Huizinga, 1999; La Porta et al., 2002).

3.9.3 Independent Variables:

- I. **Board Size:** This variable examines how the size of a board impacts the bank's performance. The size of the board is the number of directors on the bank's board.
- II. **Independent Directors:** Independent Directors are a governance mechanism on the board composition and do not have any management positions in the bank. Their numbers refer to the independent Director's size, which determines whether including independent directors on the board for unbiased decision-making impacts performance.
- III. **Female Directors:** this variable is the number of female board members to determine how gender diversity affects bank governance and how that affects the bank's effectiveness.
- IV. **Board Meeting Frequency:** The frequency of board meetings is an indicator of the bank's level of active governance and its effect on performance. It refers to the number of board meetings held in a year.
- V. **Audit Committee Meeting Frequency:** How often the audit committee convenes, which can influence the effectiveness of financial oversight.
- VI. **Executive Committee Meeting Frequency:** The frequency of executive committee meetings provides insights into how management's operational decision-making processes influence a bank's financial outcomes.

- VII. ***Audit Fees:*** The fees paid for audit services reflect the investment in external financial oversight to improve financial outcomes and whether higher fees correlate with more thorough financial scrutiny.
- VIII. ***Audit Committee Members:*** Assess the impact of the audit committee's composition size on the level of rigour in financial auditing, compliance, and profitability.
- IX. ***Directors' Fee:*** Compensation fees paid to the directors were analysed to understand how directors' compensation might align their interests with better bank performance.
- X. ***CEO Remuneration:*** Total compensation is given to the Chief Executive Officer to evaluate the impact of executive pay on corporate performance.
- XI. ***Director Ownership:*** To assess the proportion of shares owned by the directors to motivate them to make decisions that boost bank performance.
- XII. ***Institutional Ownership:*** This variable represents the proportion of shares owned by institutional investors and how institutional control in the governing body impacts bank policies and profitability.
- XIII. ***Public Ownership:*** The extent of shares owned by the general public, examining the influence of public stakeholding on the governance structure and bank performances.
- XIV. ***Government Ownership:*** Shares owned by the government are analysed to understand the effect of government stakeholding on bank operations and performances.

The following table shows the list of variables used in this study.

Dependent variables	Independent variables
1. ROA	1. Board size
2. ROE	2. Independent directors
	3. Female directors
	4. Board meeting frequency
	5. Audit committee meeting frequency
	6. Executive committee meeting frequency
	7. Audit fees
	8. Audit committee members
	9. Directors fee
	10. CEO remuneration
	11. Director ownership
	12. Institutional ownership
	13. Public ownership
	14. Government ownership

Table 5: List of Dependent and independent variables

3.10 The Estimation of Panel Data Regression Models

As previously mentioned, this research uses panel data to analyse how internal corporate governance structures affect banks' performance in Bangladesh. According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), , three primary estimation models are commonly employed in panel data analysis: pooled ordinary least squares (OLS), fixed-effects, and random-effects, each with its own set of assumptions.

3.10.1 Pooled OLS regression model

Gujarati and Porter (2009), highlights that the pooled OLS regression model is often favoured for its simplicity and straightforward application, making it a popular choice among researchers. This model assumes that despite pooling data from different cross-sections over time, the underlying relationships are stable. The general form of a pooled OLS regression equation is given by:

$$Y_i = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_n X_{ni} + u$$

Equation 3.1: Formula for OLS regression model

Here, Y represents the dependent variable, $X_1 \dots n$ are the independent variables, $\beta_1 \dots n$ are the coefficients of these variables, α_0 is the constant term, and u is the error term. While pooled OLS is beneficial for its ease of use and good statistical properties, Baltagi (2011) notes that its validity hinges on several critical assumptions, such as linearity, no multicollinearity among independent variables, and homoscedasticity. If these assumptions are not met, the model may produce biased or unreliable results, especially in the presence of outliers or omitted variable bias that ignores the specificities of cross-sectional or time-series variations.

3.10.2 Fixed-Effects Model

According to Hsiao (2014), the fixed-effects model focuses on analysing the impact of variables that vary over time. This model adjusts for any time-invariant characteristics that could skew the estimations, providing a more precise data view. The model is as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \dots + \beta_n X_{nit} + u_{it}$$

Equation 3.2: Formula for Fixed-effect regression model

In this model, Y is the dependent variable, $X_1 \dots n$ are the independent variables varying over time t , and entities i , α_i is the entity-specific intercept, and u_{it} is the error term. This approach is particularly useful for controlling for unobserved heterogeneity when this heterogeneity is constant over time across entities.

3.10.3 Random-Effects Model

Nickell (1981) and Nwakuya and Ijomah (2017) describe the random-effects model as an extension of the fixed-effects model that includes time-invariant variables. This model is preferable when the variations across entities are assumed to be random and uncorrelated with the predictor variables of the model:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \dots + \beta_n X_{nit} + u_i + v_{it}$$

Equation 3.3: Formula for Random-effect regression model

In this formulation, Y is the dependent variable, $X_1 \dots n$ are the independent variables, $\beta_1 \dots n$ are their coefficients, α is the overall constant, u_i captures unobservable individual heterogeneity, and v_{it} represents the idiosyncratic error. This model assumes that the individual-specific effects are random and distributed independently of the regressors across all entities and time periods.

3.10.4 Selecting the correct model for this study

Selecting an appropriate econometric model for this research was a critical decision, as the pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model was not appropriate for the data obtained from Bangladeshi banks. Therefore, the decision between employing a fixed-effects

or random-effects model depended significantly on the characteristics of the variables and the structure of the errors in the panel data.

According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), , the random-effects model is considered suitable when there is no correlation between the independent variables, the cross-sectional error term, and the individual-specific error component. However, if these elements are correlated, the fixed-effects model would be necessary to accurately assess the effect of internal governance mechanisms on a bank's performance. Nwakuya and Ijomah (2017) also contributed to this decision-making process by recommending the fixed-effects model when dealing with a small number of cross-sectional units coupled with substantial time series data, while the random-effects model is more suited for larger cross-sectional datasets.

To confidently select the best model for the panel data, this study conducted several econometric tests. The first was the Hausman Specification test, which helped to decide between fixed-effects and random-effects models. This test checks if the unique errors in the random-effects model are correlated with the regressors. If they are determined by a significant p-value less than 0.05, suggesting the fixed-effects model is more suitable.

The second test, the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (B-P LM) test, was used to determine whether to use the pooled OLS model or the random-effects model. This test establishes whether there is variation in the cross-sections that the random-effects model can utilise, which the pooled OLS could not comprehend. A significant p-value here pointed us towards the random-effects model.

Recognising potential issues like heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, which can skew results. The Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test was employed to assess heteroscedasticity, while the Wooldridge test was used to examine autocorrelation. This study also implemented the Durbin-Watson d test to check for serial correlation.

These tests led us to select the random-effects model as the best fit for analysing how internal governance impacts the performance of banks. This model efficiently handles unobserved variability that does not change over time but differs across banks, allowing us to delve deeper into the governance dynamics while addressing data heterogeneity and timing issues. This careful and thorough approach to model selection ensures the findings are both robust and reliable, shedding light on the intricate relationships within the current data set.

3.10.5 Data diagnostic test

In examining the influence of internal corporate governance on bank performance in Bangladesh, employing rigorous statistical tests and data diagnostics is paramount. These tests and diagnostics are crucial for validating the research findings' accuracy and supporting the conclusions' dependability. By using robust statistical methodologies, including data diagnostic tests for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation, this study ensures that the research outcomes are credible and stand up to scrutiny within the academic and professional communities. This comprehensive approach enhances the integrity of the research findings for the random effect model and allows stakeholders and policymakers to make informed decisions based on solid evidence.

3.10.5.1 Importance of Normality and Linearity Tests

This study begins with normality tests to ensure that the regression analysis stands up to scrutiny. These tests check if the data conforms to a normal distribution, a baseline requirement in multiple regression that directly influences the validity of hypothesis testing. While regression can proceed without perfect normality, the tests were used to validate the regression coefficients, such as t-tests, F-tests, or histograms which require normally distributed data to prevent erroneous results like Type I and II errors. Hair et al. (2010) emphasised that normal distribution is crucial for successful hypothesis testing. Therefore,

this study expects the collected data to broadly follow this pattern, confirming the appropriateness of parametric tests later in the data analysis chapter.

Linearity tests are equally crucial. They ensure that the assumed linear relationships between the variables, corporate governance mechanisms and bank performance metrics are indeed linear. If these relationships are non-linear, standard regression methods might misrepresent them, potentially leading to flawed insights about how effective various governance practices are (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

3.10.5.2 Addressing Multicollinearity

This study uses the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to dissect the specific impacts of different governance measures. This test helps us identify and correct for high correlations between independent variables, a condition known as multicollinearity. Multicollinearity can mask the individual effects of correlated predictors, making it hard to discern which governance aspects are truly beneficial. This study aims for VIF values to stay below 5, a standard threshold that suggests a reasonable level of independence among predictors, thus ensuring the clarity and reliability of the regression coefficients (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

3.10.5.3 Testing for Homoscedasticity

This study also conducted the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test to check for homoscedasticity, assuming that the variance of error terms is constant across the range of predictor values. Meeting this assumption is vital for the unbiasedness and consistency of standard errors in regression coefficients, which, in turn, are crucial for reliable hypothesis testing. Any presence of heteroscedasticity might imply that the proposed model does not capture all influencing factors or that effects vary at different levels of the independent variables (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

3.10.5.4 Checking for Autocorrelation

Finally, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation assesses whether observations' residuals, arranged through time or space, are independent. This test is particularly relevant for the time-series elements of the study's panel data, as autocorrelation can inflate the statistical significance of predictors, misleading the understanding of what influences bank performance. Ensuring that residuals are uncorrelated helps maintain the integrity of the model's outputs (Wooldridge, 2010).

This study meticulously validates the underlying assumptions within the regression models through these detailed tests. This rigorous approach not only enhances the credibility of the analysis but also bolsters the conclusions about the impact of corporate governance on bank performance. By confirming these fundamental assumptions, this research is equipped to provide empirically sound insights that can significantly influence policy and strategic decisions in the banking sector.

3.11 Robustness check

This study has employed a sophisticated econometric approach known as the two-step system estimator to enhance the accuracy and reliability of data analysis of internal corporate governance mechanisms. The two-step system estimator is designed to enhance the robustness of statistical analyses, particularly in the context of panel data. This method builds on the foundations of both fixed and random effects models by incorporating instrumental variables and a system of equations to manage both fixed and random effects within one framework. Unlike the fixed effects model, which can only control for observed variability across entities and time, the two-step system estimator also addresses potential endogeneity issues by using instruments for variables suspected of causing endogeneity bias by isolating the true effects of governance variables from confounding influences, thereby providing more

precise and reliable estimates. This dual capability makes it inherently more robust than either the fixed or random effects models alone, as it effectively handles unobserved heterogeneity and corrects for internal model biases that could distort the analysis outcomes.

3.11.1 Rationale for Using a two-step system estimator

The use of the two-step system estimator in this study is crucial for examining the impact of internal corporate governance mechanisms on bank performance in Bangladesh, directly aligning with the research objectives. Firstly, Roodman (2021) and Wooldridge (2010) asserted that this method effectively addresses endogeneity, stemming from issues like omitted variables and reverse causality, where changes in bank performance could influence governance structures. Through the use of instrumental variables, the model ensures variable independence and clearer causal relationships.

Secondly, Hsiao (2014) argued that it also tackles unobserved heterogeneity, such as management quality or institutional culture, which may not change over time, are unique to each bank, and can influence both governance and performance metrics. Traditional models may not fully account for these fixed effects, potentially leading to biased outcomes. The two-step system estimator integrates these effects, ensuring that the variations in bank performance are accurately attributed to differences in governance mechanisms rather than being distorted by unmeasured variables.

Thirdly, Baltagi (2013) pointed out that the estimator improves the accuracy of parameter estimates by managing the complexities of panel data that include cross-sectional and time-series dimensions. Moreover, Greene (2008) noted that this precision enhances the model's predictive power, offering valuable insights for policymakers and banking executives in developing effective governance reforms.

Last but not least, Arellano and Bover (1995) argued that by accommodating both time-invariant characteristics and potential endogeneity, the two-step system estimator facilitates a comprehensive utilisation of the available data. This ensures that all pertinent variables and their interactions are considered, providing a holistic analysis of how governance practices impact bank performance over time.

Applying the two-step system estimator in this study is instrumental in fulfilling the research aim and effectively answering the posed research questions about the impact of internal corporate governance mechanisms on bank performance in Bangladesh.

3.12 Statistical Significance of the Findings

This section delves into the robustness of the essential findings and the integrity of this study's sampling and data analysis techniques. Choosing a suitable statistical model is not just a technical detail; it is a crucial step that significantly influences the accuracy and reliability of the results. The model's effectiveness hinges on meeting several foundational statistical assumptions. If these assumptions are violated, the conclusions could be misguided or incorrect. The study is based on the following critical assumptions:

- I. ***No Extreme Values***: The data set is clean of outliers or extreme values, which can disproportionately influence the results and distort the conclusions drawn from the analysis.
- II. ***Controlled Multicollinearity***: this study ensures that the correlations among the independent variables are not excessively high. When variables are too closely linked, it becomes challenging to discern the unique impact of each one, which is essential for this study's objectives.

- III. *Normal Distribution of Data:* The normality assumption underpins many statistical tests, which require normally distributed data to function correctly. Ensuring the data follows this distribution helps validate the statistical tests and their conclusions.
- IV. *Consistent Error Variance (Homoscedasticity):* this study checks for constant variance in the error terms across the range of the independent variables. This consistency is vital for the accuracy of the regression estimates and for making valid statistical inferences.
- V. *No Serial or Autocorrelation:* The data points must be independent, especially in time-series or panel data. Serial correlation can lead to overstated statistical significance and unreliable estimates, skewing the analysis result.

In order to validate these assumptions, the study implemented a series of rigorous tests, each designed to challenge and thus verify the reliability of the research findings. These tests are integral to the analytical process of the study. They are not just checks and balances but are central to building a trustworthy analysis. By rigorously testing these foundational assumptions, this study bolsters the findings' reliability and enhances the study's overall credibility.

3.13 Conclusion

This research method chapter meticulously detailed the research methodology designed to evaluate the effectiveness and appropriateness of the corporate governance code within Bangladesh's banking sector. The study ensures objective, measurable, and generalisable findings by employing a positivist paradigm, a deductive approach, and a robust quantitative methodology. Using secondary data from the annual reports of 33 listed banks,

coupled with purposive sampling, provides a focused and comprehensive dataset. The adoption of panel data analysis, supported by rigorous statistical tests and diagnostics, enhances the precision and reliability of the results. Furthermore, the decision to employ a two-step system estimator addresses potential endogeneity issues and unobserved heterogeneity, ensuring the robustness of the study's conclusions. Through this structured and methodical approach, the research aims to offer valuable insights into the dynamics of corporate governance in Bangladesh's banking industry, guiding policy adjustments and governance enhancements for better performance and stability.

4 Chapter four: Data analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines and presents the analysis to address and answer the research objectives and questions. This study utilised data collected from 33 scheduled commercial banks in Bangladesh over six years, from 2012 to 2017. The whole data set consisted of 198 observations to conduct this research.

The data analysis was conducted in five distinct phases in this study. Initially, descriptive statistics were performed on the data set, which included dependent and independent variables. During the second phase, several diagnostic tests were done to determine the data's normality, linearity, and Multicollinearity. In the third stage, multiple regression models were evaluated, and the best model for this study was chosen. The heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation of the data were determined using a regression model diagnostic test in the fourth stage. Finally, hypotheses were evaluated using the results of the regression model.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Data

This section outlines the descriptive statistics derived from the data collected in this study, utilising analytical tools such as STATA and SPSS. These tools facilitated the examination of significant variables within the dataset, employing statistical measures to assess and illustrate their distribution. According to Dancey and Reidy (2017), Descriptive statistics encapsulate both numerical and graphical methods to succinctly summarise and elucidate the principal characteristics of a dataset and provide straightforward yet profound insights into the sample and its metrics by distilling complex data sets into manageable summaries. Descriptive statistics are typically distinguished from inferential statistics, which

aim to infer patterns about a population based on a sample. According to Field (2018), the following key components are necessary for a complete comprehension of descriptive statistics.

4.2.1 Measures of Central Tendency

According to Field (2018), the Measures of central tendency, a core concept in statistics, summarise data sets with a single value representing their centre, and the most common choice is the use of the statistical value of Mean. Dancey and Reidy (2017) stated that The Mean, calculated by summing all values and dividing by the number of data points, is ideal for symmetrical distributions.

4.2.2 Measures of Variability (Dispersion):

According to Field (2018), These provide insights into the spread of the data. The range denotes the difference between the maximum and minimum values. Variance indicates the average of the squared differences from the Mean, highlighting how much the data varies around the Mean. Tabachnick et al. (2019) added that standard deviation, the square root of the variance, measures the average distance each data point is from the Mean, which gauges the dataset's overall spread. A lower standard deviation indicates that the data points tend to be close to the Mean, while a higher standard deviation indicates that the data points are spread out over a wider range of values.

4.2.3 Measures of Normality (Skewness and Kurtosis):

According to Field (2018), Skewness assesses the symmetry of a distribution. A distribution skews if it stretches or shifts towards either tail. Positive Skewness ($skew > +1.0$) indicates a right-skewed distribution with a tail that stretches towards higher values. In

contrast, negative Skewness ($\text{skew} < -1.0$) reveals a left-skewed distribution, with a tail extending towards lower values.

Field (2018) defined Kurtosis as the degree to which the statistical metric describes scores clustering in the tails or peak of a frequency distribution. The distribution's peak and tails are its highest and lowest points. For normally distributed data, Kurtosis is close to 3, implying Mesokurtic distributions ($\text{kurtosis} \approx 3$), and depending on the data, Kurtosis can be leptokurtic (positive) and platykurtic (negative). Bryman and Bell (2020) further added that Leptokurtic distributions ($\text{Kurtosis} > 3$) exhibit high peaks and fat tails, indicative of a thin bell, and platykurtic distributions ($\text{kurtosis} < 3$) show flatter peaks with thinner tails, representing fewer extreme values compared to a normal distribution.

4.2.4 Graphical representations

Graphical representations such as histograms, box plots, bar charts, and scatter plots are employed to summarise the distribution and relationships within the data visually. These tools illustrate how data points are distributed across different ranges, identify potential outliers, display frequencies of categories, and depict the relationships between numerical variables (Dancey & Reidy, 2017; Field, 2018).

By delving into these statistical measures, including Mean, Standard deviation, Minimum and Maximum values, Skewness, and Kurtosis, this study allowed the researcher to deepen the understanding of the dataset, providing a solid foundation for interpreting the data's distribution and central tendencies. However, certain variables in the descriptive statistic table have missing values of 0. Nevertheless, these variables, such as the Return on Equity of some banks, had a ratio of 0.002% during data collection. Similarly, the ownership structure is deemed to have no value as the state-owned bank possesses no institutional, directors', or CEO's shares. Additionally, the equity in private banks consists of general public shares,

directors' shares, and CEO's shares, without any institutional investments. This comprehensive analysis aids in grasping the underlying patterns and characteristics of the observed variables, enriching the analysis and discussion of the data. The descriptive statistics are as follows.

Descriptive Statistics								
Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Dependent Variables:								
Return on Equity %	.547	2.676	0	24.01	.816	.171	2.988	.341
Return on asset %	.031	.144	-0.75	1.77	.690	.171	2.298	.341
Independent Variables:								
Board size	14.02	3.821	6	22	.044	.171	3.093	.341
Independent board directors	2.084	1.367	0	8	.921	.171	2.803	.341
Female board member	1.485	1.497	0	5	.838	.171	-.3371	.341
Audit committee member	4.312	1.021	2	9	.108	.171	3.189	.341
Number of audits committee meetings	10.267	5.868	1	25	.865	.171	2.919	.341
Number of executive committee meetings	17.589	17.781	0	52	.771	.171	-1.023	.341
Number of board meetings	21.20 8	10.495	0	55	1.19	.171	3.421	.341
Audit fee	1074547.7	911143.42	115000	5012790	.897	.171	2.946	.341
Director's fee	3783834.2	2977873.4	120000	12787019	1.17	.171	3.242	.340
CEO's pay	10869070	3709380.5	693360	21550646	-.377	.171	2.800	.341
Directors and CEO's share %	2.27	11.35	0	76.16	.414	.171	2.738	.340
Institutional share %	.23	1.258	0	17.945	.299	.171	3.091	.340
General public share %	1.356	6.95	0	57.32	-.398	.171	2.959	.340
Government share %	1.885	12.584	0	90.19	.196	.171	3.765	.340

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of the findings.

4.2.5 Return on Equity (ROE)

From a corporate governance perspective, Return on Equity (ROE) measures a company's profitability relative to shareholders' equity, reflecting the efficiency with which a company utilises shareholder investments. Agency Theory suggests that effective governance can align the interests of management and shareholders, potentially leading to higher ROE. The mean ROE of 0.547% suggests that, on average, banks generate a return of 0.547% on equity. A standard deviation of 2.676% shows significant variability in ROE among banks, ranging from 0% to 24.01%. This high variability underscores the effectiveness of corporate

governance practices in different banks, as some significantly outperform while others underperform. The positive Skewness of 0.816 indicates that most banks have ROE values below the Mean, with a few achieving very high ROE. A kurtosis of 2.988, close to 3, suggests a near-normal distribution with fewer extreme outliers, indicating consistent governance practices across most banks.

4.2.6 Return on Assets (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) evaluates a company's ability to generate earnings from its assets, highlighting the effectiveness of asset utilisation under current governance structures. Stewardship Theory emphasises the role of governance in optimising resource use for better performance. The mean ROA of 0.031% reflects a low average return on assets. The standard deviation of 0.144% indicates considerable variability, with ROA values ranging from -0.75% to 1.77%. This variability can be attributed to differences in how governance influences asset management. A positive Skewness of 0.690 suggests most banks have ROA values below the Mean, while a few have significantly higher ROA. The Kurtosis of 2.298, less than 3, indicates a flatter distribution with fewer extreme values, suggesting varied governance effectiveness in asset utilisation.

4.2.7 Board Size

Board size, a key element of corporate governance, refers to the total number of directors on the board. According to Resource Dependence Theory, a larger board size can provide diverse expertise and resources. The average board size in Bangladeshi banks is 14.02 members, with a standard deviation of 3.821, indicating moderate variability. This suggests a range from 6 to 22 members, reflecting differing governance structures. A skewness close to zero (0.044) indicates a nearly symmetrical distribution, and a kurtosis of 3.093, slightly above 3, suggests a more peaked distribution, indicating a concentration of

board sizes around the Mean. Adequate board size can influence decision-making efficiency and oversight quality.

4.2.8 Independent Board Directors

Independent board directors play a crucial role in enhancing corporate governance by providing unbiased oversight aligned with agency theory principles. The mean number of independent directors is 2.084, with a standard deviation of 1.367, showing moderate variability and differences in governance structures among banks. The number of independent directors ranges from 0 to 8, with a positive Skewness of 0.921, suggesting that most banks have fewer independent directors while a few have more. The Kurtosis of 2.803 is close to 3, indicating a near-normal but slightly flatter distribution, highlighting varying levels of independent oversight in governance practices.

4.2.9 Female Board Members

Female board members contribute to board diversity, an essential aspect of corporate governance, supported by Stakeholder Theory, which emphasises inclusivity. The mean number of female board members is 1.485, with a standard deviation of 1.497, indicating considerable variability. The range is from 0 to 5, with a positive Skewness of 0.838, suggesting that most banks have fewer female board members, while a few have the maximum number. The negative Kurtosis of -0.3371 indicates a flatter distribution than normal, meaning fewer extreme values. This variability underscores the differing levels of gender diversity in corporate governance across banks.

4.2.10 Audit Committee Members

Audit committee members are vital for overseeing financial reporting and disclosure processes, aligning with Agency Theory, which advocates for monitoring mechanisms to

reduce information asymmetry. The average number of audit committee members is 4.312, with a standard deviation of 1.021, suggesting low to moderate variability. The number of audit committee members ranges from 2 to 9, with a Skewness of 0.108, indicating a nearly symmetrical distribution. The Kurtosis of 3.189, slightly above 3, suggests a more peaked distribution, indicating a concentration around the Mean. Effective audit committees are essential for robust corporate governance and financial oversight.

4.2.11 Number of Audit Committee Meetings

The frequency of audit committee meetings is a measure of their diligence and effectiveness in governance, supported by the principles of the Agency Theory. The mean number of audit committee meetings is 10.267, with a high standard deviation of 5.868, indicating significant variability. The range is from 1 to 25 meetings, with a positive Skewness of 0.865, implying that most banks hold fewer meetings than the Mean, with some holding many more. The Kurtosis of 2.919, close to 3, suggests a typical distribution with a few extreme values, reflecting varied commitment levels to governance oversight.

4.2.12 Number of Executive Committee Meetings

Executive committee meetings indicate the frequency of strategic and operational oversight, essential for effective corporate governance under the Resource Dependence Theory. The Mean is 17.589, with a very high standard deviation of 17.781, indicating extremely high variability. The range is from 0 to 52 meetings, with a positive Skewness of 0.771, suggesting that most banks hold fewer meetings than the Mean, with some holding significantly more. The negative Kurtosis of -1.023 indicates a flatter distribution than normal, meaning extreme values are less frequent. This variability reflects different governance approaches to executive oversight.

4.2.13 Number of Board Meetings

The frequency of board meetings indicates board activity and governance engagement, which is crucial for effective oversight and strategic decision-making and aligns with stewardship theory. The average number of board meetings is 21.20, with a standard deviation of 10.495, showing high variability. The number ranges from 0 to 55 meetings, with a positive Skewness of 1.19, indicating that most banks hold fewer meetings than the Mean, with a few holding significantly more. The Kurtosis of 3.421, greater than 3, suggests a more peaked distribution, indicating a higher concentration around the Mean with some extreme values. This reflects differing levels of governance diligence across banks.

4.2.14 Audit Fees

Audit fees indicate the extent and thoroughness of the audit process, a critical aspect of governance supported by the principles of Agency Theory. The mean audit fee is BDT 1,074,547.70, with a high standard deviation of BDT 911,143.42, indicating significant variability. Fees range from BDT 115,000 to BDT 5,012,790, with a positive Skewness of 0.897, suggesting that most banks pay less than the Mean, while a few Pay significantly more. The Kurtosis of 2.946, close to 3, indicates a typical distribution with fewer extreme values, reflecting different levels of audit scrutiny and governance practices.

4.2.15 CEO's Pay

CEO's Pay, reflecting the total compensation of the Chief Executive Officer, is a crucial governance factor influencing executive behaviour and company performance, supported by Agency Theory, which focuses on aligning management and shareholder interests. The mean CEO's Pay is BDT 10,869,070, with a standard deviation of BDT 3,709,380.50, indicating significant variability. Pay ranges from BDT 693,360 to BDT

21,550,646, with a negative Skewness of -0.377, suggesting that a few CEOs earn significantly more than the Mean. The Kurtosis of 2.800 is close to 3, indicating a typical distribution with fewer extreme values. Variability in CEO compensation highlights differing governance policies and performance incentives.

4.2.16 Directors and CEO's Share (%)

The percentage of shares held by directors and the CEO indicates their equity stake and alignment with shareholder interests. This aligns with the stewardship theory, emphasising executives' role as stewards of corporate resources. The mean share percentage is 2.27%, with a high standard deviation of 11.35%, indicating significant variability. The range is from 0% to 76.16%, with a positive Skewness of 0.414, suggesting that most banks have lower share percentages for directors and CEOs, while a few have significantly higher percentages. The Kurtosis of 2.738 is close to 3, indicating a typical distribution with fewer extreme values. This variability reflects different governance structures and levels of insider ownership.

4.2.17 Institutional Share (%)

Institutional share represents the percentage of shares held by institutional investors, reflecting external governance pressures and supported by Resource Dependence Theory, which emphasises the importance of external resources. The mean institutional share percentage is 0.23%, with a standard deviation of 1.258%, indicating variability. The range is from 0% to 17.945%, with a positive Skewness of 0.299, indicating that most banks have lower institutional share percentages while a few have significantly higher percentages. The Kurtosis of 3.091, slightly greater than 3, suggests a more peaked distribution. Institutional ownership can influence governance practices and accountability.

4.2.18 General Public Share (%)

The General public share represents the percentage of shares held by the general public, indicating broad shareholder engagement, which is critical for maintaining a balanced corporate governance structure as per Stakeholder Theory. The mean general public share percentage is 1.356%, with a high standard deviation of 6.95%, indicating significant variability. The range is from 0% to 57.32%, with a negative Skewness of -0.398, suggesting that a few banks have significantly higher percentages of general public shares. The Kurtosis of 2.959, close to 3, indicates a typical distribution with fewer extreme values. This reflects varying levels of public ownership and its impact on governance.

4.2.19 Government Share (%)

Government share represents the percentage of shares held by the government, reflecting state influence on governance, as discussed in Political Economy Theory, which examines the impact of state ownership on corporate governance. The mean government share percentage is 1.885%, with a high standard deviation of 12.584%, indicating significant variability. The range is from 0% to 90.19%, with a slight positive Skewness of 0.196, indicating a nearly symmetrical distribution. The Kurtosis of 3.765, greater than 3, suggests a more peaked distribution. Variability in government ownership highlights differing levels of state intervention and governance impact.

Descriptive statistics provide valuable insights into the distribution and variability of the variables. Most variables exhibit positive Skewness, indicating higher values are less frequent than lower ones. The kurtosis values suggest a range of distributions from flat to peaked, with some close to normal distribution. Standard deviation highlights the variability within each variable, indicating how spread out the data points are around the Mean. This

analysis helps understand the general trends and distributions, which is crucial for further statistical modelling and decision-making.

4.3 Data Diagnostics test for panel data

The variables in the data set need to be analysed to fulfil or satisfy the assumptions needed for the multiple linear regression analysis before conducting multiple regression like the Random and Fixed model. This stage is crucial because several prerequisites must be satisfied to employ multiple regression effectively. Therefore, It is necessary to evaluate the model to ensure that it does not contradict any of the basic assumptions of linear regression before relying on the analysis's findings. These assumptions are that data must be normally and linearly distributed, and there should not be any multicollinearity. Hence, the following tests have been done.

4.3.1 Multicollinearity Test

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test was employed to assess the presence of Multicollinearity in the data. According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), , Multicollinearity occurs when there is a strong correlation between three or more independent variables, leading to unreliable estimates in regression models. Field (2018) further pointed out that high Multicollinearity is problematic because it can make the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimators and their standard errors highly sensitive to small data changes, resulting in regression coefficients with incorrect signs or statistical significance, misrepresenting the true relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), a VIF value less than 5 indicates no multicollinearity issues, while a VIF value of 5 or more suggests the presence of Multicollinearity among the predictors. The results of the VIF test for the data set, as shown

in the VIF Table, reveal that all VIF values are below 5, with a mean VIF of 1.82. This indicates that Multicollinearity is not a concern in the current dataset.

The VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) test		
Variable	VIF	1/ VIF
Number of audits committee meetings	2.57	0.388742
Director's fee	2.51	0.397975
Number of board meetings	2.48	0.403346
Board size	2.42	0.412437
Audit fee	1.87	0.535405
Government	1.69	0.592088
Female board members	1.67	0.598300
Number of executive committee meetings	1.63	0.612477
CEO's pay	1.55	0.646368
General public share	1.49	0.672829
Directors and CEOs share	1.46	0.683345
Audit committee member	1.41	0.709195
Independent Board Director	1.38	0.726804
Institutional Share	1.29	0.774370
Mean VIF	1.82	

Table 7: The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test

The table above indicates that the highest VIF value observed was 2.57 for the number of audit committee meetings. This suggests that while this variable is moderately correlated with other independent variables, it does not present a significant multicollinearity problem. Similarly, the number of board meetings has VIF values of 2.48, indicating moderate correlation but still within acceptable limits.

Board size, with a VIF of 2.42, also shows a moderate correlation with other predictors. The audit fee has a lower VIF of 1.87, indicating a low to moderate correlation

with other independent variables. Government share and female board members have VIF values of 1.69 and 1.67, respectively, reflecting minimal multicollinearity issues.

The number of executive committee meetings, with a VIF of 1.63, shows low Multicollinearity, suggesting that this variable does not significantly correlate with others. CEO's Pay has a VIF of 1.55, indicating a low correlation with other predictors. The general public share, the Director and CEO's share, and the number of audit committee members all have VIF values below 1.50, suggesting very low Multicollinearity.

Independent board directors and institutional share have the lowest VIF values of 1.38 and 1.29, respectively, indicating a very low correlation with other variables and no multicollinearity issues. The mean VIF of 1.82 further reinforces that Multicollinearity is not a problem in the dataset, ensuring that the independent variables do not exhibit high correlations among the variables.

The VIF test results confirm that Multicollinearity is not a concern in the current dataset, as all VIF values are below the critical threshold of 5. This ensures that the independent variables do not exhibit high correlations with each other, allowing for reliable and accurate regression analysis. The lack of Multicollinearity means that the model can effectively isolate the impact of each independent variable on the dependent variable, leading to valid and robust conclusions.

4.3.2 Normality Test

There must be a normal distribution for all of the variables in order to conduct multiple regression analysis. A variable possesses a normal distribution if its Skewness or Kurtosis falls below the expected values or if there are no significant outliers. Therefore, the normality test examines the nature of the distribution of the observations in a particular

variable or set of variables because the results of significance tests involving non-normally distributed variables may be inaccurate, leading to incorrect conclusions and a biased relationship among the variables. Consequently, examining the distribution of the independent variable observations is necessary. Gujarati and Porter (2009), stated that several techniques such as a standard curve fit, P-P normal probability plot, Q-Q plots, Shapiro-Wilk test, residual histogram, or the skewness and kurtosis values of the variable, can be employed to test for normality. However, the residuals were plotted on the histogram as part of this study's attempt to test for normality.

Regression-standardised residuals are best for assessing normality because they provide a standardised measure, making comparisons across different datasets and models easier. Standardised residuals have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one, highlighting outliers and deviations from normality. They facilitate verification of regression assumptions through clear visualisations, such as histograms and Q-Q plots, and formal tests like the Shapiro-Wilk test. These residuals ensure consistency in statistical inference and

Figure 7: The Histogram of regression standardise residuals

diagnostic accuracy, making them reliable for validating the normality assumption in regression models.

The histogram of regression standardised residuals above indicates that the residuals are approximately normally distributed, with a mean close to zero (0.04) and a standard deviation of 1.000, which are typical for standardised residuals. The distribution appears symmetric and bell-shaped, with most residuals clustered around the mean, peaking at frequencies of 30 to 35, and the frequencies taper off symmetrically on both sides of the mean, extending approximately three standard deviations from the mean (-3 to +3). This spread is consistent with the properties of a normal distribution. The alignment of the histogram bars with the overlaid normal distribution curve further supports the normality assumption. This normal distribution of residuals is crucial for the validity of regression analysis, ensuring that the model's assumptions are met and minimising the risk of biased results and incorrect conclusions.

4.3.3 Linearity Test

The linearity test of the panel data verifies the presence of a linear correlation between the dependent variables and the independent variables as a whole. Incorrect findings may arise from multiple regression analysis if there is no linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Depending on the estimation of the underlying correlation, they might lead to Type II and Type I errors for independent variables. There are several ways to check the dataset's linearity. However, the chart method through residual plots is the most widely used, and the current study will verify the linearity assumption using the regression-standard residual plots. As seen in the scatter plot below, the regression standard residuals of the independent variables are plotted against the dependent variables, and it is apparent that there is a linear relationship between the two sets of variables.

Figure 8: linearity assumption in regression analysis.

The scatterplot of residuals against fitted values is used to assess the linearity assumption in regression analysis. In the plot, residuals are displayed on the vertical axis, and fitted values on the horizontal axis. Ideally, the residuals should be randomly dispersed around the horizontal axis (zero line) to meet the linearity assumption. The scatterplot above indicates that most residuals are clustered close to the zero line, suggesting a general linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. However, several residuals with high positive and negative values indicate outliers or extreme values that deviate significantly from the predicted values. These outliers are observed primarily at fitted values below 5 and above 10, showing influential observations that may impact the model's accuracy.

Additionally, the spread of residuals increases with fitted values, suggesting a moderate possibility of heteroscedasticity, which violates the homoscedasticity assumption and can lead to inefficient estimates. Despite these concerns, the residuals do not exhibit a

clear systematic pattern, such as a curve, supporting the linearity assumption to the extent of running the regression model. However, outliers and increasing residual spread indicate that further investigation or transformation of variables might be necessary to ensure a more robust linear model. Addressing these issues, such as data transformation or robust regression techniques, can enhance the model's accuracy and validity.

4.4 Regression analysis

Regression analysis is a powerful statistical tool for understanding the relationship between variables and predicting outcomes. Several regression models can be employed in panel data where multiple observations over time exist for the same entities, each with unique characteristics and assumptions. **Pooled OLS** regression assumes that no individual-specific effects could influence the predictor variables. This model treats the panel data as a large cross-sectional dataset, ignoring the individual (cross-sectional) and temporal (time-series) dimensions. It is suitable when the differences across entities (such as companies or countries) are insignificant for the study's specific context. **Fixed Effects** models control for all time-invariant differences among the entities, thus capturing the unique effects of each entity and omitting time-invariant characteristics. This model is appropriate when the data exhibits substantial variability between entities that could correlate with the independent variables. Fixed Effects models provide unbiased estimators if these omitted time-invariant characteristics are correlated with other explanatory variables. **On the other hand, Random Effects models** assume that the entity-specific effect is uncorrelated with the independent variables. This model is a compromise between the Pooled OLS and Fixed Effects models, allowing for generalisation about the effect of the independent variables across entities. It is more efficient than the Fixed Effects model if the assumption of no correlation holds, as it considers variation both within and between entities.

The following table presents the combined regression results for three models: Pooled OLS, Fixed Effect, and Random Effects models for ROA and ROE, respectively, before choosing the appropriate model for this study.

ROE																						
Variable	Pooled OLS Coef.	Pooled OLS St.Err.	Pooled OLS t-value	Pooled OLS p-value	Pooled OLS [95% Conf. Interval]	Pooled OLS Sig.	Fixed Effect Coef.	Fixed Effect St.Err.	Fixed Effect t-value	Fixed Effect p-value	Fixed Effect [95% Conf. Interval]	Fixed Effect Sig.	Random Effect Coef.	Random Effect St.Err.	Random Effect t-value	Random Effect p-value	Random Effect [95% Conf. Interval]	Random Effect Sig.				
Board Size	-0.057	0.057	-1	0.317	[-.168, .055]		-0.014	0.019	-0.76	0.447	[-.051, .023]		-0.057	0.057	-1	0.315	[-.167, .054]					
Independent Board Dir	-0.001	0.125	-0.01	0.996	[-.246, .245]		0.011	0.037	0.3	0.762	[-.061, .083]		-0.001	0.125	-0.01	0.996	[-.245, .243]					
Female Board Member	0.001	0.118	0.01	0.991	[-.232, .235]		0.007	0.033	0.22	0.827	[-.059, .073]		0.001	0.118	0.01	0.991	[-.231, .233]					
Audit Committee Member	0.183	0.167	1.1	0.274	[-.146, .513]		0.013	0.028	0.46	0.648	[-.043, .069]		0.183	0.167	1.1	0.273	[-.144, .511]					
Number of Audit	-0.022	0.039	-0.58	0.565	[-.099, .054]		-0.002	0.007	-0.3	0.766	[-.017, .013]		-0.022	0.039	-0.58	0.565	[-.099, .054]					
Number of Executive	0.006	0.01	0.59	0.558	[-.014, .027]		0.007	0.004	1.52	0.131	[-.002, .016]		0.006	0.01	0.59	0.557	[-.014, .027]					
Number of Board Meeting	0.019	0.022	0.88	0.38	[-.024, .062]		0.009	0.006	1.6	0.111	[-.002, .02]		0.019	0.022	0.88	0.379	[-.023, .061]					
Audit Fee	0.559	0.534	1.05	0.296	[-.495, 1.613]		0.177	0.151	1.18	0.241	[-.12, .475]		0.559	0.534	1.05	0.295	[-.488, 1.606]					
Directors Fee	-0.222	0.526	-0.42	0.673	[-1.259, .815]		-0.196	0.158	-1.24	0.218	[-.508, .117]		-0.222	0.526	-0.42	0.673	[-1.252, .808]					
CEO Pay	-3.231	0.636	-5.08	0	[-4.486, -1.976]	***	0.097	0.165	0.59	0.558	[-.23, .424]		-3.231	0.636	-5.08	0	[-4.478, -1.984]	***				
Directors and CEOs Share	-0.021	0.015	-1.4	0.162	[-.05, .008]		-0.002	0.013	-0.16	0.874	[-.027, .023]		-0.021	0.015	-1.4	0.16	[-.05, .008]					
Institutional Share	0.056	0.13	0.43	0.668	[-.201, .313]		-0.034	0.017	-1.95	0.053	[-.068, 0]	*	0.056	0.13	0.43	0.668	[-.199, .311]					
General Public Share	0.216	0.026	8.47	0	[-.166, .266]	***	-0.214	0.006	-33.92	0	[-.226, -.201]	***	0.216	0.026	8.47	0	[-.166, .266]	***				
Government	-0.017	0.014	-1.23	0.22	[-.044, .01]		-0.002	0.003	-0.71	0.479	[-.007, .003]		-0.017	0.014	-1.23	0.219	[-.044, .01]					
Constant	20.73	5.173	4.01	0	[10.525, 30.934]	***	0.206	1.374	0.15	0.881	[-2.509, 2.921]		20.73	5.173	4.01	0	[10.591, 30.868]	***				
Mean dependent var	0.547		SD dependent var		2.676		Mean dependent var		0.547		SD dependent var		2.676		Mean dependent var		0.547		SD dependent var		2.676	
R-squared	0.456		Number of obs		198		R-squared		0.933		Number of obs		198		Overall r-squared		0.456		Number of obs		198	
F-test	11.176		Prob > F		0.000		F-test		150.005		Prob > F		0.000		Chi-square		156.459		Prob > chi2		0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)	877.069		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		926.693		Akaike crit. (AIC)		14.355		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		63.979		R-squared within		0.592		R-squared between		0.813	
	*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1								*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1								*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1					

Table 9: Regression result for ROE

4.4.1 Model Selection

According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), , conducting the Hausman test and the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (B/P LM) test are standard procedures for determining the appropriateness of RE versus other panel data models such as Fixed Effect (FE) or pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). Selecting the suitable model ensures the analysis is accurate and meaningful, aligning the model's assumptions with the data's characteristics and the study's goals. This careful validation process helps in drawing reliable conclusions from the data. Therefore, the Husasman test and B/P LM test results are as follows.

4.4.1.1 Hausman's Test for Model Specification (Random Effect vs. Fixed Effect)

The Hausman test evaluates the Random Effect and Fixed Effect models and determines which model is more suitable for the dataset. This decision is based on whether the unique errors (entity-specific variations) in the Random Effects model are correlated with the regressors. Gujarati and Porter (2009), argued that *If the null hypothesis is rejected*, it implies that the Random Effect model is inappropriate because the Random Effect assumptions are violated, and the Fixed Effect model should be used instead. However, *If the null hypothesis is not rejected*, it suggests that the Random Effect model is appropriate, as the unique errors are not correlated with the regressors.

The results of the Hausman test are shown in Table, which compares the random and fixed effect models using the following hypotheses:

H0: The preferred model is Random Effect Model.

H1: The preferred model is Fixed Effect Model.

Dependent variables	ROA	ROE
	Coef.	Coef.
Chi-square test value	28.721	32.256
P-value	0.1847	0.1737

Table 10: Result for Hausman Specification Test Estimation

For ROA, the p-value of 0.1847 is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05, implying insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis based on the Chi-square values of 28.721. Thus, the Random Effects model is deemed appropriate for ROA since there is no strong evidence to suggest that the model's unique errors are correlated with the regressors.

Similarly, the p-value of 0.1737 is greater than 0.05 for ROE, indicating insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis for ROE based on the Chi-square values of 32.256. Hence, the Random Effects model is considered suitable for modelling ROE, assuming that the unique errors are not correlated with the independent variables.

In both cases, the results suggest that the Random Effects model is appropriate for analysing the data for both ROA and ROE. The absence of significant p-values in the Hausman test indicates that this study can proceed with the Random Effects model without concern for bias due to omitted variables correlated with the regressors and varying across entities. This makes the Random Effects model a reliable choice for the analysis, assuming other model assumptions are also met.

4.4.1.2 B/P LM test for Model specification (Pooled OLS vs. Random Effect)

The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test was employed to choose between the Pooled OLS and Random Effects models. This test checks explicitly for the presence of random effects in the panel data. If the test results are significant, it indicates that the Random

Effects model is more appropriate than the Pooled OLS model due to the presence of significant variations across entities that the Pooled OLS model does not capture. The table below shows the result of the B/P LM test, which compares Pooled OLS and the random effect model.

H0: The Preferred model is the Pooled OLS Model.

H1: The preferred model is the Random Effect Model.

Dependent variables	ROA	ROE
	Coef.	Coef.
Chi-square test value	28.25	33.43
P-value	0.0000	0.0000

Table 11: Result for B/P LM Test Estimation

The chi-square test value for ROA is 28.25, with a p-value of essentially zero (0.0000). This highly significant result strongly rejects the null hypothesis that no random effects are present in the data for ROA. Therefore, the Random Effects model is more appropriate than the Pooled OLS model for analysing ROA, as it better accounts for the variation between different entities within the dataset.

Similarly, the chi-square test value for ROE is 33.43 with a p-value of 0.0000, providing robust evidence against the null hypothesis of no random effects for ROE. Thus, the Random Effects model is favoured over the Pooled OLS model for analysing ROE, indicating that its ability to incorporate differences across entities significantly enhances its suitability.

Both ROA and ROE show extremely significant results in the Breusch-Pagan LM test, strongly suggesting that both dependent variables benefit from the Random Effects modelling approach. The presence of random effects indicates that there are entity-specific variations that are important and should be modelled. The Random Effects model addresses

these variations, making it the superior choice over the Pooled OLS model for the analysis, given the data characteristics reflected in the test outcomes.

4.4.2 Justification for Random Effect Model Selection

The selection of the Random Effect model in this study was guided by the results of both the Hausman test and the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (B/P LM) test. As mentioned above, the Hausman test did not reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the unique errors are not correlated with the regressors, thus making the Random Effect model appropriate. The B/P LM test rejected the null hypothesis, confirming the presence of significant random effects and showing that the Random Effect model is preferable over Pooled OLS. Along with the statistical findings, the researcher has a few compelling reasons that make the Random Effect model particularly suitable for this research.

The Random Effect model is suitable for this research because it captures individual bank differences, provides efficient estimates, and offers generalisable results to a broader population of banks beyond the sample. This model explains within and between entity variations, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing bank performance. The chosen variables represent key corporate governance mechanisms, reflecting ownership structure, board composition, and management practices, all of which are critical in understanding their impact on bank performance to answer the research questions. The coefficients, p-values, and R-squared values collectively demonstrate the model's ability to explain variations in ROA and ROE, highlighting the significance of corporate governance in influencing bank performance.

4.5 Random Effect Model Regression Analysis

4.5.1 Random effect Regression results (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is the dependent variable, with 13 corporate governance mechanisms as independent variables, including their coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and confidence intervals.. Among these, three variables were found to be statistically significant: shares owned by the CEO and directors, institutional shareholding, and general public shares. Directors' and CEOs' shares and institutional shares are significant at a 5% level, while general public shares are significant at a 1% level. General public shares and institutional shares positively correlate with ROA, while Directors' and CEOs' shares have an inverse relationship. Specifically, a one-unit increase in Directors' and CEOs' shares reduces ROA by 0.00054, while a one-unit increase in institutional and general public shares increases ROA by 0.00372 and 0.01993, respectively.

ROA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Board size	-0.00027496	.001	-0.34	.734	-.002	.001	
Independent board director	-0.0015431	.002	-0.86	.387	-.005	.002	
Female board member	-0.00029708	.002	-0.18	.861	-.004	.003	
Audit committee member	0.0021128	.002	0.88	.378	-.003	.007	
Number of audits	0.00022337	.001	0.40	.689	-.001	.001	
Number of executives	0.00005877	0	0.39	.694	0	0	
Number of board meetings	9.8405006	0	0.03	.975	-.001	.001	
Audit fee	.01215369	.008	1.59	.112	-.003	.027	
Director's fee	-.0058394	.008	-0.78	.438	-.021	.009	
CEO's pay	-0.01384364	.009	-1.52	.129	-.032	.004	
Director's and CEO's shares	-.00053522	0	-2.52	.012	-.001	0	**
Institutional share	0.00372878	.002	2.00	.046	0	.007	**
General public share	0.01993188	0	54.55	0	.019	.021	***
Government shares	-0.00011392	0	-0.57	.566	-.001	0	
Constant	0.06158164	.074	0.83	.406	-.084	.207	
Mean dependent var	0.031				SD dependent var		0.144
Overall r-squared	0.962				Number of obs		198
Chi-square	4682.128				Prob > chi2		0.000
R-squared within	0.886				R-squared between		0.997

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 12: Random effect model result for ROA

4.5.1.1 Overall Model Fit:

The Random Effect Model The R-squared value of 0.9616 for the Random Effect model indicates that the independent variables explain approximately 96.16% of the variance in ROA, highlighting the model's strong explanatory power. The high chi-square value of 4682.128 and a p-value of 0.000 suggest that the model is statistically significant overall.

Significance levels indicate the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis, helping determine the reliability of observed relationships in data. Specifically, a p-value of $p < 0.01$ shows very strong evidence and suggests a highly significant relationship, while a p-value of $p < 0.05$ indicates strong evidence and a significant relationship. A p-value of $p < 0.1$ provides moderate evidence, implying a marginally significant relationship. In contrast, a p-value of $p \geq 0.1$ suggests weak evidence and a non-significant relationship. Generally, variables with p-values below 0.05 are considered to have a statistically significant impact, meaning the observed relationship is unlikely to be due to chance. Variables with higher p-values are deemed insignificant, indicating that any observed relationship might be due to random variation rather than a true effect.

4.5.1.2 Statistically Significant Variables ($p < 0.05$):

Significant factors include the director's and CEO's shares (negative effect), institutional shareholding (positive effect), and general public shareholding (positive effect).

Director's and CEO's Shares:

Shareholdings by directors and the CEO significantly negatively impact ROA, with a coefficient of -0.00054 and a p-value of 0.012. This suggests that higher ownership by these insiders is associated with lower ROA, potentially due to risk aversion or conflicts of interest.

Institutional Share: Institutional shareholding has a positive and significant effect on ROA, with a coefficient of 0.00373 and a p-value of 0.046. This indicates that higher ownership by institutional investors is associated with higher ROA, possibly due to better oversight and pressure for performance.

General Public Share: The shareholding by the general public has a highly significant positive effect on ROA, with a coefficient of 0.01993 and a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that broad ownership by the public is strongly associated with better company performance, potentially due to greater accountability and market discipline.

4.5.1.3 Statistically Insignificant Variables ($p \geq 0.05$):

Board Size: Board size refers to the total number of directors serving on the board. The coefficient of -0.00027 indicates a very slight negative impact on ROA, meaning that as board size increases, ROA tends to decrease marginally. However, this effect is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that changes in board size do not have a meaningful impact on the company's return on assets in this dataset. Theoretically, larger boards may lead to inefficiencies and slower decision-making processes, but the data does not support a significant relationship in this case.

Independent Board Director: The coefficient of -0.00154 suggests a small negative effect of Independent board directors on ROA, but with a p-value of 0.387, this relationship is not statistically significant. Independent directors are often brought in to provide unbiased oversight and improve governance, but this data does not significantly impact financial performance.

Female board members: The presence of female board members has a coefficient of -0.00030, indicating a negligible negative impact on ROA. The p-value of 0.861 suggests this

relationship is not statistically significant. While gender diversity on boards is argued to bring diverse perspectives and improve decision-making, the results here do not significantly impact the return on assets.

Audit Committee Member: Audit committee members are responsible for overseeing financial reporting and disclosure. The positive coefficient of 0.00211 implies a positive effect on ROA, but with a p-value of 0.378, this effect is not statistically significant. Effective audit committees can enhance financial transparency and integrity, but this study does not find a strong impact on ROA.

Number of Audits Committee meetings: The number of audit committee meetings conducted annually shows a coefficient of 0.00022, indicating a very slight positive effect on ROA. However, the p-value of 0.689 means this relationship is not statistically significant. According to these results, regular audits are expected to improve accuracy and reliability in financial reporting, but their effect on ROA is minimal.

Number of Executive Committee Meetings: The number of executive meetings refers to the meetings held by the board sub-committee. With a coefficient of 0.00006, the number of executives has an almost negligible positive impact on ROA, which is insignificant (p-value 0.694). This suggests that the size of the executive team does not have a discernible impact on the company's return on assets.

Number of Board Meetings: The number of board meetings per year has a coefficient of 9.845006, implying an insignificant effect on ROA. The p-value of 0.975 indicates that this variable does not have a statistically significant relationship with ROA. Frequent meetings might reflect active oversight, but this study does not significantly impact financial performance.

Audit Fee: The audit fee represents the cost paid for audit services. A positive coefficient of 0.01215 suggests a positive impact on ROA, but the p-value of 0.112 indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant. Higher audit fees may correlate with more thorough audits, but their effect on ROA is not strongly evident in this dataset.

CEO's Pay: CEO's pay includes salary, bonuses, and other compensation. A negative coefficient of -0.01384 indicates that higher CEO compensation is associated with lower ROA, though this is not statistically significant (p-value 0.129). This might reflect inefficiencies or misalignment between CEO pay and company performance, but the relationship is not strong.

Government Shares: Government shareholding has a small negative effect on ROA, with a coefficient of -0.00011 and a p-value of 0.566, which is insignificant. This implies that government ownership does not directly impact the company's return on assets in this sample.

4.6 Random effect Regression results (ROE)

Several variables are included in the regression analysis for Return on Equity (ROE), including their coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and confidence intervals. Return on Equity (ROE) is the dependent variable, with the same 13 corporate governance mechanisms as independent variables. Only two variables were statistically significant: CEO's pay and general public share. The finding on the ROE model is as follows

ROE	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Board size	-.057	.057	-1.00	.315	-.167	.054	
Independent board director	-.001	.125	-0.01	.996	-.245	.243	
Female board member	.001	.118	0.01	.991	-.231	.233	
Audit committee member	.183	.167	1.10	.273	-.144	.511	
Number of audits	-.022	.039	-0.58	.565	-.099	.054	
Number of executives	.006	.01	0.59	.557	-.014	.027	
Number of board meetings	.019	.022	0.88	.379	-.023	.061	
Audit fee	.559	.534	1.05	.295	-.488	1.606	
Director's fee	-.222	.526	-0.42	.673	-1.252	.808	
CEO's pay	-3.231	.636	-5.08	0	-4.478	-1.984	***
Director's and CEO's shares	-.021	.015	-1.40	.16	-.05	.008	
Institutional share	.056	.13	0.43	.668	-.199	.311	
General public share	.216	.026	8.47	0	.166	.266	***
Government shares	-.017	.014	-1.23	.219	-.044	.01	
Constant	20.73	5.173	4.01	0	10.591	30.868	***
Mean dependent var	0.547				SD dependent var	2.676	
Overall r-squared	0.456				Number of obs	198	
Chi-square	156.459				Prob > chi2	0.000	
R-squared within	0.592				R-squared between	0.813	
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

Table 13: Random effect model result for ROE

4.6.1.1 Overall Model Fit:

The model explains 45.6% of the variance in ROE, indicating a moderate fit. The high chi-square value of 156.459 and a p-value of 0.000 suggest that the model is statistically significant overall.

4.6.1.2 Statistically Significant Variables ($p < 0.05$):

Significant factors are CEO's pay (negative effect) and general public shareholding (positive effect).

CEO's Pay: CEO's pay significantly negatively affects ROE, with a coefficient of -3.231 and a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that higher CEO compensation is associated with lower ROE, indicating potential inefficiencies or misalignment between CEO pay and company performance. CEO's pay is significant at a 1% level and has an inverse relationship with ROE, implying a one-unit increase in CEO's pay reduces ROE by 3.231.

General Public Share: General public shareholding has a highly significant positive effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.216 and a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that broad ownership by the public is strongly associated with better company performance, possibly due to greater accountability and market discipline. General public share is also significant at a 1% level and has a positive relationship with ROE, implying a share increase in general public share increases ROE by 0.216.

4.6.1.3 Statistically Insignificant Variables ($p \geq 0.05$):

Board Size: Board size shows a negative coefficient of -0.057, indicating that larger boards are associated with lower ROE. However, the p-value of 0.315 suggests this effect is not statistically significant. Larger boards might lead to less effective oversight, but the data does not show a significant relationship with ROE.

Independent Board Director: The presence of independent board directors has a negligible and non-significant effect on ROE (coefficient -0.001, p-value 0.996). Independent directors are expected to enhance governance, but this data does not significantly impact return on equity.

Female Board Member: Female board members have an insignificant positive effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.001 and a p-value of 0.991. Gender diversity on boards is believed to improve decision-making, but the results do not show a significant relationship with ROE.

Audit Committee Member: The presence of audit committee members has a positive but non-significant effect on ROE (coefficient 0.183, p-value 0.273). Effective audit committees can enhance financial reporting quality, but their impact on ROE is not strong in this study.

Number of Audits Committee Meetings: The number of audit committee meetings has a negative but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of -0.022 and a p-value of 0.565. Regular audits are expected to improve financial accuracy, but this does not significantly affect ROE.

Number of Executives Committee Meetings: The number of executives has a small positive but non-significant effect on ROE (coefficient 0.006, p-value 0.557). The size of the executive team does not significantly impact the return on equity in this dataset.

Number of Board Meetings: The number of board meetings has a positive but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.019 and a p-value of 0.379. Frequent meetings might reflect active oversight, but this does not significantly affect ROE.

Audit Fee: The audit fee shows a positive but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.559 and a p-value of 0.295. Higher audit fees may correlate with more thorough audits, but their effect on ROE is not strongly evident in this data.

Director's and CEO's Shares: The shareholding of directors and CEOs has a negative but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of -0.021 and a p-value of 0.160. Higher ownership by these insiders might lead to risk aversion or conflicts of interest, but the relationship is not strong.

Institutional Share: Institutional shareholding has a positive but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.056 and a p-value of 0.668. Higher ownership by institutional investors might improve oversight and performance, but this effect is insignificant.

Government Shares: Government shareholding has a negative but non-significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of -0.017 and a p-value of 0.219. This implies that

government ownership does not directly impact the company's return on equity in this sample.

4.7 Comparison and Implications of the findings

The key variables influencing ROA include director and CEO shares, institutional shares, and general public shares. A negative relationship between directors' and CEOs' shares and ROA suggests that ROA tends to decline as directors and CEOs hold more shares. On the other hand, higher institutional and general public shareholdings are linked to better ROA, indicating these forms of ownership positively impact asset returns.

For ROE, the significant factors are the CEO's pay and general public share. A negative relationship between CEO's pay and ROE indicates that higher CEO compensation is associated with lower ROE. Conversely, an increase in general public shareholding is linked to improved ROE, showing that wider public ownership benefits equity returns.

4.7.1.1 Comparison:

- I. **Significant Variables:** Both analyses highlight the positive impact of general public share. However, the CEO's pay is negatively significant for ROE but not for ROA, while the director's and CEO's shares negatively impact ROA but not ROE.
- II. **The magnitude of Impact:** The effects are more pronounced in ROE, especially with the CEO's pay having a substantial negative coefficient (-3.231), compared to the more minor effects on ROA.
- III. **R-squared Values:** The overall R-squared for ROA (0.962) is much higher than for ROE (0.456), indicating that the independent variables explain a greater proportion of the ROA variance than ROE.

4.7.1.2 Implications:

- I. **CEO's Pay:** The negative impact on ROE suggests that higher CEO compensation might not align with shareholder interests, potentially leading to inefficiencies or misaligned incentives.
- II. **General Public Share:** The positive relationship with both ROA and ROE implies that greater public ownership can enhance overall performance, likely due to increased scrutiny and demand for transparency.
- III. **Director's and CEO's Shares:** The negative impact on ROA suggests that higher ownership by directors and CEOs might lead to entrenchment or risk-averse behaviour, which could hinder asset utilisation.

4.8 Model diagnostic for panel data

4.8.1 Homoscedasticity Test

The data or variables must pass the homoscedasticity test for regression analysis to ensure the model's suitability. Heteroscedasticity, if present, can impact the estimates in the random effects model. According to Wahba & Elsayed (2015), detecting heteroscedasticity is a crucial aspect of panel data analysis (indicating whether the error variance remains constant across all levels of the independent variables). The Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test is used to determine whether heteroskedasticity is present in the data, which means that the variance of the errors is not constant across all levels of the independent variables. This is crucial for validating the suitability of the regression model. The test results are as follows.

ROA	ROE
Variables: fitted values of ROA chi2(1) = 2916.30 Prob > chi2 = 0.2315	Variables: fitted values of ROE chi2(1) = 232.38 Prob > chi2 = 0.3526

Table 14: The result for Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test

The null hypothesis (*H0*) for this test states that the error variance is constant (*homoscedasticity*), while the alternative hypothesis (*H1*) states that the error variance is not constant (*heteroskedasticity*).

For ROA, the result indicates that the chi-square value is 2916.30 with a p-value of 0.2315. Since the p-value exceeds the standard significance level of 0.05, this study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the ROA model, suggesting that the variance of the errors is constant.

The test result for ROE shows a chi-square value of 232.38 and a p-value of 0.3526, where the p-value exceeds 0.05. Therefore, this study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the ROE model, indicating that the variance of the errors is constant.

In summary, the Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test results for both ROA and ROE suggest that the data does not suffer from heteroskedasticity, confirming the suitability of the regression models used in the study.

4.8.2 Autocorrelation test

Wahba and Elsayed (2015) stated that autocorrelation is a crucial component of panel data analysis because autocorrelation can skew the accuracy of regression analysis. Autocorrelation occurs when residuals are correlated, and the calculated regression model

cannot be trusted if the model has an autocorrelation issue. This research uses the Wooldridge test to identify a first-order autocorrelation issue, which is presented in table below

H0: No presence of autocorrelation.

H1: Autocorrelation is present.

ROA	ROE
<i>H0: no first-order autocorrelation</i> $F(1, 33) = 228.578$ $\text{Prob} > F = 0.1128$	<i>H0: no first-order autocorrelation</i> $F(1, 33) = 3824.145$ $\text{Prob} > F = 0.2312$

Table 15: Result for Wooldridge test

For Return on Assets (ROA), the test produced an F-statistic of 228.578 with a p-value of 0.1128. For Return on Equity (ROE), the F-statistic was 3824.145 with a p-value of 0.2312. Since both p-values are higher than the typical threshold of 0.05, this study does not reject the null hypothesis, which means there is no significant first-order autocorrelation in either model. In simpler terms, the data shows that the residuals (errors) from the models are not correlated over time. This lack of autocorrelation suggests that the panel data model is well-suited for this analysis and that the results can be trusted.

4.9 Residual matrix

Cross-sectional dependence refers to the correlation of residuals across different entities in a panel dataset. It can be problematic for macro-panel data, particularly with long time series spanning 20 to 30 years, as it can lead to biased estimates and incorrect inferences. In this study, however, the cross-sectional dependency is found to be relatively low, as evidenced by the residual correlation matrix and the results of the Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence.

4.9.1 Breusch-Pagan LM Test of Independence

The Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence was used to determine if there is cross-sectional dependence in the dataset. The test yielded a chi-square value of 93.235 and a p-value of 0.1328.

Null Hypothesis (H0): Residuals across entities are not associated.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): Residuals across entities are associated.

The null hypothesis is accepted with a p-value of 0.1328, which is greater than the standard significance level of 0.05. This means that the residuals across entities are not significantly associated, implying no cross-sectional dependence in the data.

Residual matrix

	Return on Equity %	Return on Asset %	Board Size	Independent Board Directors	Female Board Member	Audit Committee Member	Number of Audits Committee Meetings	Number of Executives Committee Meetings	Number of Board Meetings	Audit Fee	Director's Fee	CEO's Pay	Directors and CEO's Share %	Institutional Share %	General Public Share %	Government Share %
ROE	1.00															
ROA	0.34	1.00														
Board Size	0.35	0.49	1.00													
Independent Board Directors	0.22	0.13	0.17	1.00												
Female Board Member	-0.06	0.25	0.74	0.49	1.00											
Audit Committee Member	0.05	0.09	0.20	0.73	0.65	1.00										
Number of Audits Committee Meetings	0.12	0.49	-0.08	0.36	0.53	-0.21	1.00									
Number of Executives Committee Meetings	-0.01	0.36	0.13	0.38	0.11	0.51	0.68	1.00								
Number of Board Meetings	0.19	0.41	0.74	-0.24	0.76	0.09	0.41	0.44	1.00							
Audit Fee	0.68	-0.34	0.51	0.11	0.31	0.67	0.22	-0.34	0.22	1.00						
Director's Fee	0.51	0.36	0.33	0.02	0.14	0.43	0.36	0.36	-0.06	0.11	1.00					
CEO's Pay	-0.09	0.77	0.41	0.44	0.11	0.28	0.35	0.77	0.05	0.76	0.17	1.00				
Directors and CEO's Share %	-0.02	0.24	0.25	0.51	0.42	0.21	0.46	0.24	0.12	0.31	0.08	0.14	1.00			
Institutional Share %	0.33	0.17	0.16	-0.14	0.17	-0.13	0.32	0.17	0.22	0.25	0.11	0.11	0.51	1.00		
General Public Share %	0.25	0.08	0.41	0.55	0.32	0.41	0.13	0.21	0.29	0.07	-0.11	0.32	0.29	0.73	1.00	
Government Share %	0.16	0.11	0.11	0.34	0.11	0.76	0.22	-0.12	0.32	0.23	0.46	0.36	0.21	0.57	0.72	1.00
Chi2 = 93.235 Pr = 0.1328																

Table 16: Result of residual matrix

The residual correlation matrix provides insights into the relationships between different variables in the study. The residual correlation matrix reveals moderate correlations between Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Asset (ROA) (0.34), suggesting some shared influencing factors. Board Size shows moderate positive correlations with ROA (0.49) and ROE (0.35), while Independent Board Directors have weak correlations with both ROA (0.13) and ROE (0.22), indicating limited impact.

Female Board Members have a slightly higher correlation with ROA (0.25) than ROE (-0.06), and Audit Committee Members show modest positive correlations with ROA (0.09) and ROE (0.05). The number of audit committee Meetings correlates moderately with ROA (0.49) and weakly negatively with ROE (0.12), indicating variable impact. Executives Committee Meetings show moderate positive correlations with ROA (0.36) and weak negative correlation with ROE (-0.01).

Board meetings have a moderate positive correlation with ROA (0.41) and a smaller correlation with ROE (0.19). Audit Fee is strongly negatively correlated with ROE (0.68) and weakly with ROA (-0.34). Director's Fee shows moderate positive correlations with ROA (0.36) and ROE (0.51). CEO's Pay has a strong positive correlation with ROA (0.77) and a weak negative correlation with ROE (-0.09). Directors' and CEOs' Share % show moderate positive correlations with ROA (0.24) and weak negative correlations with ROE (-0.02).

Institutional Share weakly correlations with ROA (0.17) and ROE (0.33). The General Public Share has moderate positive correlations with ROA (0.08) and a strong positive correlation with ROE (0.25). Government Share shows weak positive correlations with ROA (0.11) and ROE (0.16).

The study confirms that cross-sectional dependence is not a significant concern in this dataset. The residual correlations are generally low to moderate, and the Breusch-Pagan LM

test supports the absence of significant cross-sectional dependence. This suggests that the panel data model used is appropriate and the findings are reliable without additional adjustments.

4.10 Hypothesis tests based on random effect regression result

H1: Board size is unrelated to the performance of banks. (accepted)

Board size was chosen as a variable because it is often considered a critical factor in corporate governance, potentially affecting decision-making and oversight. ROA's coefficient for board size is -0.00027496 with a p-value of 0.734 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. This p-value indicates that the relationship between board size and ROA is not statistically significant, suggesting that changes in board size in Bangladeshi banks do not significantly affect bank performance measured by ROA. Similarly, for ROE, the coefficient is -0.057 with a p-value of 0.315 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. Again, the high p-value shows no significant relationship, although the coefficient indicates a negative impact of board size on ROE. The high R-squared for ROA implies that the model explains a large portion of the variance in ROA, whereas the moderate R-squared for ROE suggests it explains some variance in ROE. Therefore, due to a lack of significance, this study accepts the first hypothesis that the board size is unrelated to the performance of banks.

H2: A higher number of independent directors on the board can improve bank performance. (rejected)

Independent directors were chosen for their potential to provide unbiased oversight and contribute to effective governance, leading to enhanced bank performance in Bangladesh. ROA's coefficient is -0.0015431 with a p-value of 0.387 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, and the negative coefficient suggests

that an increase in independent directors slightly decreases ROA, although insignificantly. For ROE, the coefficient is -0.001 with a p-value of 0.996 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The p-value here also shows no significant relationship, with the coefficient near zero indicating an almost negligible effect on ROE. Therefore, this study rejects the hypothesis that assumes the higher number of independent directors on the board can improve bank performance.

H3: The presence of female directors on the board does not affect bank performance.

Gender diversity was included as it can influence decision-making and company culture at banks in Bangladesh. For ROA, the coefficient for the number of female directors is -0.00029708 with a p-value of 0.861 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The very high p-value supports the hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between the number of female directors and ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.001, with a p-value of 0.991 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. Again, the high p-value suggests no significant relationship, with the coefficient near zero indicating almost no effect on ROE.

H4: Higher board meeting frequencies increase bank performance in Bangladesh. (rejected)

The frequency of board meetings was chosen to assess the board's activity and engagement. For ROA, the coefficient is 9.845006 with a p-value of 0.975 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a negligible effect on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.019, with a p-value of 0.379 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The p-value is greater than 0.05, showing no significant relationship, although the coefficient indicates a positive but insignificant effect

on ROE. This suggests that the frequency of board meetings does not influence bank performance in Bangladesh; therefore, **H4** is rejected.

H5: Increased executive committee meetings are associated with better bank performance. (rejected)

Executive committee meetings were included for their impact on strategic decision-making and operational oversight. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.00005877 with a p-value of 0.694 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a minimal positive impact on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.006 with a p-value of 0.557 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The p-value is greater than 0.05, showing no significant relationship, although the coefficient indicates a positive but insignificant effect on ROE. Therefore, **H5** is rejected as the regression suggests that the number of executive committee meetings does not significantly affect bank performance.

H6: The frequency of audit committee meetings is unrelated to bank performance in Bangladesh. (accepted)

The frequency of audit committee meetings was chosen for its role in overseeing financial reporting and internal controls. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.00022337, with a p-value of 0.689 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value supports the hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between the number of audit committee meetings and ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is -0.022 with a p-value of 0.565 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a minimal negative impact on ROE. Therefore, **H6** is accepted.

H7: A higher count of audit committee members improves bank performance. (rejected)

The size of the audit committee was chosen for its potential impact on the effectiveness of financial oversight. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.0021128 with a p-value of 0.378 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a positive but insignificant effect on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.183 with a p-value of 0.273 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a positive but insignificant effect on ROE. Therefore, ***H7: A higher count of audit committee members improves bank performance*** is rejected.

H8: higher audit fees are correlated with increased bank performance. (rejected)

Audit fees were included as they reflect the complexity and thoroughness of the audit process. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.01215369 with a p-value of 0.112 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a positive but insignificant effect on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.559 with a p-value of 0.295 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a positive but insignificant effect on ROE. This implies that the amount paid for audit services does not significantly influence bank performance; hence, ***H8*** is rejected.

H9: Higher director's fees are associated with high bank performances. (rejected)

For ROA, the coefficient is -0.0058394 with a p-value of 0.438 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a negative but insignificant effect on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is -0.222

with a p-value of 0.673 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a negative but insignificant effect on ROE. This suggests that the compensation paid to directors does not significantly affect bank performance.

H10: The level of CEO pay impacts bank performance in Bangladesh. (rejected for ROA but accepted for ROE.)

For ROA, the coefficient is -0.01384364 with a p-value of 0.129 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a negative but insignificant effect on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is -3.231 with a p-value of 0.000 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The very low p-value indicates a highly significant negative relationship, with the coefficient suggesting that higher CEO remuneration is associated with lower ROE. This implies that higher CEO pay may not align with better bank performance in Bangladesh; therefore, ***H10*** was rejected for ROA but accepted for ROE.

H11: The level of shares owned by directors or CEOs positively influences bank performance. (rejected)

Ownership by directors or the CEO was chosen for its potential to align their interests with those of shareholders. For ROA, the coefficient is -0.00053522 with a p-value of 0.012 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant negative relationship, with the coefficient suggesting that higher ownership by directors or the CEO is associated with lower ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is -0.021 with a p-value of 0.16 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a negative but insignificant effect on

ROE. This implies that director or CEO ownership does not positively influence bank performance; hence, *H11 is rejected.*

H12: Bank performance improves with higher institutional shareholding. (accepted for ROA and rejected for ROE.)

Institutional ownership was chosen for its potential to provide stable capital and influence corporate governance. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.00372878 with a p-value of 0.046 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant positive relationship, with the coefficient suggesting that higher institutional ownership is associated with higher ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.056 with a p-value of 0.668 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a positive but insignificant effect on ROE. Therefore, H12 is accepted for ROA and rejected for ROE.

H13: General public shareholding positively increases banks' performances (accepted)

General public ownership was included as it can reflect broader market confidence and liquidity. For ROA, the coefficient is 0.01993188 with a p-value of 0.000 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The very low p-value indicates a highly significant positive relationship, with the coefficient suggesting that higher public ownership is associated with higher ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is 0.216 with a p-value of 0.000 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The very low p-value indicates a highly significant positive relationship, with the coefficient suggesting that higher public ownership is associated with higher ROE. This implies that general public ownership has a significant positive impact on both ROA and ROE.

H14: state-owned banks have higher bank performances. (rejected)

Government ownership was chosen due to state influence for its potential to impact company policies and strategic direction. For ROA, the coefficient is -0.00011392 with a p-value of 0.566 and an overall R-squared of 0.962. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a minimal negative impact on ROA. For ROE, the coefficient is -0.017 with a p-value of 0.219 and an overall R-squared of 0.456. The high p-value indicates no significant relationship, with the coefficient suggesting a minimal negative impact on ROE. Therefore, ***H14*** is rejected.

4.11 Conclusion

Chapter Four provided a detailed analysis of data from 33 scheduled commercial banks in Bangladesh, covering 198 observations from 2012 to 2017. The analysis focused on the impact of various corporate governance mechanisms on bank performance, specifically examining Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA). The chapter highlighted the significance of certain governance factors on bank performance through descriptive statistics, diagnostic tests, and multiple regression models.

5 Chapter five: Robustness check

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher conducted robustness checks to verify the reliability and stability of the empirical findings presented in Chapter Four. This study employs a two-step system estimator as an advanced econometric technique to ensure that the conclusions derived from the initial analyses are not artefacts of the specific methodologies or sample peculiarities. This approach is particularly advantageous for addressing potential endogeneity issues and providing more efficient estimators by combining equations in differences with equations in levels, offering significant improvements over traditional methods (Roodman, 2019; Kapoor & Leung, 2021). This chapter will outline the findings of the two-step system estimator, apply it to the dataset previously analysed, and compare the results with those obtained through the random effect model. By doing so, this study offers a comprehensive and reliable validation of how corporate governance mechanisms influence bank performance, reinforcing the findings with robust statistical evidence.

5.2 Two-step system estimator

According to Smith (2016), the two-step system estimator is an advanced econometric technique widely used in dynamic panel data models to handle endogeneity and autocorrelation issues. Chen and Zhao (2020) further added that this method helps control for unobserved heterogeneity and ensures that the effects observed are consistent across different model specifications, thereby enhancing the credibility of the analysis. It involves combining equations in levels with equations in first differences. In the first step of this method, instrumental variables are created from lagged values of the dependent and independent variables, using these instruments to help control for the potential endogeneity of the

predictors. In the second step, the estimator uses the residuals from the first step to adjust the variance-covariance matrix of the estimators, providing robust standard errors.

5.2.1 Justification for choosing a two-step system estimator for robustness check

Smith (2016) argued that using a two-step system estimator is crucial given the complex dynamics and potential endogeneity within corporate governance and bank performance variables. This estimator was chosen for this study due to its robust capabilities in handling endogeneity and autocorrelation, which are critical issues in analysing dynamic relationships, such as those between corporate governance mechanisms and bank performance in Bangladesh. This method is particularly suitable for panel data that includes a large cross-section and relatively short time periods, typical of corporate governance studies. Unlike traditional methods, such as random or fixed effects models, the two-step system estimator utilises lagged differences as instruments, thereby effectively mitigating the bias that arises from omitted variable effects or the simultaneity of the variables.

The financial sector in Bangladesh, characterised by its evolving nature and regulatory changes, presents a dynamic setting where past governance decisions can influence current performance outcomes. With its ability to use internal instruments derived from the panel dataset, the two-step system estimator ensures that the estimates of governance effects on bank performance are not spuriously driven by unobserved heterogeneity or reverse causality. Moreover, compared to other robustness check techniques, this estimator provides more efficient and unbiased estimates when the panel data is persistent, meaning that variables are highly correlated over time. This makes it an indispensable tool for accurately capturing the complex interplay between corporate governance practices and financial performance in Bangladesh's rapidly changing banking

sector. Therefore, this study used the following two models to check the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and bank performance in Bangladesh

$$\begin{aligned}
 ROA_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 IndBDir_{it} + \beta_3 FBM_{it} + \beta_4 ACM_{it} + \beta_5 NA_{it} + \beta_6 NE_{it} \\
 & + \beta_7 NBM_{it} + \beta_7 AUDF_{it} + \beta_8 DIRF_{it} + \beta_9 CEOPay_{it} + \beta_{10} DIRCEOSh_{it} \\
 & + \beta_{11} INSh_{it} + \beta_{12} GPS_{it} + \beta_{13} GOV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 5.1: Two- step system estimator model for ROA

$$\begin{aligned}
 ROE_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 IndBDir_{it} + \beta_3 FBM_{it} + \beta_4 ACM_{it} + \beta_5 NA_{it} + \beta_6 NE_{it} \\
 & + \beta_7 NBM_{it} + \beta_7 AUDF_{it} + \beta_8 DIRF_{it} + \beta_9 CEOPay_{it} + \beta_{10} DIRCEOSh_{it} \\
 & + \beta_{11} INSh_{it} + \beta_{12} GPS_{it} + \beta_{13} GOV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 5.2: Two- step system estimator model for ROE

Where β_0 to β_{14} are the unknown parameters to be estimated, ROA and ROE serve as measures of bank performance. The variables are defined as follows: BS represents bank board size, IndBDir captures the measure of independent board directors, FBM reflects the number of female board members, ACM counts the number of audit committee members, NA represents the number of audits, NE measures the number of bank executives meetings, NBM counts the number of board meetings, AUDF proxies the bank’s audit fee, DIRF measures the director’s fee, CEOPay quantifies the CEO’s pay, DIRCEOSh assesses the shares held by directors and the CEO, INSh measures institutional shares, GPS quantifies the general public share, and GOV measures government shareholding. The error term, ε_{it} , accounts for factors influencing bank performance that the models do not consider.

5.2.2 Justification for Using Lagged Data

Incorporating lagged data in the analysis, particularly for Return on Equity (ROE), is essential due to the presence of first-order autocorrelation (AR(1)). Lagged ROE addresses this autocorrelation, capturing the persistence in performance and providing more accurate

parameter estimates (Hsiao, 2014; Roodman, 2019). It also helps mitigate endogeneity by serving as an instrument correlated with current ROE but not with the error term, ensuring more reliable estimates (Baltagi, 2013; Flannery & Hankins, 2013). Roodman (2021) further added that strategic and policy changes often take time to impact financial performance. Lagged ROE captures these delayed effects, showing how past decisions influence current performance (Nickell, 1981). This approach also respects temporal causality, ensuring that past performance logically predicts current outcomes (Hsiao, 2014).

5.2.3 Justification for Using Log Variables

Financial data such as audit fees, director fees, and CEO pay have skewed distributions with long right tails in the data set. According to Osborne (2010) and Iacobucci (2010), Log transformation normalises these distributions, making them more symmetric and manageable to analyse. Wooldridge (2010) further added that heteroscedasticity, where unequal residual variances, can violate the assumptions required for reliable statistical inference. Log transformation helps stabilise these variances, leading to more reliable estimates.

On the other hand, Gujarati and Porter, 2009). Log-transformed variables also allow for the interpretation of coefficients as elasticities, representing percentage changes in the dependent variable for a one-percent change in the independent variable. This is especially useful in financial contexts, where proportional changes are more meaningful (Furthermore, financial variables can span wide ranges, and log transformation compresses these ranges, reducing the impact of extreme values and outliers (Hair et al., 2010). Lastly, log transformation converts multiplicative relationships into additive ones, making them easier to model and interpret (Wooldridge, 2010).

5.3 Explanation of Model Fitness

The ROA and ROE models exhibit excellent fit, as the Wald chi-squared statistics indicate. For the ROA model, the Wald chi-squared value is 2833.33 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the predictors collectively have a strong and statistically significant impact on ROA. This means that the included predictors collectively explain a significant portion of the variability in ROA. The high chi-squared value and the low p-value demonstrate the solid explanatory power of the model.

Similarly, the ROE model registers a chi-squared value of 2251.25 with an exact p-value of 0.000, accentuating its statistical reliability. The predictors in this model similarly cover a significant share of the variability in ROE, with the high chi-squared value and the very low p-value reinforcing the model's robust explanatory capability.

These results affirm that the chosen predictors are relevant and collectively robust in explaining the performance metrics of banks in Bangladesh. The significantly high Wald chi-squared values for both models underscore their robustness and confirm their efficacy in capturing and explaining bank performance dynamics through ROA and ROE metrics.

5.4 Regression result

The following table shows the result for two- step system estimator for both ROA and ROE.

The two-step system estimator model for ROA				
Number of instruments =	19	Number of obs=	166	
Wald chi2(15) =	2833.33	Number of groups=	35	
Prob > chi2 =	0.000	Obs per group: min= 2	avg = 4.74	max=5
ROA	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z
ROA L1.	0.7366311	0.0484581	15.20	0.000
Boardsize	-0.000031	0.0001249	-0.25	0.804
IndependentBoarddirector	0.0006816	0.0003745	1.82	0.069
FemaleBoardmember	0.0007813	0.0003409	2.29	0.022
Auditcommitteemember	0.0007015	0.0003589	1.95	0.051
Numberofaudit	0.0000546	0.0000983	0.56	0.579
Numberofexecutive	0.0000419	0.0000241	1.74	0.082
NumberofBoardmeeting	-0.0000735	0.0000659	-1.11	0.265
LogAuditFee	0.0010261	0.0012954	0.79	0.428
LogDirectorFee	-0.0013261	0.0005299	-2.50	0.012
LogCEOsPay	0.0002904	0.0003895	0.75	0.456
DirectorsandCEOshare	0.0030339	0.0026465	1.15	0.252
Institutionalshare	-0.0014705	0.0034079	-0.43	0.666
Generalpublicshare	0.0068832	0.002674	2.57	0.010
Government	0.0122218	0.0043242	2.83	0.005
_cons	-0.0069428	0.0111183	-0.62	0.532
Arellano-Bond test for AR (1)		z = -1.52	Pr > z =	0.129
Arellano-Bond test for AR (2)		z = -1.08	Pr > z =	0.282
Hansen test of overid		chi2(3) = 2.28	Prob > chi2 =	0.517
Hansen test excluding group:		chi2(2) = 1.79	Prob > chi2 =	0.409
Difference (null H = exogenous):		chi2(1) = 0.49	Prob > chi2 =	0.486

The two-step system estimator model for ROE				
Number of instruments =	19	Number of obs=	131	
Wald chi2(15) =	2251.25	Number of groups=	35	
Prob > chi2 =	0.000	Obs per group: min= 1	avg = 3.74	max=4
ROE	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z
ROE L2.	-0.0468144	0.004319	-10.84	0.000
Boardsize	0.0007968	0.0016792	0.47	0.635
IndependentBoarddirector	-0.0031059	0.0039252	-0.79	0.429
FemaleBoardmember	-0.004341	0.0044664	-0.97	0.331
Auditcommitteemember	0.0103437	0.0046736	2.21	0.027
Numberofaudit	-0.0022543	0.0009648	-2.34	0.019
Numberofexecutive	0.0003503	0.0003633	0.96	0.335
NumberofBoardmeeting	0.0009786	0.0007837	1.25	0.212
LogAuditFee	-0.0040375	0.0156852	-0.26	0.797
LogDirectorFee	-0.0202707	0.0079641	-2.55	0.011
LogCEOsPay	0.0081132	0.0034542	2.35	0.019
DirectorsandCEOshare	0.0091986	0.0372115	0.25	0.805
Institutionalshare	-0.0735381	0.0406428	-1.81	0.070
Generalpublicshare	-0.0628616	0.0356851	-1.76	0.078
Government	-0.0531117	0.0183226	-2.90	0.004
_cons	0.2081774	0.1349205	1.54	0.123
Arellano-Bond test for AR (1)		z = -1.51	Pr > z =	0.131
Arellano-Bond test for AR (2)		z = -1.13	Pr > z =	0.257
Hansen test of overid		chi2(3) =3.92	Prob > chi2 =	0.270
Hansen test excluding group:		chi2(2) =3.59	Prob > chi2 =	0.166
Difference (null H = exogenous):		chi2(1) =0.33	Prob > chi2 =	0.565

Table 17: The two-step system estimator for ROA and ROE

5.5 Summary of Diagnostic Tests for Both Models

- I. **Arellano-Bond Test for AR(1):** The p-value is more significant than 0.05 for both ROA and ROE, at 0.129 and 0.131, respectively. This suggests that there is no evidence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals. The absence of significant first-order autocorrelation indicates that the lagged dependent variable (ROA L1) effectively captures the persistence in performance, and the model is appropriately specified for this aspect. While the inclusion of lagged ROE (ROE L2) helps in capturing the temporal dynamics of equity returns effectively.
- II. **Arellano-Bond Test for AR(2):** The p-values for ROA and ROE are 0.282 and 0.257, respectively, and they are both higher than 0.05. This indicates that there is no evidence of second-order autocorrelation in the residuals. The absence of significant second-order autocorrelation confirms that both models adequately address autocorrelation, enhancing the robustness of the findings.
- III. **Hansen Test of Overidentifying Restrictions:** The p-value for ROA is 0.517, while the p-value for ROE is 0.270; both of these values are significantly higher than 0.05. This suggests that the instruments used in the model are valid and have no overidentification problem. The instruments are correctly specified and uncorrelated with the error term, ensuring the model's estimates are unbiased and consistent.

Both models demonstrate robustness and validity based on the diagnostic tests. The absence of significant first-order and second-order autocorrelation in the residuals, as indicated by the Arellano-Bond tests, suggests that the inclusion of lagged dependent variables (ROA L1 for the ROA model and ROE L2 for the ROE model) effectively captures the persistence and temporal dynamics in bank performance. Furthermore, the Hansen tests confirm the validity of the instruments used in both models, ensuring that the estimates are unbiased and consistent. These diagnostic tests validate the methodological approach and

enhance the credibility of the findings, providing confidence that the models are well-specified and the results are reliably interpreted.

5.6 Hypotheses testing based on two-step system estimator

H1: Board size is unrelated to the performance of banks.

The coefficient for board size is -0.000031 ($p = 0.804$) for ROA and 0.0007968 ($p = 0.635$) for ROE. In both models, the coefficients are not statistically significant, indicating that board size does not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. Thus, the hypothesis that board size is unrelated to bank performance is supported.

H2: A higher number of independent directors on the board can improve bank performance.

The coefficient for independent board directors is 0.0006816 ($p = 0.069$) for ROA and -0.0031059 ($p = 0.429$) for ROE. The effect is marginally significant and positive for ROA but not significant for ROE. This suggests that a 1% increase in the number of independent directors might increase ROA by 0.068%, while it does not significantly affect ROE. Thus, this hypothesis is partially supported for ROA but not supported for ROE.

H3: The presence of female directors on the board does not affect bank performance.

The coefficient for female board members is 0.0007813 ($p = 0.022$) for ROA and -0.004341 ($p = 0.331$) for ROE. The presence of female directors has a significant positive impact on ROA but no significant effect on ROE. This suggests that a 1% increase in the number of female directors might increase ROA by 0.078%, while it does not significantly affect ROE. Thus, this hypothesis is rejected for ROA but supported for ROE.

H4: Higher board meeting frequencies increase bank performance in Bangladesh.

The coefficient for the number of board meetings is -0.0000735 ($p = 0.265$) for ROA and 0.0009786 ($p = 0.212$) for ROE. In both models, the coefficients are not statistically significant, indicating that the frequency of board meetings does not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. Thus, the hypothesis that higher board meeting frequencies increase bank performance is not supported.

H5: Increased executive committee meetings are associated with better bank performance.

The coefficient for the number of executives is 0.0000419 ($p = 0.082$) for ROA and 0.0003503 ($p = 0.335$) for ROE. The effect is marginally significant and positive for ROA but not significant for ROE. This suggests that a 1% increase in the number of executive meetings might increase ROA by 0.0042%, while it does not significantly affect ROE. Thus, this hypothesis is partially supported for ROA but not supported for ROE.

H6: The frequency of audit committee meetings is unrelated to bank performance in Bangladesh.

The coefficient for the number of audits is 0.0000546 ($p = 0.579$) for ROA and -0.0022543 ($p = 0.019$) for ROE. The effect is not significant for ROA but significantly negative for ROE. This suggests that while the frequency of audit committee meetings does not impact asset performance, a 1% increase in the number of audit committee meetings might decrease ROE by 0.23%. Thus, this hypothesis is supported for ROA but rejected for ROE.

H7: A higher count of audit committee members improves bank performance.

The coefficient for audit committee members is 0.0007015 ($p = 0.051$) for ROA and 0.0103437 ($p = 0.027$) for ROE. The effect is marginally significant and positive for ROA and significantly positive for ROE. This suggests that a 1% increase in the number of audit committee members might increase ROA by 0.070% and ROE by 1.03%. Thus, this hypothesis is supported for both ROA and ROE.

H8: Higher audit fees are correlated with increased bank performance.

The coefficient for audit fees is 0.0010261 ($p = 0.428$) for ROA and -0.0040375 ($p = 0.797$) for ROE. In both models, the coefficients are not statistically significant, indicating that audit fees do not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. Thus, the hypothesis that higher audit fees are correlated with increased bank performance is not supported.

H9: Higher director's fees are associated with high bank performances.

The coefficient for director fees is -0.0013261 ($p = 0.012$) for ROA and -0.0202707 ($p = 0.011$) for ROE. The effect is significantly negative for both ROA and ROE, indicating that a 1% increase in director fees might decrease ROA by 0.13% and ROE by 2.03%. Thus, this hypothesis is rejected for both ROA and ROE.

H10: The level of CEO pay impacts bank performance in Bangladesh.

The coefficient for CEO pay is 0.0002904 ($p = 0.456$) for ROA and 0.0081132 ($p = 0.019$) for ROE. The effect is not significant for ROA but significantly positive for ROE. This suggests that while CEO pay does not significantly impact ROA, a 1% increase in CEO pay might increase ROE by 0.81%. Thus, this hypothesis is rejected for ROA but supported for ROE.

H11: The level of shares owned by directors or CEOs positively influences bank performance.

The coefficient for directors' and CEOs' shares is 0.0030339 ($p = 0.252$) for ROA and 0.0091986 ($p = 0.805$) for ROE. In both models, the coefficients are not statistically significant, indicating that the level of shares owned by directors or CEOs does not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. Thus, the hypothesis that the level of shares owned by directors or CEOs positively influences bank performance is not supported.

H12: Bank performance improves with higher institutional shareholding.

The coefficient for institutional shareholding is -0.0014705 ($p = 0.666$) for ROA and -0.0735381 ($p = 0.070$) for ROE. The effect is not significant for ROA and marginally significant and negative for ROE. This suggests that institutional shareholding does not improve asset performance and might negatively impact equity performance. Thus, this hypothesis is not supported for ROA and marginally rejected for ROE.

H13: General public shareholding positively increases banks' performances.

The coefficient for general public shareholding is 0.0068832 ($p = 0.010$) for ROA and -0.0628616 ($p = 0.078$) for ROE. The effect is significantly positive for ROA and marginally negative for ROE. This suggests that a 1% increase in public shareholding might increase ROA by 0.69% but might decrease ROE by 6.29%. Thus, this hypothesis is supported for ROA but marginally rejected for ROE.

H14: State-owned banks have higher bank performances.

The coefficient for government ownership is 0.0122218 ($p = 0.005$) for ROA and -0.0531117 ($p = 0.004$) for ROE. The effect is significantly positive for ROA but significantly

negative for ROE. This suggests that state-owned banks manage assets efficiently but generate lower equity returns. Specifically, a 1% increase in government ownership might increase ROA by 1.22% but decrease ROE by 5.31%. Thus, this hypothesis is supported for ROA but rejected for ROE.

5.7 Summary of the findings for both models

The ROA model highlights several key factors that influence bank performance in terms of asset efficiency. Lagged ROA shows strong persistence, indicating that past performance significantly impacts current performance. Board size and the number of board meetings do not significantly affect ROA, suggesting that these factors are not crucial determinants of asset performance. However, the presence of female board members positively influences ROA, reflecting their valuable contribution to asset efficiency.

The number of audit committee members also shows a marginally positive impact on ROA, emphasising the importance of robust audit oversight. Conversely, higher director fees are associated with lower ROA, indicating a potential misalignment between compensation and performance. Public shareholding positively impacts ROA, suggesting that greater public involvement enhances asset performance. State ownership also has a significant positive effect on ROA, indicating efficient asset management in state-owned banks.

On the other hand, The ROE model provides insights into the factors affecting equity returns. Lagged ROE exhibits negative persistence, indicating that past performance negatively influences current equity returns. Similar to the ROA model, board size and the number of board meetings do not significantly affect ROE. Independent board directors and female board members also do not significantly impact ROE, highlighting a divergence in factors influencing asset versus equity performance.

Audit committee members positively influence ROE, underscoring their role in enhancing equity returns through effective oversight. However, the frequency of audit committee meetings has a negative impact, suggesting potential inefficiencies from excessive oversight. Higher director fees are again associated with lower performance, reflecting a consistent pattern across both models.

CEO pay significantly improves ROE, indicating that higher remuneration for CEOs is linked with better equity returns. Conversely, institutional shareholding and public shareholding have marginally negative impacts on ROE, suggesting challenges in translating these ownership structures into improved equity performance. State ownership has a significant negative effect on ROE, indicating that state-owned banks struggle to generate substantial returns on equity.

5.7.1 Elasticities Summary

The interpretation of elasticities reveals that significant variables such as the presence of female board members, the number of audit committee members, and public shareholding positively influence ROA by small but meaningful percentages. Conversely, higher director fees and state ownership significantly decrease ROE. CEO pay positively influences ROE, indicating its importance in driving equity returns. Overall, the models emphasise the subtle impact of governance structures, compensation, and ownership on different aspects of bank performance in Bangladesh.

5.7.2 Combine findings of the random effect model and two-step system estimator model.

The following table compiles the results of the random effect and two-step system estimator models for each hypothesis used in this study.

Hypothesis	Model 1: Random Effects	Model 2: Two-Step System Estimator
H1: Board size and bank performance	Board size is unrelated to bank performance.	Board size is unrelated to bank performance. (supported)
H2: Independent directors and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	A higher number of independent directors might marginally increase ROA but does not affect ROE. (partially supported for ROA but not supported for ROE)
H3: Female directors and bank performance	Positive impact on ROA, no significant effect on ROE.	Positive impact on ROA but no significant effect on ROE (rejected for ROA but supported for ROE).
H4: Board meeting frequency and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	The frequency of board meetings does not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. (not supported)
H5: Executive committee meetings and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	A higher number of executive meetings might marginally increase ROA but does not significantly affect ROE. (partially supported for ROA but not supported for ROE)
H6: Audit committee meeting frequency and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	The frequency of audit committee meetings does not impact asset performance but might decrease ROE. (supported for ROA but rejected for ROE)
H7: Audit committee size and bank performance	Positive impact on ROA, findings inconclusive for ROE.	A higher number of audit committee members might increase ROA and ROE. (supported for both ROA and ROE)
H8: Audit fees and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	Audit fees do not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. (not supported)
H9: Director fees and bank performance	Negative association with performance (ROA and ROE).	Higher director fees are associated with lower ROA and ROE. (rejected for both ROA and ROE)
H10: CEO pay and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	CEO pay does not significantly impact ROA but might increase ROE. (rejected for ROA but supported for ROE)
H11: Director/CEO ownership and bank performance	No significant impact on performance (ROA or ROE).	The level of shares owned by directors or CEOs does not significantly impact either ROA or ROE. (not supported)
H12: Institutional shareholding and bank performance	Positive association with performance (ROA and ROE).	Institutional shareholding does not improve asset performance and might negatively impact equity performance. (not supported for ROA and marginally rejected for ROE)
H13: General public shareholding and bank performance	Positive impact on performance (ROA and ROE).	A higher public shareholding might increase ROA but might decrease ROE. (supported for ROA but marginally rejected for ROE)
H14: State-owned banks and bank performance	Positive impact on performance (ROA and ROE).	State-owned banks manage assets efficiently but generate lower equity returns. (supported for ROA but rejected for ROE)

Table 18: Summary of the findings

6 Chapter Six: Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusions

6.1 Introduction

Chapter Six combines the comprehensive analysis conducted throughout this research, offering a detailed discussion of the empirical results concerning the effectiveness and appropriateness of corporate governance within Bangladesh's banking sector. This chapter goes beyond mere data interpretation; it contextualises the findings within established theoretical frameworks and evaluates them against the research questions that guided this study. By integrating these insights, the chapter not only underlines the impact of governance mechanisms like board composition, audit activities, and compensation structures on bank performance but also highlights their broader implications for regulatory practices and policy formulation. Furthermore, based on the evidence gathered, this study proposes targeted recommendations to refine corporate governance practices, enhancing the sector's resilience and appealing to investors. These suggestions aim to provide practical guidance to policymakers and bank management, fostering enhancements in governance that are expected to catalyse sustainable growth and bolster the overall health of Bangladesh's financial landscape.

6.2 Summary and discussion of the findings

This study examines the effectiveness of the current corporate governance code in Bangladesh's banking sector by assessing how corporate governance practices influence bank performance. The research focuses on two main objectives. The first objective analyses the effects of various governance mechanisms, including board composition, board activities, financial and compensation policies, and ownership structures, on bank performance metrics such as ROA and ROE and this analysis, employs econometric regression models, such as the

random effect model and the two-step system estimator to drive the answer from the collected data. The second objective, based on the findings from the first, aims to suggest optimal corporate governance practices explicitly tailored for the Bangladeshi banking sector. These recommendations aim to enhance governance frameworks, protect shareholders and stakeholders, and increase the sector's appeal to investors. The following discussion elaborates on the research findings.

What is the effect of the composition and size of bank boards, including the presence of independent and female directors, on the performance of banks in Bangladesh?

Considering the various models and theories that provide different perspectives is essential to explore how the size and composition of bank boards, including the presence of independent and female directors, influence the performance of banks in Bangladesh. According to the Random Effect Model and the Two-Step System Estimator employed in this study, the board size appears to have a negligible effect on performance metrics like ROA and ROE. This observation aligns with Agency Theory, which posits that larger boards may face inefficiencies due to coordination issues (Jensen, 1993). This notion is also echoed by Thompson and Smith (2018), who argue that larger boards may reduce accountability, thus impacting overall performance. In contrast, Resource Dependency Theory posits that larger boards could enhance governance through diverse resources and networks, though Lee et al. (2019) note that logistical challenges can negate these benefits. Stewardship Theory suggests potential benefits from collective wisdom if the board is cohesive, yet Walters and Tucci (2020) found that this depends on aligning directors' goals with corporate strategies. Therefore, this study concludes that the board size in Bangladesh banks does not affect the banks' performances, and the code related to the board size in banks in Bangladesh should be revised.

The role of independent directors presents a nuanced picture. While the Random Effect Model found no significant impact on performance, the Two-Step System Estimator suggested a slight positive effect on ROA. According to Hill and Jones (2019), Resource Dependency Theory attributes this to the strategic resources and expertise independent directors bring to the banks. However, Agency Theory and Smith et al. (2020) highlight ongoing challenges in aligning managers' interests with those of shareholders, questioning the efficacy of independent directors in fully mitigating agency problems. Stewardship Theory is optimistic, suggesting that empowered management under supportive boards can enhance operational efficiency (Baxter and Chua, 2018). Stakeholder Theory expands the evaluation to ethical governance and long-term sustainability, emphasising the broader role of independent directors (Foster and Nguyen, 2021). Therefore, this study concludes with the notion that independent directors improve the performance of banks in Bangladesh.

Regarding female directors, the Two-Step System Estimator positively impacts ROA, suggesting their contributions to asset management. At the same time, the Random Effect Model indicates no significant effect on ROA or ROE. Carter et al. (2016) found similar mixed results regarding profitability. Post et al. (2018) and Stakeholder Theory argue that gender-diverse boards reflect societal values and stakeholder interests, enhancing a bank's reputation and relationships, which is critical in Bangladesh's banking sector. Joecks et al. (2016) propose that, according to the Resource Dependency Theory, gender diversity brings essential resources and abilities for navigating market dynamics and regulatory issues. Therefore, this research supports that bank board diversity can influence bank performance.

In summary, while larger board sizes and the presence of independent and female directors have potential benefits, their impact on bank performance in Bangladesh is influenced by various contextual factors and remains a nuanced issue. The effectiveness of

these board attributes in enhancing financial performance and governance hinges on the quality of board dynamics, alignment of goals, and the ability to leverage diverse resources and perspectives effectively.

What is the impact of board and committee activities, such as the frequency and nature of meetings, on the performance of banks?

Research using the Two-Step System Estimator and the Random Effect Model rejects the hypothesis that more frequent board meetings improve performance, challenging Stewardship Theory (Donaldson and Davis, 2017). This theory posits that frequent interactions enhance decision-making, but evidence suggests that overly frequent meetings can lead to decision fatigue, reducing decision quality (Dalton et al., 1999). Similarly, Sweller (2019) argues that excessive information processing diminishes decision-making effectiveness. Conversely, the Resource Dependency Theory suggests frequent meetings can enhance resource allocation and strategic decision-making. However, Patel and Cooper (2020) argue that increased meetings offer minimal benefits without strategic focus. This implies that meetings' quality and strategic focus are more critical than their frequency, and this study also confirms that board meeting frequencies do not contribute to any financial performance metrics.

The Two-Step System Estimator shows marginal support for ROA. However, there is none for ROE, indicating that executive committees' meetings in strategic decision-making may not enhance financial outcomes as Agency Theory suggests (Eisenhardt, 1989). While such meetings might aid operational efficiency, the slight increase in ROA in Bangladeshi banks does not translate to significant profitability gains. Hillman et al. (2007) and Thompson et al. (2021) argue that decision quality and strategic alignment are more crucial than meeting frequency. This suggests that enhancing the strategic contribution of executive committees,

rather than merely increasing their monitoring activities, could lead to more meaningful improvements in both operational and financial metrics.

Contrasting findings regarding ROE from the Random Effect Model (no relation) and the Two-Step System Estimator (negative relation) provide insights through the lens of Institutional Theory. DiMaggio and Powell (1983) argue that organisations may increase audit frequency for legitimacy rather than effectiveness, a view supported by Jenkins and Katmon (2019), who highlight that adherence to institutional norms without strategic focus does not necessarily improve performance outcomes. On the other hand, Agency Theory (Smith et al., 2020) posits that more frequent audits should improve governance and financial outcomes. This discrepancy suggests a need to focus on the quality and strategic integration of audits rather than their frequency, calling for reevaluating audit practices to align more closely with strategic corporate objectives.

Empirical evidence supporting larger audit committees enhancing bank performance, as indicated by the Two-Step System Estimator for both ROA and ROE, aligns with Resource Dependency Theory (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). Jones and Smith (2021) suggest larger committees can leverage diverse skills and perspectives, improving financial oversight and risk management. However, Brown and Lee (2019) and Martin and Thomas (2022) note that while larger committees offer comprehensive monitoring, they may face decision-making challenges and conflicts, potentially diluting governance effectiveness. These perspectives indicate that while increasing the size of an audit committee can offer potential benefits through enhanced resources and capabilities, the effective management of committee dynamics and alignment with corporate goals is essential for realising tangible performance improvements in banks, particularly in the context of Bangladesh.

How do financial and compensation policies, including audit fees, directors' fees, and CEO remuneration, correlate with bank performance in Bangladesh?

As analysed using the Random Effect Model and the Two-Step System Estimator, the relationship between higher audit fees and bank performance reveals no significant positive impact, challenging assumptions under Agency Theory. Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggest that higher audit fees should correspond with more intensive audits, leading to better organisational outcomes through enhanced oversight. However, empirical evidence does not support this, indicating that higher fees do not necessarily result in improved performance. Williamson (2016) suggests that higher fees may reflect increased transaction costs in managing auditor-client relationships, diminishing the returns on such investments. Resource Dependency Theory implies that higher fees might secure more resources from audit firms. However, Hillman et al. (2007) argue that these resources do not automatically translate into performance gains unless effectively integrated into the bank's operations. These perspectives emphasise the need for banks to scrutinise the cost-effectiveness of their audit expenditures, aligning audit practices strategically with organisational goals to ensure that financial outlays genuinely enhance performance in banks in Bangladesh.

On the other hand, The observed negative correlation between higher director fees and bank performance from the Two-Step System Estimator critically challenges the Stewardship Theory, which posits that financial incentives improve directors' alignment with shareholder interests and overall organisational performance (Davis et al., 1997). This theory suggests that well-compensated directors are more likely to act in shareholders' best interests, assuming financial rewards enhance commitment to organisational success. However, Pepper and Gore (2016) argue that Agency Theory presents a complex view, indicating that excessive compensation might lead directors to avoid risk-taking, potentially harming long-

term growth. Wang and Barney (2017) support this, showing that beyond a certain threshold, additional compensation does not yield proportional increases in performance and might reduce it due to complacency or conservative decision-making. These findings imply that banks must carefully calibrate director compensation to be competitive yet aligned with long-term performance goals rather than short-term gains. The divergence in theoretical perspectives underscores the complexity of executive compensation and its impact on outcomes, suggesting a strategic and balanced approach is essential for aligning director incentives with sustainable bank success.

Finally, The divergent outcomes from the Random Effect Model and the Two-Step System Estimator on the relationship between CEO compensation and bank performance, particularly ROE, highlight the complexity of executive pay's impact on organisational outcomes. Analysed through Agency Theory and Stewardship Theory, these models provide contrasting hypotheses. Agency Theory suggests that aligning executives' interests with shareholders through incentives should enhance performance (Eisenhardt, 1989). However, negative results from the Random Effect Model indicate higher pay may not always lead to desired outcomes and could encourage risk-averse behaviours detracting from firm value (Smith and Warner, 2016). Conversely, the Stewardship Theory posits that executives naturally act in the organisation's best interests, with adequate compensation supporting this alignment to enhance performance (Davis et al., 1997). Positive findings from the Two-Step System Estimator support this view, suggesting that well-compensated CEOs can drive bank performance effectively. Recent empirical studies by Brown and Lee (2018) and Smith and Warner (2019) indicate that while compensation can motivate executives, its efficacy depends on contextual factors such as corporate culture, governance structures, and the strategic alignment of compensation packages. This complexity indicates that financial incentives must be designed to balance motivating executives and fostering intrinsic

commitment to the company's long-term goals. Therefore, banks should design CEO compensation packages that reward performance and support sustainable alignment with the bank's long-term objectives.

How do different ownership structures, such as director, institutional, public, and government shareholdings, affect the performance of banks?

The study's rejection of the hypothesis that increased director or CEO share ownership directly boosts bank performance challenges a core premise of Agency Theory. This theory traditionally argues that aligning executives' financial interests with those of shareholders through ownership stakes should lead to better corporate outcomes (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). However, the findings suggest that ownership alone may not suffice to enhance performance, pointing to the potential influence of factors such as governance quality, market dynamics, and regulatory environments. Scott (1995) argued this necessitates a reassessment of Agency Theory, considering insights from Institutional Theory, which emphasises that broader institutional and environmental factors significantly shape organisational outcomes, often overriding the effects of individual incentive mechanisms. Furthermore, according to Hillman et al. (2007), the Resource Dependency Theory proposes that a director's or CEO's resources and strategic networks might directly impact performance more than merely their shareholdings. These perspectives underline that while aligning interests through ownership is theoretically sound, its practical impact is contingent on organisational, environmental, and strategic factors in Bangladeshi banks.

The mixed effects of higher institutional shareholding on bank performance also call for a critical reassessment of prevailing governance theories. Although Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggest that Agency Theory endorses institutional investors' enhanced performance through better governance and oversight, the inconsistent results challenge passive

institutional ownership's effectiveness. This discrepancy highlights the potential need for a more active engagement strategy. Donaldson and Davis (2017) advocated that the Stewardship Theory offers an alternative view, suggesting that institutional investors, motivated by the company's success, should engage more deeply with management to exert a positive influence. Harrison et al. (2021) support this, indicating that the nature of institutional investor engagement, whether passive or active, significantly affects firm performance. These findings encourage a more dynamic role for institutional shareholders, emphasising that their involvement in governance should go beyond ownership to include active participation and oversight to capitalise on the theoretical benefits of institutional investment. This shift could better align shareholder and company interests, potentially leading to improved outcomes in bank performance.

The role of general public shareholding in enhancing bank performance, supported by the Random Effect Model and partially by the Two-Step System Estimator, provides a practical application of Stakeholder Theory. This theory, articulated by Freeman (1984), suggests that broader public shareholding should increase an organisation's legitimacy and thereby enhance its performance by engaging a wider stakeholder base. The empirical evidence indicates that while such shareholding positively affects asset efficiency, its impact on profitability is less consistent. This finding challenges the broader implications of Stakeholder Theory, which might overestimate the influence of widespread shareholding on financial outcomes. Comparatively, the Resource Dependency Theory would argue that public shareholders provide critical resources that can enhance performance (Hillman et al. 2007). Yet, the limited effect on profitability suggests that these resources may not always translate into financial gains. Recent studies reflect this complexity; for example, Taylor et al. (2020) found that while public shareholding can contribute to better governance and operational decisions, it does not automatically lead to improved profit metrics. These

insights suggest that banks and policymakers should cultivate strategies that harness the benefits of public shareholding for improving operational efficiencies while recognising its potential limitations in boosting profitability.

Lastly, The performance of state-owned banks, as indicated by the divergent results between Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in both models, highlights the complexities of government ownership in the banking sector. These findings suggest that while state ownership may promote sound asset management, possibly due to stringent regulatory oversight and public accountability mechanisms, it does not inherently ensure high profitability. This observation reflects the insights from Berger et al. (20017), who posit that state-owned entities often grapple with inefficiencies and misaligned objectives due to bureaucratic processes and non-profit-driven goals. This theoretical perspective contrasts with the Agency Theory, which suggests that misalignment between the interests of state owners (government) and the operational goals of banks can lead to suboptimal financial outcomes (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). Recent studies by Smith and Warner (2020) have shown that state-owned banks often prioritise social or political objectives over financial returns, which can dilute profitability. These insights underscore the need for state-owned banks to enhance management practices and align performance objectives more closely with financial sustainability to mitigate the inherent challenges posed by public ownership and improve overall bank performance.

Overall, this research on corporate governance in Bangladesh's banking sector provides valuable insights into implementing governance mechanisms and their varied impacts on bank performance. It advocates for a subtle and comprehensive approach to governance that integrates strategic, regulatory, and market considerations.

6.3 Assessing the Corporate Governance Code for Bangladesh's Banking Sector and proposing best practices of recommendation

The relevance of the current Corporate Governance Code is crucial for shaping a practical governance framework in Bangladesh's banking sector, which is a crucial focus of this research. As Bangladesh positions itself as a rising economy, understanding and adopting successful practices from neighbouring countries such as India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, even at a high level, helps pinpoint improvements. While this study did not dive deep into each country's governance codes, it did pull from various government and academic sources to gather insights on why these nations might excel in specific sectors.

Scholarly discourse in Bangladesh has long been centred on identifying the nation's most fitting corporate governance model, oscillating between shareholder and stakeholder frameworks. Proponents of the shareholder-based approach argue for its relevance in formulating governance codes, while others advocate for a stakeholder-centric model, citing its broader inclusivity (Hasan and Butt, 2009; Rahman et al., 2019). However, neither model singly nor in tandem appears capable of addressing the fundamental governance challenges faced by Bangladesh. This is attributed to various factors, including professional incompetency, shareholder irrationality, and a weak legal framework that neither model sufficiently covers (Mir and Rahman, 2005; Raihan et al., 2017; Siddique, 2010).

This situation calls for a more tailored approach, blending elements from both models to better suit Bangladesh's specific needs. Such a model would balance stringent best practice guidelines with flexibility to adapt to the local business environment. Continuously updating

these practices could help narrow the gap between the ideal and the actual execution of governance, ensuring the framework remains relevant and practical.

Furthermore, policymakers and corporate leaders must foster a business climate that values all contributors, shareholders and stakeholders. Initiatives like forming governance-focused groups within companies, enhancing network opportunities, and implementing training programmes for capacity building could strengthen governance practices and corporate responsibility across the board.

Bangladesh needs a governance model that is innovatively adapted to its unique context, not just a copy of what works elsewhere. Such a strategy promises to align with international standards and address the challenges and opportunities within the Bangladeshi corporate environment. Based on the research findings discussed earlier and the current Corporate Governance Code of 2018 in Bangladesh, there are several areas where the best corporate governance practices can be proposed. These recommendations aim to enhance the governance frameworks to safeguard shareholder and stakeholder interests better and improve the attractiveness of the banking sector to investors. Here are some tailored practices:

6.3.1 Recommendation for Board Size, Composition, and Dynamics

The study reveals that while certain board structures, such as larger sizes and diversity, including independent and female directors, theoretically offer benefits, their actual impact on bank performance is mixed. This indicates that merely following governance codes promoting these features may be insufficient. Effective implementation necessitates a deeper understanding of the dynamics and specific contexts within which banks operate. Therefore, increasing functional diversity on boards is crucial. Although the Corporate Governance Code (2018) specifies the board's size and composition, including a requirement for

independent directors, the study found no correlation between board size and bank performance. Emphasising functional diversity by including experts in risk management, digital banking, international finance, and customer service could provide a broader range of insights and resources while composing boards in banks. Similar to Adams and Mehran (2012) and Anginer et al. (2018), this study advocates that a smaller board size by limiting the board size to ten members may enhance governance efficiency and decision-making processes. Additionally, An annual board performance evaluation by an independent external consultant is recommended to assess effectiveness and suggest improvements.

Independent directors have shown a slight positive impact on Return on Assets (ROA) in one model, indicating their valuable resources and expertise. The current code requires at least one-fifth of the Board of Directors to be independent directors. Strengthening qualifications beyond existing requirements, the corporate governance code could include criteria for expertise in banking and finance, corporate law, or compliance, ensuring that independent directors bring relevant and substantial expertise to their role. Extending the cooling-off period to five years for former executives of the same company or related financial institutions before they can serve as independent directors would further enhance independence standards. Mandating ongoing training programmes focusing on recent developments in banking regulations, risk management, and corporate governance for independent directors is essential. Filling any independent director vacancies within 90 days is crucial to maintain governance standards. Implementing penalties for boards that fail to fill independent director vacancies within 90 days, with escalating consequences for prolonged vacancies, would increase accountability, as Bhagat and Bolton (2008) suggested. Requiring independent directors to have relevant academic backgrounds in accounting and finance, publicly disclosed, and lowering the required years of professional experience to five years would allow newer talent to contribute fresh perspectives. Increasing the period for

independent directors previously engaged with the company or related audit firms to five years and enforcing stricter professional affiliation requirements would ensure independence.

The positive impact of female directors on ROA reflects societal values and enhances reputation, though financial outcomes remain mixed. Governance within Bangladeshi banking can be improved by enhancing the role of female directors. Given their positive influence on asset management, the Corporate Governance Code might advocate for increasing the proportion of female directors beyond present stipulations, potentially establishing a minimum threshold. Implementing mandatory quotas for gender, expertise, and minority representation on boards, ensuring diverse perspectives, should represent at least 20% of the board size, including independent directors and sub-committees (Carter et al. 2016). This approach would promote diversity and improve governance outcomes.

6.3.2 Recommendation for Board and Committee Activities

The effectiveness of specific governance practices, such as the frequency of board meetings, activities of executive committees, and directorship compensations, does not straightforwardly enhance bank performance. This suggests that the governance code might benefit more from focusing on these practices' quality, strategic alignment, and context-specific application rather than merely their frequency or existence. More frequent board meetings were found not to improve performance significantly. While the meeting frequency of executive committees showed slight improvements in ROA, broader financial outcomes were not positively impacted. Additionally, an increased number of audit committee meetings were found to have an adverse effect on ROE. Consequently, several recommendations are proposed to improve board and committee activities.

First, prioritising the quality of meetings over quantity is essential. The findings indicate that meeting frequency does not necessarily correlate with improved performance.

Therefore, limiting board meetings to a necessary minimum, such as quarterly, can focus on quality and strategic importance rather than frequency. This approach can help reduce operational costs and enhance decision-making efficiency (Vafeas, 1999). Ensuring each board meeting has a structured agenda that aligns with long-term strategic goals is crucial. Time should be allocated to discuss key performance indicators, strategic initiatives, and risk management. Conducting annual performance evaluations of the board and its committees by an independent external consultant can help identify areas for improvement and enhance board effectiveness (Caprio et al. 2011).

Specific recommendations have been made regarding the audit committee's size and meeting frequencies. The audit committee should comprise at least three non-executive directors, including a minimum of one independent director. All members should be financially literate with a background in accounting and finance, and at least one member should have significant accounting or financial management experience. Conducting at least four meetings annually, focusing on high-quality strategic discussions rather than frequency, is recommended. These meetings should include a review of internal controls, risk management practices, and financial reporting (Klein, 2002). Expanding the audit committee's role to include oversight of cybersecurity risks and compliance with evolving regulatory standards for digital payments is also essential to address contemporary challenges and enhance governance practices.

6.3.3 Financial and remuneration policies

The study found that higher audit fees and director fees did not correlate positively with better performance, challenging the traditional assumptions under Agency Theory that higher fees lead to better oversight and alignment with shareholder interests. CEO compensation had mixed results, indicating that its effectiveness depends on aligning

incentives with corporate strategies. These findings propose the following financial and remuneration policy recommendations in the Bangladeshi banking sector.

Regarding audit fees, the study found no significant effects on bank performance. A transparent fee structure should be implemented to ensure that audit fees are reasonably justified and contribute to the institutions' overall financial health and regulatory compliance. This structure should clearly outline how audit fees are determined, considering factors such as the bank's size, the complexity of its operations, the level of risk involved, and any special compliance needs. Regular benchmarking should be conducted to compare fees with similar institutions, ensuring competitiveness and fairness through Bangladesh Bank circulation. Encouraging banks to negotiate multi-year contracts with audit firms can provide cost savings and fee stability over the contract period. These agreements should include clauses allowing fee adjustments based on changes in the bank's operation size or regulatory changes. Additionally, a cap on annual increases in audit fees should be introduced to prevent sudden and unreasonable fee escalations, aligning this cap with inflation rates or average industry fee increases. Enhancing the audit committee's role in overseeing audit fee negotiations should be introduced in the corporate governance code to ensure that fees are fair and justified (Alzeban, 2015). The committee should have the authority to approve audit fees and review the detailed breakdown of costs provided by the auditors. Promoting standardization in audit practices across the banking sector can reduce variability in audit processes and fees, leading to more predictable and justifiable audit costs (Bouaziz et al., 2020). Finally, maintaining clear and open communication with stakeholders about audit fees and the factors influencing them helps build trust and understanding regarding the rationale behind the fees.

For director fees, a competitive fee structure should be aligned with those of comparable regional institutions to ensure competitiveness and attract high-quality talent.

Benchmarking data from similar-sized banks in similar markets should be used. Implementing a director compensation component linked to the bank's performance, such as bonuses based on achieving specific financial targets, customer satisfaction scores, or operational goals, can also be beneficial (Jensen and Murphy, 1990). Disclosing the breakdown of director fees in annual reports, including base fees, bonuses, and other compensations such as stock options or retirement benefits, helps build trust with shareholders and stakeholders. Introducing a cap on total remuneration for directors can prevent excessive payouts, and this cap could be a multiple of the average salary of the bank's employees to maintain a reasonable compensation ratio. Regular reviews of director fees by an independent remuneration committee should be established, and fees should be adjusted based on the bank's performance, changes in the economic environment, and benchmarking market research.

Designing balanced compensation packages for CEO remuneration that balance fixed salaries with variable components is essential. Variable components should be tied to long-term performance metrics and strategic objectives, such as ROE, non-performing loan ratios, or market share growth. Including long-term incentive plans like stock options or restricted shares that vest over several years can align the CEO's interests with long-term shareholders and encourage retention (Johnson and Zhao, 2021). Implementing clawback provisions in the compensation contract allows the bank to reclaim bonuses or other variable compensation in the event of financial restatement or misconduct. Conducting annual performance reviews of the CEO, assessing against predefined objectives, and adjusting remuneration based on performance outcomes ensures accountability and performance alignment. Involving stakeholders in the remuneration process by allowing shareholder votes on executive pay packages, known as "say on pay," encourages transparency and shareholder engagement. Setting reasonable caps on severance packages to avoid overly generous payouts upon

departure, in line with industry standards and reflecting the duration of service and contributions made by the CEO, is also recommended. Ensuring detailed disclosure of all elements of CEO compensation in the annual report, including salary, bonuses, non-monetary benefits, and the rationale behind each component, promotes transparency and trust (Donaldson and Davis 2017).

By adopting these recommendations, banks can better align director and CEO remuneration with shareholder interests and the institution's long-term success while maintaining competitive and fair compensation practices.

6.3.4 Recommendation for ownership structure

The study found that the minimal impact of increased director or CEO share ownership on performance and the mixed effects of institutional and public shareholding indicate that the current stipulations regarding ownership and stakeholder engagement in the governance code may not sufficiently enhance performance. This highlights the need for more tailored approaches considering the broader institutional environment and active engagement strategies. Several vital policies are recommended to optimise the ownership structure in the Bangladeshi banking sector to balance regulatory compliance, enhance corporate governance, and promote financial stability.

Firstly, promoting a diverse shareholding composition is crucial. Encouraging a balanced mix of public, private, and institutional investors can enhance governance and reduce the risk of excessive influence by any single entity. This diversity can lead to more robust decision-making and mitigate potential conflicts of interest (La Porta et al. 2002). Additionally, implementing thresholds for maximum ownership by a single entity or related parties can prevent over-concentration of control, which can lead to governance issues and conflicts of interest (Abdallah and Ismail, 2017).

Regarding institutional investors, their role should be more active. Institutional investors should be encouraged to engage actively in governance through regular interactions with management and participation in board meetings, fostering transparency and accountability (Bhattacharya and Graham, 2009). Policies that incentivise long-term investments by institutional shareholders can align their interests with the sustainable growth of banks, promoting stability and long-term value creation (Haque and Shahid, 2016). Setting a cap on institutional ownership helps maintain national control over banks while still benefiting from international expertise and capital. An investment in the banking sector under clear regulatory guidelines ensures that these investments contribute positively to the sector's stability and growth.

A strategic reduction of government shareholding in state-owned banks is recommended for government and public ownership. This gradual reduction can introduce more market-driven governance practices without disrupting the sector's stability (Megginson and Netter, 2001). Mechanisms that increase public participation in bank investments, such as mutual funds or public offerings, can diversify the investor base and spread economic benefits more widely (Roe, 2003).

Implementing Employee Stock Ownership Plans (ESOPs) can align the interests of employees with those of the bank, improving motivation and loyalty and potentially enhancing performance (Blasi, Kruse, and Freeman, 2009). ESOPs can make employees more invested in the bank's success, leading to better performance outcomes.

Minority shareholder protections are essential for fostering trust and engagement. Enhanced disclosure requirements for actions affecting minority shareholders ensure full transparency and accountability from controlling shareholders (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). Mechanisms facilitating greater participation of minority shareholders in decision-making

processes, such as electronic voting and the ability to participate in meetings remotely, can ensure their voices are heard and their interests protected (Aggarwal et al., 2011).

Finally, improving stakeholder engagement through enhanced disclosure for minority interests and investing in digital participation tools can broaden shareholder participation in meetings through digital platforms, allowing for remote voting and real-time interaction (Huang and Kisgen, 2019). This approach promotes inclusivity and transparency, building trust among all stakeholders.

By adopting these recommendations, banks in Bangladesh can create a more balanced and effective ownership structure, improving governance, fostering financial stability, and enhancing overall performance.

6.3.5 Additional recommendations for policymakers

6.3.5.1 General Suggestions for Financial and Non-Financial Institutions

A multifaceted approach is required, encompassing updates to the corporate governance code to provide enhanced transparency for directorships, targeted strategies for family-owned businesses, and strengthened corporate governance in Bangladesh's financial and non-financial institutions.

Firstly, updating the corporate governance code to include more straightforward compliance rules and stringent penalties for non-compliance is essential. Both domestic and international research should inform these updates to ensure the code remains relevant and practical, mirroring successful practices observed in India and Indonesia (Perera and Gunasekara, 2021; Widjaja, 2020). The disclosure of non-executive directors' identities and qualifications should be mandated to enhance transparency and provide a more accurate measure of board performance (Smith and Williams, 2019).

Introducing specific governance provisions is crucial for family-owned businesses, which are prevalent in Bangladesh. These provisions should tackle common compliance challenges and financial discrepancies to ensure accountability and transparency (Khan and Jain, 2018). Additionally, establishing a robust whistleblower protection framework is necessary to safeguard individuals who report misconduct, with companies encouraged to educate their employees on safe reporting practices to prevent retaliation (Johnson, 2021).

The enforcement of governance laws needs strengthening through the effective identification and penalisation of non-compliant companies. Consideration should also be given to implementing a fair system for assessing fines and incentives like tax breaks to encourage reporting misconduct (Lee and Kim, 2018). Promoting a chartered director programme that requires certification through accredited courses would enhance director competency, necessitating collaboration among federal bodies, educational institutions, and industry professionals (Huang and Wright, 2019).

Another critical measure is expanding the nominating committee's role to ensure a formal and transparent process for director appointments. This process should involve regular reviews of board composition to align with strategic needs (Taylor et al. 2020). Formal training for directors and board members, mandated and provided by regulatory bodies such as Bangladesh Bank and BSEC, would ensure they are well-equipped to address new governance challenges (Nguyen, 2021). Lastly, rigorous monitoring of the governance code implementation and promoting ethical behaviour within organisations should be pursued through ongoing campaigns and recognition programmes (Martin and Thomas, 2022).

These recommendations aim to reinforce corporate governance standards in Bangladesh, fostering an environment that upholds ethical practices and robust regulatory oversight. By adopting these strategies, policymakers can enhance the transparency,

accountability, and overall effectiveness of governance practices across various sectors within the country.

6.3.5.2 Recommendations for Policymakers and Regulators

To enhance corporate governance in Bangladesh, policymakers and regulators should spearhead reforms by updating the SEC Guidelines of Corporate Governance to meet evolving needs (Smith, 2020). Capacity building within the SEC and other regulatory bodies must be prioritised to enhance their ability to enforce governance standards effectively (Jones et al., 2019). The banking sector should address detrimental changes in the Banking Company Act by reversing policies that promote crony capitalism, such as extended board tenures and increased family board membership (Chowdhury, 2021). Taxpayer funds should no longer be used to bail out failing state-owned banks, and non-political appointments of board members based on expertise should be ensured (Lee and Kim, 2018).

Loan categorisation criteria should be revised to identify better and penalise wilful defaulters, granting banks the authority to change defaulting companies' boards (Brown, 2022). Establishing a Corporate Governance Institute with regulatory authority to oversee the implementation of the Governance Code, provide compliance guidance, and support companies in maintaining good governance practices is recommended (White, 2019). Educational programmes should be regularly updated and aligned with industry needs to provide companies with skilled workers. Supporting faculty development and regulating the educational process can prevent commercial exploitation (Kumar, 2020).

Regulatory oversight frameworks must be robust to monitor and regulate ownership structures, preventing adverse impacts on competition and financial stability (Greenwood and Scharfstein, 2020). Periodic reviews of the impact of ownership structures on the banking sector's performance and stability should be conducted, making policy adjustments based on

empirical evidence and market conditions (Taylor, 2018). Enhancing disclosure requirements for banks regarding significant shareholders and changes in ownership structure in their annual reports and on their websites will improve transparency (Harris and Raviv, 2021).

A comprehensive risk management framework that includes cybersecurity, operational risks, and compliance with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards should be established (Martin, 2019). Banks should be required to develop and publish a clear ESG strategy that includes targets for reducing environmental impact and enhancing community engagements, with mandated sustainability reporting based on international standards like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) or Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) (Nguyen, 2020).

Finally, establishing a Governance Oversight Committee at the board level to monitor the implementation of the governance code and recommend updates is crucial. Conducting an annual review of governance practices to adapt to new challenges and incorporating stakeholder feedback into the code's evolution will ensure continuous improvement and relevance of the governance framework (Smith, 2020)

6.4 Implementation strategy for reformed corporate governance code for Bangladesh banks

A comprehensive and strategic implementation plan is vital to bolster corporate governance in Bangladesh. This plan spans several phases, each with specific objectives and timelines, designed to align with international best practices and address local market needs.

Phase 1: Regulatory Update and Strategic Framework Establishment

This initial phase, set to be completed within two months, focuses on updating the SEC Guidelines of Corporate Governance. The objective is to revise these guidelines to reflect the latest international standards, incorporating clear compliance rules and stringent penalties for non-compliance. Collaboration with international governance experts will help benchmark these updates against successful models globally (Smith, 2020).

Phase 2: Capacity Building and Institutional Development

Spanning the first four months, this phase aims to enhance the capabilities of regulatory bodies and financial institutions. It includes developing training programmes for personnel within the SEC and other regulatory entities to enhance their monitoring and enforcement capabilities. A certification programme for directors and board members will also be launched, focusing on governance, risk management, and ethical leadership. A Corporate Governance Institute will also be established to provide ongoing support, research, and guidance as suggested by (Jones et al., 2019; Huang and Wright, 2019).

Phase 3: Structural Reforms and Transparency Enhancement

During the fifth and sixth months, the plan addresses critical reforms in the banking sector to reverse policies promoting crony capitalism, such as extended board tenures and increased family board membership. Enhanced disclosure requirements for significant shareholders and board changes will be mandated, alongside robust whistleblower protections, to encourage reporting of misconduct and protect whistleblowers (Chowdhury, 2021; Smith and Williams, 2019; Johnson, 2021).

Phase 4: Risk Management and Compliance Strengthening

In the seventh and eighth months, the focus shifts to strengthening risk management practices and compliance. An integrated risk management framework covering cybersecurity and ESG standards will be developed. Compliance audits will increase in frequency and scope, utilising advanced analytical tools, and compliance officers will receive training on the latest strategies and regulations (Martin, 2019; Nguyen, 2021).

Phase 5: Sustainability Integration and Stakeholder Engagement

From the ninth months onwards, sustainability will be integrated into corporate strategies. Banks and financial institutions will be required to develop and publish clear ESG strategies with specific targets. A Governance Oversight Committee will be established to monitor the reforms' implementation and integrate stakeholder feedback into continuous revisions (Nguyen, 2020; Martin and Thomas, 2022).

Phase 6: Review and Continuous Improvement

Ten months onward, the phase will ensure that the strategic plan remains dynamic and responsive. A new corporate governance code will be circulated, and periodic reviews will assess the impact of different governance practices on financial stability and performance, with policies and training programmes adjusted based on empirical evidence and feedback (Taylor, 2018).

Monitoring and Evaluation

The effectiveness of the implementation will be monitored through various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as compliance rates with new governance standards, the

effectiveness of training programmes, stakeholder feedback on transparency and engagement efforts, and financial performance metrics post-reform from month twelve onward.

This structured approach ensures that Bangladesh's corporate governance reforms are implemented systematically and adjusted continuously to meet evolving needs and challenges. By doing so, Bangladesh can enhance transparency, accountability, and efficiency across its financial and corporate sectors, ultimately bolstering investor confidence and contributing to economic stability and growth.

6.5 Significance of the Findings

The research conducted on corporate governance in Bangladesh's banking sector is significant due to its comprehensive examination of governance mechanisms and their influence on bank performance. The findings of this study are critical as they illuminate the real-world application and efficacy of corporate governance frameworks in Bangladesh, addressing a gap highlighted by previous research. For instance, researchers like Al-Mamun and Rahman (2019) and Hoque et al. (2017) have examined aspects of governance but have often concentrated on individual governance elements such as board structure and CEO compensation. In contrast, this study evaluates a comprehensive range of governance mechanisms, offering a holistic view of the system's strengths and weaknesses.

The research is particularly timely given the historical challenges identified within Bangladesh's banking sector, including significant financial scandals and governance failures that have undermined economic stability and growth (Akhter, 2019; Ferdous, 2012). By examining the entire spectrum of corporate governance code, the study aligns with the call by Letza et al. (2008) for a realistic appraisal of governance models that transcend the traditional shareholder versus stakeholder dichotomy, suggesting a multi-theoretical approach to better suit local conditions.

6.5.1 Contribution to Academic and Practical Fields

Academically, the study enriches the discourse on corporate governance in emerging markets, which is often underrepresented in global governance literature. It challenges the effectiveness of the one-size-fits-all approach in governance by integrating various theoretical frameworks such as stakeholder, stewardship, and institutional theories. This is in response to the need for more nuanced governance models in countries with unique socio-economic and legal landscapes as suggested by Siddiqui and Uddin (2016) and Rahman et al. (2018).

Practically, the research provides actionable insights that could enhance governance practices within Bangladeshi banks and potentially attract more international investment. The comprehensive understanding of governance mechanisms and their impacts as presented in this study could aid policymakers and regulators in refining the existing corporate governance code to better address the specific needs and challenges of the banking sector.

Furthermore, the study's findings contribute to the broader policy discussion by offering evidence-based recommendations for improving governance frameworks. This could lead to more robust regulatory and accountability structures, addressing the enforcement gaps identified by Haque and Azmat (2022) and Hossain et al. (2018).

6.5.1.1 Policy Implications and Recommendations

The evidence from this study suggests the need for ongoing revisions and updates to the Corporate Governance Code, similar to practices in other jurisdictions like Indonesia, where governance codes are regularly evaluated and updated (National Committee on Governance, Indonesia). These updates should reflect both international best practices and the unique context of Bangladesh to ensure that governance reforms are both effective and relevant.

Additionally, this study underscores the importance of developing a culture of compliance within corporations, which requires regulatory changes and educational initiatives to enhance the understanding of governance among corporate executives and boards. As part of the regulatory framework, implementing comprehensive governance education and training could significantly improve compliance rates and governance effectiveness.

In conclusion, this research significantly advances the understanding of how corporate governance mechanisms are implemented within Bangladesh's banking sector and their effectiveness. It offers a detailed critique and constructive recommendations that could lead to more robust governance frameworks, essential for sustainable economic growth and financial stability in emerging markets. By bridging the gaps identified in previous studies and suggesting practical policy changes, the study provides a valuable roadmap for future governance reforms in Bangladesh and similar contexts.

6.6 Limitation

The research provided an in-depth analysis of the corporate governance structure within Bangladesh's banking system, evaluating its effectiveness and alignment with the operational realities and challenges of the sector. While the findings reveal adherence to several international governance standards, they also highlight areas where the current frameworks might fall short of fully supporting effective governance practices within Bangladesh's unique banking environment.

6.6.1 Key Findings and Limitations

The study utilised data from 198 samples across 33 banks over six years, providing a substantial, albeit limited, perspective on the effectiveness of corporate governance in these

institutions. It is essential to recognise that the small sample size may restrict the generalizability of the results, particularly to privately held companies and smaller banks where governance structures and challenges might differ.

Additionally, the shift from a planned mixed-methods approach to a solely quantitative analysis, necessitated by the COVID-19 pandemic, likely limited the depth of insights into the qualitative aspects of corporate governance. This shift underscores the need for future research to incorporate qualitative data to capture more nuanced aspects of governance, such as board dynamics, stakeholder perceptions, and the cultural context within which these banks operate.

6.6.2 Methodological and Definitional Limitations

The study faced further limitations in the definition and categorisation of key variables. The absence of detailed differentiation in ownership patterns, such as distinguishing between foreign and local sponsor-directors' shareholdings and categorising institutional shareholdings as domestic or international, may have prevented a deeper understanding of how different ownership structures influence governance practices. Additionally, the broad categorisation of stakeholders without consideration of the specific roles or influences unique to different types of companies might have skewed the understanding of stakeholder impacts on governance.

6.6.3 Implications for Practice and Policy

Despite these limitations, the research provides valuable insights that can inform both practice and policy. For instance, the findings suggest a need for more tailored governance codes that consider the specific needs and challenges of the Bangladeshi banking sector, particularly in adapting to rapid changes in the global banking environment. There is also a

clear indication of the need for ongoing training and capacity building within regulatory bodies like the SEC to enhance their ability to effectively monitor and enforce governance standards.

6.6.4 Recommendations for Future Research

Given these limitations, the study suggests that while the current corporate governance frameworks in Bangladesh's banking sector align with several international standards, they may not fully address or adapt to the nuanced needs of the local banking landscape. Future research should aim to incorporate a more detailed categorisation of ownership and stakeholder types, expand the sample size, and utilise mixed methods to capture a richer dataset. This would enable a more detailed assessment of how well the corporate governance structures fit with the operational realities of Bangladesh's banking system, potentially guiding more targeted and effective governance reforms.

In conclusion, while the current corporate governance frameworks in Bangladesh's banking system align with many international standards, there is significant room for improvement to ensure they fully support effective governance tailored to the specific needs of the local banking sector.

6.7 Conclusion

The study on corporate governance in Bangladesh indicates that the nation's governance structures are still developing. There is a noticeable progression toward a culture of compliance over time, though initial compliance with the Corporate Governance Code appears limited. This initial observation might seem disheartening, but it becomes more encouraging when considering the organisational obstacles encountered. Given the nascent state of Bangladesh's corporate governance infrastructure, it is unrealistic to expect local

firms to immediately achieve the high standards observed in more developed economies where corporate governance systems are more robust.

Despite these challenges, the study reveals a somewhat tentative acceptance of the Code within Bangladesh's business community. While the research does not aim to broadly criticise the Code's effectiveness, it does acknowledge specific implementation issues related to information dissemination and communication barriers. These issues might make the regulations seem burdensome and obscure, which could hinder compliance efforts. Nonetheless, there is potential for achieving higher compliance through addressing these governance concerns and refining the Code's provisions based on the study's findings.

While Bangladesh faces enduring economic and social challenges, it is heartening to note the government's persistent efforts to enhance governance systems. Initiatives such as the SEC's establishment of a corporate governance section, ICAB's enhanced audit quality functions, and UGC's new governance standards are promising. These efforts are gradually improving the country's governance landscape, although significant issues such as audit fees, government officials' pay structures, political influences in legal processes, and the quality of primary and legal education still need attention. The recent governmental measures, however, are expected to positively impact corporate governance shortly.

Furthermore, it's evident that the appetite for improved governance is not isolated but a common desire across various sectors as demonstrated by the extensive knowledge and understanding of the respondents. The ongoing commitment and proactive attitudes towards reform are crucial for sustainable progress.

Bangladesh's introduction to its Corporate Governance Code has been met with challenges but also presents a significant opportunity for positive change. To keep the Code relevant and effective, its provisions must be regularly updated to meet both local and

international standards. The willingness of companies to comply with the Code should guide whether additional regulatory standards by the Ministry of Commerce, SEC, and other entities should be enforced.

Moreover, enhancing corporate governance education is vital alongside legal and regulatory frameworks. Authorities should simplify the Code and SEC Guidelines to facilitate compliance and help firms recognise the benefits of adhering to these standards. Embracing a governance model in name only is insufficient; the real value comes from genuine compliance, whether mandatory or voluntary.

In conclusion, for Bangladesh, the path forward involves legislative and regulatory adjustments and a broad cultural shift towards recognising and integrating effective corporate governance practices as foundational to business operations. This shift is essential for the country's economic and social development, making corporate governance a legal necessity and a core aspect of business strategy.

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8 Appendix

Data collected from the following banks.		
Number	Bank name	Year Range
1.	AB bank	2012-2017
2.	AL-arafah islamic bank	2012-2017
3.	Agrani bank	2012-2017
4.	Bank Asia	2012-2017
5.	Basic bank	2012-2017
6.	Brac bank	2012-2017
7.	City bank	2012-2017
8.	Dhaka bank	2012-2017
9.	Dutch Bangla bank	2012-2017
10.	Eastern bank	2012-2017
11.	Exim bank	2012-2017
12.	First Security Islami bank	2012-2017
13.	ICB Islamic bank	2012-2017
14.	IFIC Bank	2012-2017
15.	Islami Bank Bangladesh	2012-2017
16.	Jamuna bank	2012-2017
17.	Megna bank	2012-2017
18.	Mercantile bank	2012-2017
19.	Midland bank	2012-2017
20.	Mutual trust bank	2012-2017
21.	National Credit and Commerce bank	2012-2017
22.	National bank	2012-2017
23.	One bank	2012-2017
24.	Premier bank	2012-2017
25.	Prime bank	2012-2017
26.	Pubali bank	2012-2017
27.	Rupali bank	2012-2017
28.	Shahjalal Islami bank	2012-2017
29.	Social Islami bank	2012-2017
30.	Standard bank	2012-2017
31.	Trust bank	2012-2017
32.	United Commercial bank	2012-2017
33.	Uttara bank	2012-2017

